

ELUCIDATING THE ROLE OF PAR2 IN BRONCHIAL SMOOTH MUSCLE IN COPD

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By Kimberly Black BSc (Hons)

Under the supervision of Dr Gary Litherland & Co-
supervision of Prof. John Lockhart & Dr Andrew MacKenzie

Collaboration establishment: Dundalk Institute of
Technology, Queen's University Belfast, University of
Glasgow

Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis has been composed by myself and that it has not been submitted for any comparable academic degree award. The work contained within this thesis has been carried out independently, except where specifically indicated and all sources of information provided acknowledged by reference. The work carried out for the fulfilment of this thesis was carried out at the University of the West of Scotland, Dundalk Institute of Technology and University of Glasgow.

Kimberly Black, April 2022

Dedication

I dedicate the research work carried out within this project to my loving family for always supporting me in all my endeavours. Finally, it is dedicated to the COPD patients around the world who everyday battle this disease and continue to inspire with their resilience and bravery.

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Abstract

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a multifactorial condition encompassing chronic bronchitis & emphysema. Characterised by progressive airflow limitation & chronic inflammation, COPD is currently the third leading cause of death worldwide and there is an urgent unmet clinical need for improved treatments.

Proliferation, hypertrophy, and hyper-contractility of bronchial smooth muscle (BSM) are key features of COPD, and current treatments focus on bronchodilation to improve airflow. Proteinase-activated receptor-2 (PAR2) is a promising therapeutic target that plays a key role in multiple inflammatory pathologies and is associated with airway hypersensitisation and inflammation in asthma. Protective bronchodilatory roles for PAR2 have also been described, thus the overall contribution of PAR2 to respiratory disease, particularly COPD, is unclear.

This study investigated putative PAR2 roles in BSM phenotype, function, and pathogenic mechanisms, including COPD-relevant contexts of oxidative stress and ageing. Since an important COPD co-morbidity is rheumatoid arthritis (RA), lung pathology in a murine RA model, collagen-induced arthritis (CIA) was also explored.

PAR2 activation induced significant and concentration-dependent calcium mobilisation in human BSM cells (hBSMC), consistent with a direct role in regulation of BSM contractility. In *ex vivo* murine airway rings, PAR2 activation elicited a substantial dilatory effect on pre-contracted tissue, which was comparable in both sexes and abolished in PAR2-deficient tissue.

PAR2-dependent relaxation of both bronchi and trachea was enhanced following induction of oxidative stress, concomitant with increased PAR2 expression, and was inhibited by exogenous superoxide dismutase. Oxidative conditions also increased collagen abundance throughout murine lung tissue. Baseline collagen levels and smooth muscle actin expression were increased in PAR2-deficient tissue.

PAR2-dependent bronchodilation was reduced in older mice, as was PAR2 expression. There was a modest decrease in smooth muscle actin (SMA) in tissues from older wild-type mice, whereas SMA expression was reduced in PAR2-deficient airways regardless of age. Collagen abundance was increased with age, whereas in age-matched PAR2-deficient samples SMA expression was reduced.

Murine CIA led to strikingly reduced lung tissue density, reflected in decreased alveolar septal width and tissue cell density, whilst a trend toward increased small airway thickness was observed. CIA parenchyma exhibited increased collagen levels, consistent with early fibrosis, whilst arterioles exhibited decreased SMA. Neutrophil elastase was increased in CIA, whilst PAR2 was unchanged or decreased.

In conclusion, PAR2 plays a key role in regulating bronchodilation that, importantly, is enhanced in oxidative stress but decreased in age. These findings, along with the influence of PAR2 on lung collagen and SMA levels, may inform possible future PAR2-directed therapeutic strategies for COPD and related pathologies. This study also reveals striking lung changes during murine inflammatory arthritis, offering the potential to model RA lung pathology and perhaps illuminate mechanisms underpinning RA-COPD co-morbidity.

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Abbreviations

ACh	Acetylcholine
ASM	Airway Smooth Muscle
ASMCs	Airway Smooth Muscle Cells
BSM	Bronchial Smooth Muscle
CAFO	Concentrated Animal Feeding Organisations
CCh	Carbachol
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
COX	Cyclooxygenase
DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagles Medium
ELISA	Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay
FBS	Foetal Bovine Serum
FLIGRLO	2-Furoyl-Leu-Ile-Gly-Arg-Leu-Orn-NH ₂ – PAR2 agonist peptide
FOLIGRL	2-Furoyl-Orn-Leu-Ile-Gly-Arg-Leu-NH ₂ – PAR2 agonist scrambled peptide
HEPES	4-2-Hydroxyethy-1-piperazine ethanesulfonic acid
IL	Interleukin
LABAs	Long-Acting Beta Agonists
LAMAs	Long-Acting Muscarinic Antagonists
LBW	Low Birth Weight
MMP	Matrix Metalloproteinase
NO	Nitric Oxide
NOS	Nitric Oxide Synthase
NSAIDs	Non-Steroidal anti-inflammatory Drugs
PAR	Proteinase Activated Receptor
PG	Prostaglandin
RP	Reverse Peptide
SP	Scrambled Peptide
SABAs	Short Acting Beta Agonists
SAMAs	Short Acting Muscarinic Antagonists
SLIGKV-NH ₂	Ser-Leu-Ile-Gly-Lys-Val-NH ₂ -PAR2 agonist peptide
TGF-β	Transforming Growth Factor-β
TNF-α	Tumour Necrosis Factor-α
ROI	Region of Interest

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

1.1 Characterisation

The American Thoracic Society (ATS) defines chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) as a disease state characterised by the presence of airflow obstruction due to chronic bronchitis or emphysema (Hnizdo & Vallyathan, 2017). COPD is associated with structural remodelling, hypersensitivity, hypercontractility and alterations in the airway which in turn lead to irreversible airway obstruction (Ricciardolo et al, 2017).

1.2 GOLD standard definition

The Global Initiative for chronic obstructive lung disease (GOLD) defined COPD as: “a common, preventable and treatable disease that is characterized by persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow limitation that is due to airway and/or alveolar abnormalities usually caused by significant exposure to noxious particles or gases.” (GOLD, 2018). However, the fact there is no treatment available to reverse or cure COPD supports further research into the underlying mechanisms to identify novel therapeutic targets.

1.3 Diagnosis

COPD is often undiagnosed due to patients under-reporting symptoms; it is known as a ‘silent killer’ as death can result without recognition of prior symptoms (Rodríguez-Roisin and Soriano, 2008). In any patient who has chronic cough or increased mucus production and/or a history of exposure to risk factors associated with disease, COPD should be taken into consideration. In order to confirm a diagnosis of COPD, a noninvasive physical measurement of lung function using the method of spirometry is required (Buist *et al.*, 2007). The presence of a post-bronchodilator forced expiratory volume/forced vital capacity (FEV₁/FVC) <0.70 confirms the presence of persistent airflow limitation (Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017). Peak expiratory flow measurement alone cannot be reliably used as the only diagnostic test because of its weak specificity, despite good sensitivity (Jackson and Hubbard, 2003). Other key indicators which are indicative for diagnosis of COPD include recurrent lower respiratory tract infections, history of risk factors and potentially a family history of COPD and/or childhood factors (Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017).

1.4 Biomarkers

COPD biomarkers are required for improved diagnosis, classification of disease state and prediction of exacerbations. There have been several studies over the last decade which have focused on identifying novel biomarkers of COPD (Chen, Leung and Sin, 2016; Mannino, 2019; Stockley *et al.*, 2019). Despite recent attempts at identifying candidate biomarkers and creating biomarker profiles for COPD, there is still a significant lack of reliable biomarkers available, which complicates refinement of patient care with respect to the extent of disease (Truedsson *et al.*, 2016).

1.5 Clinical symptoms & exacerbations

The most common respiratory symptoms of COPD include cough, wheezing and mucus hyperproduction and in some cases these symptoms may be under-reported by COPD patients. Lives of patients with the disease may be disrupted for periods of time with acute worsening of these symptoms, known as exacerbations (Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017). These exacerbations lead to more frequent hospitalisations, an impaired quality of life and an increase in the severity of the disease (Celli *et al.*, 2004). Exacerbations can be triggered by a diversity of factors such as bacterial or viral infections, or even a change in weather (MacIntyre & Huang, 2008).

1.6 Epidemiology & risk factors

COPD is a significant and ever-increasing medical and societal burden in both developed and developing countries, yet there are no successful strategies to prevent this disease and very few effective at management and treatment (Ambrosino & Simonds, 2007). COPD is currently the third leading cause of death in the world (OECD and European Commission, 2016). Globally, the COPD burden is

anticipated to rise in coming years based on the continued exposure to COPD risk factors and aging of the population (Mathers & Loncar, 2006). Upwards of 3 million people died of COPD in 2012, accounting for 6 % of all deaths globally (Lozano *et al.*, 2012). Despite being known primarily as a smoker’s disease, COPD is in fact multifactorial (Douthwaite *et al.*, 2017), with a multiplicity of causes and risk factors (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1 Risk Factors considered to contribute to the onset of COPD. COPD is a multifactorial disease and the risk factors identified in this figure allow an understanding of the wide range of possible contributions to disease pathology. Factors such as cigarette smoke, and oxidative stress causing a protease imbalance from environmental and occupational exposures, are believed to contribute to disease pathology. Similarly, exposure to these factors from an early onset, along with genetic factors can predispose to respiratory problems and later progression to disease pathology. Accelerated ageing can also contribute to the progression of COPD. Image created using Biorender.

1.6.1 Smoking

The World Health Organisation advised, one hundred million deaths were caused by tobacco in the 20th century and with a rising trend set to continue, there will be up to one billion deaths due to tobacco use in the 21st century (2021). Around the world, cigarette smoke is the most common encountered risk factor for COPD. However, for reasons that are still unclear, not all smokers will develop COPD, and conversely some non-smokers are known to develop the disease (Vestbo *et al.*, 2013). Cigarette smoke comprises an exceedingly high concentration of oxidants and thus the reactive oxygen species generated by smoking induces inflammation in the lung and airways. Smokers have thus been shown to exhibit chronic inflammatory changes such as an increased number of specific inflammatory cell types in various parts of the lung, and structural changes/remodelling from repeated injury and repair (Laniado-Laborín, 2009).

1.6.2 Ageing

Ageing has been defined as ‘the progressive decline of homeostasis that occurs after the reproductive phase of life is complete, causing in increased risk of disease or death’ (Ito, Colley and Mercado, 2012). Typical ageing characteristics which are observed in patients with COPD include epigenetic alterations, mitochondrial dysfunction, loss of proteostasis and genomic instability (Mercado *et al.*, 2015). The natural ageing process results in a loss of lung elasticity which subsequently leads to an enlargement of the alveolar ducts, typically this is referred to as ‘senile emphysema’. COPD shows age-associated features such as an increase in oxidative stress, alterations of the extracellular matrix, and an increase in cellular senescence all of which provide supporting evidence that accelerated ageing is a driving mechanism in the disease (Mercado *et al.*, 2015). Thus, understanding the mechanisms of accelerated ageing in COPD may identify novel therapeutic approaches and treatments.

Cellular senescence, which is the state of irreversible growth arrest is of particular interest in COPD. The triggering mechanisms such as telomere shortening, oxidative stress, oncogene activation and constant DNA damage have been identified as key drivers (Chilosi *et al.*, 2013). Once DNA damage can no longer be repaired the cells lose the potential to replicate which subsequently results in cell cycle arrest. The harmful aspect of senescent cells is that they remain metabolically active which results in alterations to their environment for as long as they remain and display what is known as a senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP) (Mercado *et al.*, 2015). Senescent cells secrete a vast array of harmful inflammatory mediators, which provoke changes in the neighbouring tissues with subsequent negative impact on the whole organism (Mercado, Ito, Barnes, 2015).

1.6.3 Occupational exposure

Work-based exposure is a highly important risk factor for COPD due to the extensive range of historical occupations which involved respiratory toxins, with minimal provision of personal protective equipment (Hnizdo & Vallyathan, 2017). Angle-grinding is an occupation which historically may not have been associated with risk of damage to the respiratory system, however silica dust is one of the most important work-related respiratory pollutants. A review of epidemiological and pathological data in COPD considered the effect of occupational exposure to silica dust (Hnizdo & Vallyathan, 2017).

Another occupation which poses a health threat and a potential cause/risk for COPD is concentrated animal feeding operations (CAFOs) in modern agriculture. This working environment sees a vast array of harmful proteases and particles released into a confined area which poses a harmful threat to the respiratory system of the employees in that area (Heederik *et al.*, 2007). Alongside CAFOs having an impact on the employees, it also has an impact on communities in close proximity to the facilities (Donham *et al.*, 2007). Degrading manure produces volatile toxic gases which include ammonia and hydrogen sulphide, with both short and long-term health consequences possible from these substances. Dust particles and bacterial toxins in manure dust can exacerbate asthma and directly affect respiratory health (Phang, 2013), but this has been under-researched in terms of COPD. Farming is an identified occupation with associated possible risk to damage of the respiratory system potentially leading to COPD. In numerous developing and developed countries, many farmers spray pesticides on to their fields without any form of protective clothing/respiratory mask (Elliott & Essen, 2016).

1.6.4 Environmental factors

Inhalation of oxidants resulting from environmental exposures other than those discussed above is also thought to cause chronic inflammation, remodelling of the small airways and damage of lung parenchyma, leading to COPD (Maestrelli *et al.*, 2001). Another review by (Cosio, Saetta & Agustí, 2009) emphasised the role inflammation has in response to inhaled particles and pollutants in the pathogenesis of COPD. A study in 2017 explored a range of activities, all of which could be probable environmental contributors to the pathogenesis of COPD. Activities such as shovelling (particulates dispersion), cutting grass, cleaning with harmful chemicals, use of wood smoke fire, all could have a harmful impact on the respiratory system (Sama *et al.*, 2017). Importantly, there is also the increasingly topical problem of air pollution, which acts as a contributing factor to COPD disease exacerbations and thus hospital admissions (Lee, 2017). Indoor pollution also poses a risk: the use of biomass fuel is an important COPD risk factor particularly for women for in developing countries (Lee, 2017).

1.6.5 Early onset lung damage

There is mounting evidence to suggest that COPD is not solely a disease of old age largely restricted to heavy smokers, but it may also be linked with insults to the developing lung during foetal life and the first few years of postnatal life (Stocks & Sonnappa, 2013). While the frequency of maternal smoking during pregnancy has decreased during the past decade, it remains the key, potentially preventable, insult to the developing lung in addition to being a major cause of abrupt infant death, low birth weight (LBW), preterm delivery and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) (Hayatbakhsh *et al.*, 2009).

1.6.6 Genetic and environmental interactions

It has been known for a substantial period of time that genetic variants in the alpha-1 antitrypsin (AAT) gene serpin peptidase inhibitor clade A, member 1 (SERPINA1) can also lead to COPD (Berndt, *et al.*, 2012). This deficiency allows proteolytic enzymes to attack various tissues of the body, which results in destructive changes in the lung known as emphysema (Gooptu, Ekeowa and Lomas, 2008). However as this deficiency is responsible for a small portion of 1-2 % of all COPD cases, it is important to identify other contributors to the pathogenesis of COPD such as epigenetic changes and somatic mutations (Yao & Rahman, 2012). There is sufficient evidence to establish a familial pattern of COPD, however for several years it has been contended that this was largely related to frequent exposure to harmful toxins (Celli, 2012).

COPD fulfils the criteria for being a complex genetic disease with environmental factors interacting with multiple polymorphic genes to influence susceptibility (Silverman, Spira & Paré, 2009). Epigenetic mechanisms help regulate gene activity in mammalian cells and have historically been thought to be involved in developmental processes or contribute to disease states (Roth & Sweatt, 2011). The ever-growing field of epigenetics presents important potential because if gene expression is modifiable it could also be amendable to therapeutic targets and interventions (Celli, 2012). One study (Chuang *et al.*, 2017) identified 9 genome- (or exome) wide significant loci in studies of COPD. The loci and their protein function can be seen in Table 1.1 below.

Loci	Protein	Protein function	Citation
<i>HHIP</i>	Hedgehog Interaction protein	Embryonic development	(Zhao <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>CHRNA5</i>	Cholinergic receptor nicotinic alpha 5 subunit	Nicotinic acetylcholine receptor	(Diabasana <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>HTR4</i>	5-hydroxytryptamine receptor 4	Serotonin receptor	(Hodge <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
<i>FAM13A</i>	Family with sequence similarity 13 member A	Signalling GPCR & Rho GTPase	(Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
<i>RIN3</i>	Ras and Rab interactor 3	Vesicle mediated transport	(Janson <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
<i>TGFβ2</i>	Transforming growth factor beta-2	Produces TGF-β2	(Parker <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
<i>GSTCD-NPNT</i>	Glutathione S-Transferase C-terminal Domain containing	Cytochrome P450	(Henry <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
<i>CYP2A6</i>	Cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily A member 6	Cytochrome P450	(Bray <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>IL27-CCDC101</i>	Interleukin 27	IL27 formation	(Hobbs <i>et al.</i> , 2016)

Table 1.1 Susceptibility loci and related protein function identified by genome wide association and related studies.

1.7 Co-morbidities

There is evidence supporting a relationship between lung cancer and COPD via the genes *CHRNA3* (neuronal acetylcholine receptor subunit alpha 3), *CHRNA5* (nicotine acetylcholine receptor) positioned on chromosome 15 (Yoon *et al.*, 2010). However, in genetic investigations of both diseases, the reported gene associations can only account for 5 to 10 % of cases of development of lung cancer and/or COPD because gene expression is determined by several factors including environment (Schwartz *et al.*, 2011). Other COPD co-morbidities are osteoarthritis (OA) and cachexia, as these pathologies diminish physical activity (Calder *et al.*, 2018). It is worth noting that COPD and OA are both associated with increased social isolation and a diminution in quality of life (Wshah *et al.*, 2018). Among other COPD co-morbidities, cardiovascular diseases are among the most important, due to an increased risk for hospitalisation and mortality (Morgan *et al.*, 2018). A disease which is of particular interest in relation to its co-incidence with COPD is rheumatoid arthritis (RA). A recent population based study by (McGuire *et al.*, 2019) demonstrated a connection between COPD and inflammation,

which raises the question whether chronic inflammatory conditions such as RA predispose to COPD. An increase in attention to these comorbidities has been seen due to the reduction in quality of life and an increase in mortality (Dougados *et al.*, 2014; Han & Han, 2016). The study by McGuire (2019), revealed that COPD hospitalisations were more common in the RA cohort compared with the general populations. The potential relationship between RA and COPD is complex by the fact that smoking is a risk factor for both diseases. The magnitude of COPD risk in RA relative to the general population declined with age; this is likely related to higher baseline rates of COPD in older generations. The study ultimately showed that RA is significantly linked with a higher risk of incident COPD (McGuire *et al.*, 2019). Despite joint disease being the main presenter in RA, there are a number of extra-articular manifestations which includes inflammatory lung disease, termed RA-associated interstitial lung disease (RA-ILD) (Shaw *et al.*, 2015). It is interesting to speculate that RA-ILD may in fact be a prelude to COPD development in patients with RA. Figure 1.2 below illustrates the suggested links connecting both RA and lung disease, reviewed by Shaw and colleagues (Shaw *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1.2 Illustration of the concepts of the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis associated lung disease. Although the pathogenesis of RA related lung disease is not entirely understood, genetic predisposition and epigenetic factors are thought to have some involvement. As smoking is also a risk factor for RA and causes recurrent injury to the alveolar epithelium and changes in the cytokine environment. Citrullination of proteins also occurs resulting in the removal of an amino group, which subsequently affects the function of the protein. The inflammatory response observed in RA patients involves cytokines, chemokines, and growth factors. All of these mediators add to the differentiation and proliferation of fibroblasts, increased activity of metalloproteinases (MMP) and an increase in extracellular matrix (ECM) resulting in lung disease. The fibroblasts in the synovial lining play a comparable role in the pathogenesis of joint manifestations of RA and the increase in anti-CCP indicates an autoimmune link and is a strong indicator of RA. Figure was adapted from (Shaw *et al.*, 2015) and created using Biorender.

Studies by (Gan *et al.*, 2004; Kramer & Gaffen, 2007; Ruiz-Esquide *et al.*, 2012; Khawar, Abbasi & Sheikh, 2015) have all concluded the involvement of pro-inflammatory mediators IL-17, IL-32 and anti-citrullinated protein antibodies which contribute to RA, may also have a role in COPD pathogenesis.

In patients with RA, emphysema is thought to develop following the induction of destructive airway disease (Jacob *et al.*, 2018). The causes which underly this mechanism and the high incidence of airway lesions remain unclear; the emphysematous lung lesions noted in RA may largely be associated to an airway-centred destruction process (Sakai, 2018). Airway involvement has been reported to include both upper and distal small airways. The common manifestations reported include bronchiectasis and excess sputum production, bronchiolitis and airway hyperreactivity (Yunt & Solomon, 2015).

Bronchiectasis has been recognised in patients with RA for many decades, however the research area has been under investigated (Wilczynska, Condliffe & McKeon, 2013). The key mechanisms involved in the pathophysiology of bronchiectasis include recurrent infections, peribronchial fibrosis and of relevance to COPD, airway obstruction. Histological changes include features such as bronchial cartilage destruction and fibrosis, mucosal and mucosa gland hyperplasia and inflammatory cell infiltration (Bird & Memon, 2020).

1.8 Treatments and management

At present smoking cessation has the greatest capacity to influence the natural history of COPD (Vogelmeier *et al.*, 2017). To aid smoking cessation, pharmacological drugs such as nicotine replacement treatments (NRTs) are available for use: patches, gum, inhaler, nasal spray, lozenge tablets and oral spray (Chepkin *et al.*, 2018). In combination with counselling, these medications have been shown to be effective in even the most persistent smokers with COPD (Tonnesen, 2013).

Bronchodilators are medications that reduce airway resistance and thereby increase FEV₁ and/or change other spirometric variables. Most often in terms of COPD, bronchodilator medications are given on a regular basis to avert or reduce symptoms. A vast array of various types of bronchodilator are available such as short-acting and long-acting beta₂-agonists (SABAs and LABAs, respectively), and short-acting and long-acting antimuscarinics (SAMAs and LAMAs, respectively) (Appleton *et al.*, 2008). There are also combination bronchodilator therapies which comprise various bronchodilators with varying mechanisms and durations of action. This form of therapy increases the degree of bronchodilation whilst decreasing the risk of side-effects, in comparison with a higher dosage of a single bronchodilator (Cazzola and Molimard, 2010). Other types of inhaled treatments such as inhaled corticosteroids are used as an anti-inflammatory intervention in COPD and typically are used in conjunction with bronchodilators (Tashkin and Strange, 2018).

The mechanism of action of β₂-agonists is to relax airway smooth muscle via stimulation of β₂-adrenergic receptors. This subsequently causes an increase in the intracellular messenger cyclic AMP which has the principal role of controlling smooth muscle tone (Tashkin and Fabbri, 2010). Muscarinic agonists work in a reverse manner by blocking the broncho constrictive effect of acetylcholine on M₃ muscarinic receptors which are expressed in airway smooth muscle (Malerba *et al.*, 2019).

In cases where patients may have had an exacerbation or have severe resting hypoxemia, administration of oxygen (oxygen therapy) has been reported to increase survival in those with chronic respiratory failure (Cranston *et al.*, 2008). This also helps to relieve symptoms such as wheeziness and breathlessness. According to McCarthy and colleagues (2015), pulmonary rehabilitation also has been shown to benefit COPD sufferers and has been highlighted as the most effective therapeutic method to improve shortness of breath, overall health status and exercise tolerance (Mccarthy *et al.*, 2015). There is an array of treatment options available, all with various mechanisms of action and ways of alleviating symptoms, however to date there are no disease-modifying therapeutic strategies effective at disease reversal or cure. Thus, better COPD therapies can be viewed as a major and urgent unmet clinical need.

2. Airway Smooth Muscle

Smooth muscle forms part of the walls of many hollow organs and conduits and is structurally and functionally diverse in different contexts of the body. This muscle type reflects the specialised contractile requirements of these structures including blood vessels, airways, gut, bladder and uterus e.g. modulation of arterial tone, blood flow supply, the ability to control gastrointestinal and genitourinary tract motility (Somlyo & Siegman, 2012). Of particular relevance to the lungs, is the role of smooth muscle in regulating lung airway resistance (Bowens & Parmacek, 2012).

Smooth muscle, named due to the absence of striations (Goldman, 2003), is controlled involuntarily: the autonomic nervous system primarily controls the smooth muscle to regulate many of the body's subsystems required for life with no conscious input from the individual (Hafen & Burns, 2018). For example, humans do not consciously regulate the cardiovascular response needed to increase oxygen

supply during exercise. The control of smooth muscle tone is a complex interplay between endocrine, paracrine and neural influences which act on a variety of receptors and cellular pathways.

Although airway smooth muscle (ASM) physiology and smooth muscle physiology continue to be the subject of extensive research, a more complete understanding of ASM impact on disease and healthcare at a basic level will allow for professionals to have better tools for managing respiratory disease outcomes in the future (Sinha, Iyer & Granata, 2014). ASM is present in the tracheal and bronchial walls, including down to the terminal bronchioles. The ASM is a key factor in airway pathophysiology through its ability to regulate airway diameter and bronchomotor tone (Pan, Conaway & Deshpande, 2019). ASM surrounds the airway epithelium in a circumferential manner such that muscle contraction reduces lumen diameter (Doering & Solway, 2013) and can restrict airflow and. This ASM constriction can be intensified by cytokine release, which can also lead to extracellular matrix alterations via inflammatory processes, as well as exhibiting excessive proliferation (Pan, Conaway and Deshpande, 2019). Thus, the contractile capabilities of ASM are just one aspect to be considered in terms of their contribution to respiratory pathologies.

Throughout embryogenesis ASM development arises before that of vascular smooth muscle. The origin of the ASM cells seems to derive from neural crest cells and mesenchymal cells (Low & White, 1998). Visceral smooth muscle such as ASM expresses and accumulates cytosolic α -smooth muscle actin, myosin, desmin and SM22 α at mid gestation, all of which serve as smooth muscle markers (Owens, Kumar & Wamhoff, 2004).

2.1 ASM structure and function

In both the trachea and the primary bronchi, smooth muscle bands connect the two edges of the horseshoe shaped open cartilage ring. In the bronchioles the structural organisation of smooth muscle is different due to the absence of the cartilage in the peripheral bronchi and the smooth muscle forms a continuous layer in a helix-antihelix pattern encasing the bronchi (Amrani & Panettieri, 2003). There is a variation in cellular mass between upper and peripheral airways with ASM accounting for 25 % of the upper airways cellular mass and only 4-5 % of the lower airways (Gunst & Tang, 2000). Contraction of the smooth muscle reduces airway diameter and thus causes an increase to airflow resistance (Ouedraogo & Roux, 2014). In order to execute varied functions, the ASM transitions between a mature contractile, and a synthetic and a proliferative phenotype which is characterised by a predisposition to grow and/or synthesise ECM and other biologically active proteins (Amrani & Panettieri, 2003). This reversible phenotypic alteration is achieved by an intricate coordinated interaction among external stimuli eliciting a network of intracellular signalling cascades in ASM cells, which leads to transcriptional activation and protein translation of phenotypic genes (Pan, Conaway & Deshpande, 2019). The external stimuli regulating this phenotypic switch include cell to cell interaction, cytokines, growth factors and mechanical forces (Billington *et al.*, 2013).

Airway smooth muscle contraction

The mechanism of contraction in ASM is stimulated by hormones and neurotransmitters that bind to receptors in the cell membrane, causing cellular influx of calcium through L-type channels (Boerman, 2018). This first method of stimulation then leads to a second wave of calcium induced calcium release, whereby increased intracellular calcium promotes the release of calcium from the sarcoplasmic reticulum via ryanodine receptors and IP₃ (Ouedraogo, 2014) (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3 Regulation of smooth muscle contraction. A vast array of agonists binds to receptors on the sarcoplasmic reticulum causing the release of Ca²⁺. This then results in the activation of PKC, leading to the phosphorylation of target proteins which regulate cross-bridge cycling and phosphorylate Ca²⁺ channels. Subsequently, Ca²⁺ then binds to calmodulin which results in the stimulation of myosin light chain kinase (MLCK) and consequently actin and myosin light chain (MLC) contracted. This kinase phosphorylates the light chain of myosin and in combination with actin, cross bridge cycling occurs which prompts shortening of the smooth muscle cell. Reproduced in Biorender with permission from (Webb, 2003).

Airway smooth muscle relaxation

In ASM, the 3'-5'-cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) pathway, which is the most imperative signal transduction pathway in relaxation and also the 3'-5'-cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP) pathway are both predominantly stimulated by inhibition of cyclic nucleotide breakdown or by direct action on ion channels within the cell membrane (Knox & Tattersfield, 1995). In terms of both relaxation and contraction, there is a well-established relationship between intracellular calcium level and smooth muscle tone. Targeting the main relaxation signal transduction pathway mentioned above through GPCRs, studies have observed a cAMP mediated relaxation in canine ASM (Ozaki *et al.*, 1990) and also a cGMP mediated relaxation in both canine and bovine ASM (Jones *et al.*, 1994). cAMP in smooth muscle causes relaxation by inhibiting myosin light chain kinase (MLCK), which is the enzyme that is normally accountable for phosphorylation of smooth muscle myosin and which causes contraction (Bai & Sanderson, 2006). The cGMP mechanism of relaxation in ASM involves reversible oxidation of thiols on proteins, for example the myosin head, that controls contraction or the contractile proteins in smooth muscle (Perkins *et al.*, 1998).

In ASM numerous GPCRs such as adenosine (A_{2b} receptor), prostacyclin (IP receptor), β-2 adrenergic receptor (β₂AR), Prostaglandin (PG) receptors (EP2 and EP4) which are discussed in more detail below have been identified as being involved in ASM relaxation (Billington *et al.*, 2013). Prostaglandins are mediators which are derived from arachidonic acid via cyclooxygenase (COX) activation and it is thought that PGE₂ is the most abundant and the most physiologically relevant in a lung context (Billington *et al.*, 2013). In ASM cells PGE₂ also has various other roles including mediating anti-proliferative, anti-migratory and anti-relaxant effects via cAMP-dependent pathways in a similar manner as other cAMP increasing agents (Yan *et al.*, 2011). The biological effects observed in response to PGE₂ are mediated through four distinct prostanoid EP receptor subtypes known as EP1, EP2, EP3 and EP4 from the superfamily of GPCRs (Vancheri *et al.*, 2004). Stimulation of EP2 and EP4 receptors raises the intracellular levels of cAMP with EP2 being reported as the functionally dominant receptor

for ASM relaxation (Walch *et al.*, 1999). However ASM EP4 receptors have also been reported to contribute functionally in rat tissue to, and it has been noted that both receptors have a role in the anti-proliferative effects of PGE₂ (Mori *et al.*, 2011).

2.2 ASM pathophysiology, treatment, and management

Pathophysiology

The contractile capabilities of ASM are just one aspect to be considered in terms of respiratory pathologies. These cells also secrete extracellular matrix, cytokines and chemokines and can exhibit unwarranted proliferation (Pan, Conaway and Deshpande, 2019). Airway smooth muscle (ASM) surrounds the airway in a circumferential pattern such that muscle contraction causes reduction in lumen diameter (Doeing & Solway, 2013). This ASM constriction can be amplified by cytokine release, which can lead to extracellular matrix alterations via inflammation and cell proliferation. The ability of this tissue to undergo phenotypic modulation in lung airways supports the view that ASM, normally a 'passive' contractile tissue, may develop to be an 'active participant' in controlling inflammation in chronic lung diseases such as COPD (Panettieri, 2003).

Changes in airway structure and function are vital in the pathogenesis of specific diseases such as COPD and asthma (Fehrenbach *et al.*, 2017). The increase in ASM mass is an important element of airway remodelling which accounts for airway narrowing and loss of respiratory function in patients with severe asthma and/or COPD (Aubier *et al.*, 2016). Although this ASM remodelling is a recognised characteristic of COPD, the underlying mechanisms remain elusive. In terms of asthma, it has been reported that ASM cells from asthmatic patients proliferate more rapidly than cells from non-asthmatic patients. This perhaps indicates that alongside rapid proliferation, ASM from asthmatic subjects also sustains airway inflammation and remodelling by producing a vast array of proinflammatory and fibrotic mediators such as IL-8 and eotaxin (Pepe *et al.*, 2005). ASM cells are also likely to respond to a wide range of mediators or growth factors released from inflammatory cells within the bronchial mucosa, however the key signals for cell proliferation have been under-investigated (James *et al.*, 2018). An increase in mast cell activation has long been documented in the airways of asthma patients (Tam & Caughey, 1990), and the quantity of mast cells have been reported to rise with the airway smooth muscle itself (Ammit *et al.*, 1997). The mast cells can discharge a number of potent mediators, some of which have profound effects on smooth muscle. For example, mast-cell derived histamine and products of arachidonic acid metabolism have drawn attention for their significant roles in facilitating bronchoconstriction (Ellis *et al.*, 1994).

Treatments and management

At present, ASM is the key target in treatment of airway disorders. Most of the bronchodilators available target GPCR by either stimulating the relaxant pathways or alternatively inhibiting the contractile pathways to allow for bronchodilation (Yan *et al.*, 2018a). For example, β_2 -agonists mediate their therapeutic effects via cell surface β_2 -ARs. These agonists work via the ligand binding to the active site of the receptor, which causes the α -component of the G-protein to dissociate and subsequently activate adenylate cyclase which leads to the production of intracellular cAMP followed by activation of protein kinase A (Howarth *et al.*, 2004). However, airway lumen alterations in COPD are also affected by physical modification, induced by phenotypic shift and an increase in cytokines. To date, therapies available for COPD fail to target this aspect of the ASM pathophysiology in the disease (Yan *et al.*, 2018a).

2.3 Airway smooth muscle in COPD

Smooth muscle cells are vital constituents of airway contractile function and overall contributions to the production of inflammatory factors, proteases and growth factors (Howarth *et al.*, 2004). In COPD patients, airway remodelling, and structural changes are observed within the small airways. These changes include processes such as inflammation, epithelial metaplasia, goblet cell hyperplasia, submucosal gland hypertrophy and a rise in the mass and proportion of airway smooth muscle (Chung, 2005). A previous study (Hogg, 2004) reported that the lamina propria, the smooth muscle and the adventitia were increased collectively by 50 % in the Global initiative for chronic obstructive lung

disease (GOLD) stages 3 and 4 compared with that of GOLD stage 0. This indicates that there is a progressive remodelling of the small airways with increasing severity of the disease. To further support the contention that ASM is increased in the remodelling process, an investigation using myography was undertaken to analyse the functional capacity of the airway tissue of COPD patients compared with non-obstructed patients (Opazo *et al.*, 2000). The results of this investigation highlighted that force exerted by ASM samples from COPD sufferers was increased compared with that from non-COPD sufferers, indicating that increased ASM mass was thus generating greater force (Opazo *et al.*, 2000). In Figure 1.4 below a schematic diagram of the difference in structure between a normal and inflamed airway can be seen, illustrating the considerable difference in airway diameter when the smooth muscle is hypercontractile, inflamed and combined with hypersecretion of mucus.

Figure 1.4 Illustration of healthy vs COPD human airways. The Figure illustrates the variation in tissue structure between healthy and diseased airways, highlighting the impact that changes in smooth muscle can cause to the airways of COPD patients. Reproduced using Biorender with permission from (Cosio Piqueras and Cosio, 2001).

Hypertrophy and hyperplasia of the ASM in COPD can be directly correlated with a decline in lung function and with an increase in severity of airway wall thickening (Hogg *et al.*, 2004). This ASM remodelling observed in COPD is typically accompanied by ASM proliferation. It has been suggested that this proliferation of the ASM is induced due to MMPs stimulating the release of immobilized growth factors such as TGF- β and insulin like growth factor II. ASM is a key source of MMPs, and these zinc-dependent proteolytic enzymes play a key regulatory role in remodelling (Chen *et al.*, 2014). Changes such as matrix turnover, remodelling and angiogenesis of the airway smooth muscle are common features exhibited in COPD airways.

Alongside the changes to the ASM described above, the changes to ASM are interlinked with regulation of bronchomotor tone and in the overall control of the airway calibre, by which COPD patients may exhibit ASM hyper-contractility (Yan *et al.*, 2018a). A range of governing mechanisms are involved in the process of ASM contraction, and thus adaptations of these lead to airway hyper-responsiveness. This is a key feature as the abnormal regulation of contraction and relaxation in ASM contributes to COPD pathogenesis. This abnormality has detrimental effects in the airways due to ASM inability to maintain appropriate balance between airway contractility and dilation in response to stimuli (Prakash, 2013). Key mechanisms involved in this dysregulation of bronchomotor tone include G-protein coupled receptor pathways (Billington & Penn, 2003) such as non-selective cation channels, specifically transient receptor potential channels (Gosling, Poll & Li, 2005), store-operated calcium channels (Ay *et al.*, 2004) and G_q and G_i -dependent signalling (Billington & Penn, 2003).

3. Pathogenic Mechanisms

COPD is known as a progressive lower respiratory tract disorder which involves both chronic bronchitis and emphysema. Chronic bronchitis is characterised by hypersecretion of mucus from differentiating

goblet cells resulting in a thicker mucosal lining in the airways (Lahousse *et al.*, 2017), alongside hypersensitivity, hypercontractility and hyperplasia of the airway smooth muscle (James & Wenzel, 2007). Emphysema is caused by the destruction of the terminal bronchioles and alveolar wall destruction which results in a decrease in gas exchange in the lower airways (Sharafkhaneh, Hanania & Kim, 2008). There are many potential mechanisms by which particles and oxidants can initiate cell injury, thus leading eventually to COPD (Hnizdo & Vallyathan, 2017). The predominant inflammatory cells that are involved in the remodelling of the airways and the characteristic parenchymal destruction known as emphysema in COPD are neutrophils, macrophages, and T lymphocytes (CD8+ and CD4+) (Cosio & Majo, 2002). These cells are located in the airways, tissues and circulation of patients with COPD, during both stable disease and exacerbations (Bafadhel, Pavord and Russell, 2017). This increase is suggested to be coordinated through T helper 2 (Th2) cells and type 2 innate lymphoid cells via the release of cytokine IL-33 from epithelial cells (Peter J. Barnes, 2016). ASM can produce chemokines, for example eotaxin which plays a role in recruiting eosinophils from the systemic outer circulation into the lungs (Ghaffar *et al.*, 1999).

The molecular mechanisms which lead to the process of cytotoxicity, include the production of reactive oxygen/nitrogen species and secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines, chemokines, elastase and fibrogenic factors (Dai *et al.*, 1998). Oxidative stress is now recognised as being a key predisposing influence in driving COPD pathogenesis, specifically inflammation, and is reported to result in many pathogenic mechanisms (Kirkham & Barnes, 2013). Examples of these include, reduction of antioxidant capacity, activation of inflammatory transcription factor nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), protease-antiprotease imbalance, autoantibody generation, DNA damage and cellular senescence which leads to accelerated ageing (Barnes, 2016). This accelerated ageing observed in COPD patients can lead to the release of inflammatory proteins from senescent cells, which contributes to the chronic inflammation (Boe, Boule & Kovacs, 2017). These mechanisms can initiate changes in lung tissues leading ultimately to airflow obstruction and destruction of the alveolar surfaces.

In conditions of oxidative stress, mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways are activated by reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Thimraj *et al.*, 2018). Specific types of ROS activate certain pathways, for example hydrogen peroxide exposure to cells results in prolonged activation of the Jun amino terminal kinase (JNK) pathway (Kamata *et al.*, 2005). Prolonged activation of extracellular signal regulated kinases (ERK) is induced by glutamate-induced ROS by degradation of Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase Phosphatase 1 (MKP1), an inhibitor of MAPKs (Choi *et al.*, 2006). Activation of the stress activated protein kinases (p38/SAPKs) in alveolar macrophages have also been discussed in the context of COPD (Renda *et al.*, 2008). MAPKs are among the most studied redox sensitive transcriptional regulators, and an increase in their activity has been reported in asthma as well as COPD (Thimraj *et al.*, 2018). Pathogenesis of COPD can also be affected by the process of inflammatory cells releasing proteases and various mediators such as cytokines and chemokines, which can contribute to the chronic inflammation and tissue remodelling (Castranova, 2000; Heuberger *et al.*, 2015).

3.1 Cytokines

The role of cytokines in COPD (Figure 1.5) was first highlighted by a study (Keatings *et al.*, 1996) demonstrating raised concentrations of both TNF- α and IL-8 in induced sputum of COPD patients. This was compared with smokers with normal lung function and non-smokers, and these cytokines were linked to an increase in neutrophil numbers within the sputum (Keatings *et al.*, 1996). Pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1 β and IL-6 are also increased in COPD and amplify inflammation. This amplification in the inflammatory response is often linked to disease severity (Donaldson *et al.*, 2005, Barnes, 2009). IL-6 is mainly secreted by T cells and macrophages and exerts pro-inflammatory effects through the activation of Janus Kinase-signal transducer and activator of transcription (JAK-STAT) signalling (Stahl *et al.*, 1994). Further evidence indicated that IL-6 levels are increased in broncho-alveolar lavage (BAL) in COPD patients, again associating with a decrease in lung function (Soler *et al.*, 1999). These findings suggested a role for IL-6 in the chronic inflammatory state that causes disease progression in COPD (Bhowmik *et al.*, 2000).

Figure 1.5 The Cytokine Network in COPD. Cigarette smoke and other inhaled irritants activate epithelial cells and macrophages to release various cytokines that entice inflammatory cells to the lung. These inflammatory cells, together with macrophages and epithelial cells, release proteases which cause elastin degradation and mucus hypersecretion which results in emphysema and airflow obstruction. Alongside proteases, the release of proinflammatory cytokines and chemokines amplify the inflammatory setting observed in the COPD lung. Reproduced using Biorender, with permission from (Barnes, 2009).

Other cytokines that have been investigated in relation to COPD (Table 1.2) include IL-18, due to its ability to induce lung inflammation in mice (Imaoka *et al.*, 2008). In conjunction with this, IL-18 expression in the alveolar macrophages and CD8⁺ cells of the airways is increased in COPD patients, and correlates with disease severity (Rovina *et al.*, 2009).

Cytokine	Alternative nomenclature	Secreting cells	Activates
TNF- α	Cachexin or Cachectin	Epithelial cells Macrophages T-Lymphocytes Airway smooth muscle cells NK cells	Macrophages Mast cells NK cells Sensory Neurons
IL-1 β	Leukocytic pyrogen	Macrophages	Neutrophils CD4 ⁺ cells CD8 ⁺ cells NK cell ILC3 Th17 Tc17
IL-6	CXCL6	Epithelial cells CD4 ⁺ cells CD8 ⁺ cells Macrophages	NK cell ILC3 Th17 Tc17
IL-32	CXCL32	Epithelial cells	Monocytes

		Macrophages CD8 ⁺ cells NK cells	Macrophages
IL-1	Lymphocyte activating factor Endogenous pyrogen catabolin	Macrophages Epithelial cells Neutrophils	Neutrophils Eosinophils Basophils Mast cells NK cells
IL-8	CXCL8	Epithelial cells Macrophages	Neutrophils Monocytes NK cells ILC3 Th17 Tc17 Th1 Tc1
TSLP	Thymic stomal lymphopoietin	Airway smooth muscle cells Epithelial cells Fibroblasts Mast cells Macrophages	CD8 ⁺ cells Th1
IL-10	CXCL10	CD4 ⁺ cells CD8 ⁺ cells	Th1 Tc1
IL-18	CXCL18	Macrophages CD8 ⁺ cells	NK cells Th1
IL-17	CXCL17	ILC3 Th17 Tc17	Neutrophils
TGF- β	Transforming Growth Factor	Epithelial cells Macrophages	Fibroblasts
IL-23	CXCL23	Macrophages CD4 ⁺ cells CD8 ⁺ cells	Th17 Tc17 ILC3 NK cell
IL-33	CXCL33	Epithelial cells	Th2 ILC2 Eosinophils
IL-22	CXCL22	ILC3 Th17 Tc17	Keratinocytes hepatocytes
IL-4	CXCL4	Mast cells Basophils T cells Eosinophils Neutrophils	B cells T cells

Table 1.2 Cytokines in COPD. List of known cytokines involved in COPD, alongside the secreting cells, the activated cells and other known names for each (Barnes, 2009; Hikichi *et al.*, 2019; Redhu & Gounni, 2012; Pisetsky, 2014; Zenewicz & Flavell, 2011; Smiley & Grusby, 1998).

Another cytokine that has been shown to be increased in COPD and long recognised as a key factor in the disease is IL-8, and similar to other cytokines, the increase is triggered by cigarette smoke inhalation (Zhang *et al.*, 2011). Studies have shown that cigarette smoke enhances the release of IL-8 from both dendritic cells (Mortaz *et al.*, 2009) and airway smooth muscle cells (Gosens *et al.*, 2009), suggesting

that cigarette smoke exposure is sufficient to explain the release of amplified levels of IL-8 in COPD airways (Smiley & Grusby, 1998; Bautista *et al.*, 2009).

The pleiotrophic cytokine TSLP, which in the case of ASM could be described as an effector cytokine, has more recently emerged as a key player which is a key regulator of inflammation which is seen in asthma (Hendrix *et al.*, 2013). TSLP is a short chain cytokine that was primarily from a thymic stomal cell line and played a role in the maturation of B cells (Roan *et al.*, 2012). Literature has shown that the cytokine is generated by cells which are often involved in asthma such as dendritic cells, mast cells and basophils with some reports of its expression in smooth muscle cells (Redhu & Gounni, 2012). The cytokine can also be induced by a range of proinflammatory mediators such as IL-1 β and TNF- α (Takai, 2012). It has also been highlighted that the proteases which induce TSLP response are from common airborne fungal allergens and dsRNA produced by infections with viruses such as rhinovirus infection (Holgate, 2012). This aspect may help to explain why asthmatics tend to be more sensitive to lung viral infections compared with non-asthmatics (Jackson & Johnston, 2010).

In the context of COPD, it has been reported that TSLP is involved in initiation of allergic airway inflammation through a dendritic cell-mediated Th2 (response from epithelial derived TSLP (Anzalone *et al.*, 2018). It also has been shown by (Redhu & Gounni, 2012) that there are elevated levels of TSLP in the bronchial mucosa of both COPD and asthma patients, linking its involvement in the function and mechanism of airway diseases. Increased expression of TSLP has also been described in ASM of patients with COPD, mechanisms for which are illustrated in Figure 1.6 below (Zhang *et al.*, 2007).

Figure 1.6 Triggers & mechanisms of TSLP expression in ASM. Pro-inflammatory cytokines induce TSLP in ASM via various pathways such as MAPK, NF- κ B and AP-1. Although the mechanisms remain unknown, β 2-agonists may involve G-protein coupled receptor G_i subunit stimulation, which subsequently induces ERK activation to modulate cytokine-induced ERK MAPK pathways. The solid line arrows indicate current known pathway(s) and the dotted line arrows represent possible pathway(s) that could be explored. Reproduced using Biorender with permission from Redhu & Gounni (2012).

3.2 Chemokines

Chemokines are small peptide molecules ranging from 8 to 12 kDa in size and belong to the cytokine superfamily. There is specific interest in the role of chemokines in inflammatory diseases due to their biological functions, such as chemotaxis and leukocyte degranulation (Baggiolini, 1998), signalling through G-protein-coupled receptors to play a vital role in the recruitment of inflammatory cells to the lung from the circulation in sufferers of COPD (Donnelly & Barnes, 2006). Certain chemokines can activate only a single receptor and are therefore characterised in terms of their receptors, categorised as chemotactic chemokines (CC) (activating CCRs) and cysteine chemokines (CXC) (binding CXCRs) (Yung & Farber, 2013). The first COPD identified chemokine was CXCL8, where 'L' denotes 'ligand'. (Keatings *et al.*, 1996), however other chemokines have also been implicated in COPD (Table 1.3). Research on chemokines and their receptors could identify novel therapeutic targets that could both slow the disease and treat acute exacerbations, by preventing recruitment of pathogenic cells in lungs during a heightened inflammatory response (Panina, Mariani & D'Ambrosio, 2006).

Attracting cells	Expressing cells	Chemokine	Receptor	Alternative nomenclature
Neutrophils Monocytes	Macrophages Mast cells	CXCL1	CXCR2 CXCR1	C-X-C motif chemokine 1, Gro-a, GRO1, NAP-3, KC
Neutrophils Monocytes	Macrophages Mast cells	CXCL2	CXCR2	Gro- β , GRO2, MIP-2a
Neutrophils Monocytes	Alveolar macrophages Epithelial cells Platelets	CXCL5	CXCR2	ENA-78
Neutrophils Monocytes	Inflammatory cells Fibroblasts Endothelial cells Platelets	CXCL7	CXCR2	NAP-2, CTAPIII, PEP, β -Ta
Neutrophils Monocytes	Neutrophils Epithelial cells Macrophages Fibroblasts Airway smooth muscle cells	CXCL8	CXCR1 CXCR2 CCR2	IL-8, NAP-1, MDNCF, GCP-1
Th1 Lymphocytes Tc1 Lymphocytes B Lymphocytes	Macrophages Dendritic cells Bronchial epithelial cells	CXCL9 CXCL10 CXCL11	CXCR3	MIG, CRG-10, IP-10, CRG-2, I-TAC, β -R1, IP-9
Monocytes T Lymphocytes Fibrocytes	Alveolar macrophages T cells Endothelial and epithelial cells	CCL2	CCR2	MCP-1
Macrophages Th2 Lymphocytes	Macrophages Lymphocytes Fibroblasts Epithelial cells	CCL3	CCR1 CCR4 CCR5	MIP-1a
Macrophages Neutrophils Dendritic cells Memory T cells Basophils	Endothelial cells Smooth muscle cells T Lymphocytes Epithelial cells	CCL5	CCR1 CCR3 CCR5	RANTES

Eosinophils Fibrocytes				
Eosinophils Th2 Lymphocytes	Epithelial cells Endothelial cells T Lymphocytes Macrophages Eosinophils	CCL11	CCR3	C-C motif chemokine 11, Eosinophil, chemotactic protein, small-inducible cytokine A11
T cells Monocytes Eosinophils Endothelial cells	Basophils Alveolar Macrophages Airway smooth muscle cells	CCL15	CCR4	Leukotactin-1, MIP-5, HCC-2, NCC-3
Dendritic cells Neutrophils Lymphocytes	Airway epithelial cells Macrophages	CCL20	CCR6	LARC, Exodus-1, Ckβ4

Table 1.3 Chemokines in COPD. List of known chemokines implicated in COPD, alongside the cells expressing each chemokine, the cells attracted by the molecules and the receptors involved for each (After Henrot *et al.*, 2019).

3.3 Proteases

As mentioned previously, the main confirmed genetic cause of COPD is A₁AT deficiency (Janciauskiene *et al.*, 2011). A₁AT is a serine protease inhibitor which regulates neutrophilic chemotaxis involving both CXCR1 and Fc γRIIIb signalling (Bergin *et al.*, 2010). The serine proteinase inhibitor has also been shown to regulate levels of cathepsin-B and MMP-2 in A₁AT deficient patients treated with A₁AT augmentation therapy (Geraghty *et al.*, 2008). The imbalance of proteases and antiproteases in COPD is a common hallmark and contributes to the progression of the disease, as supported by evidence from both animal and human studies (Gadek & Pacht, 1990; Churg & Wright, 2005; Demedts *et al.*, 2006).

There are three classes of proteases involved in COPD, these are: metallo-, cysteine and serine (Pandey, De & Mishra, 2017). The zinc-dependent matrix metalloproteinases including, MMP-2, MMP-9, MMP-12 and MMP-13 are found to be highly expressed in both clinical patient samples and also *in vivo* models (Vernooy *et al.*, 2004; Molet *et al.*, 2005; Baraldo *et al.*, 2007; Hunninghake *et al.*, 2009). Parallel to this within the cysteine proteinase group, caspase-1, 3, 7, 8, 9, 11 and cathepsin-K and S have also been evidenced to be upregulated in COPD patients (Demedts *et al.*, 2006; Lockett *et al.*, 2012; Podolin *et al.*, 2013; Eltom *et al.*, 2014). Following on from cysteine proteases, another mechanism thought to contribute to COPD pathogenesis is through the involvement of the ‘inflammasome’. Inflammasomes are multimeric protein complexes of the innate immune system which regulate the activation of the cysteine protease caspase-1 and cause the induction of inflammation (Heuberger *et al.*, 2015), typically in response to microbes, and to molecules derived from host proteins (Guo, Callaway & Ting, 2016). The primary role of the inflammasome is as part of the innate immune system that when triggered, assists in the defence of the body against invading pathogens (Optiz, Van Laak & Eitel, 2010; Franchi, Munoz-Planillo & Nunez, 2012). Recently, there has been a rise in interest in the contributions of inflammasomes in relation to COPD (Rovina, Koutsoukou & Koulouris, 2013). As well as stimulating caspase-1 activation, these complexes cause the release of inflammatory cytokines such as IL- 1β and IL-18 (Brusselle, Provoost & Bracke, 2014). Finally, in terms of the serine proteases, neutrophil elastase, cathepsin G, mast cell tryptase, chymase and proteinase-3 are all involved in the destruction of the alveolar tissue leading to emphysema (Nadel, 2000; Owen, 2008; Guyot *et al.*, 2014; Chang *et al.*, 2016).

4. Proteinase Activated Receptors

4.1 Overview

Proteolysis is involved in many varied responses to stress, injury, and infections in the body. While proteases are necessary for controlling cell motility, matrix degradation, tissue remodelling and cell-cell interactions, extracellular proteolytic activity is also directly sensed by cells through a unique class of G protein-coupled receptors (Rothmeier & Ruf, 2012). These receptors are activated by proteolysis and known as proteinase activated receptors (PARs). Four PARs have been identified to date PAR1, PAR2, PAR3 and PAR4 (Miotto *et al.*, 2002a). Coagulation proteases activate PARs to regulate haemostasis, thrombosis, and cardiovascular function (Rothmeier & Ruf, 2012). These receptors are not stimulated by the conventional ligand-receptor interaction but require partial proteolytic cleavage of the NH₂ terminus by serine proteases (Jin *et al.*, 2003). PAR1, -3 and -4 were originally identified as receptors for the coagulation protease thrombin and mediate thrombin signalling primarily as heterodimers, whilst PAR2 is thrombin insensitive (Rothmeier & Ruf, 2012). PAR2 is instead activated by proteases such as trypsin, tryptase, matriptase and a range of others, shown in Table 1.4.

The roles of PARs have been extensively investigated and it has become clear that this family of receptors constitute part of the body's defence system; PARs actively contribute to inflammatory responses via release of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory mediators (Ostrowska & Reiser, 2008). These pro-inflammatory mediators include IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-8 and IL-6 (Fyfe *et al.*, 2005) and anti-inflammatory mediators such as IL-10, whilst also down-regulating pro-inflammatory mediators such as IL-12 (Trinchieri, 2003). Proinflammatory cytokines amplify the inflammatory response and this is often linked with the severity of disease (Peter J. Barnes, 2009). At all stages of COPD there is evidence of activated innate immunity, however in more severe disease, adaptive immune mechanisms become involved (Curtis, Freeman & Hogg, 2007; Barnes, 2008). Both of these immune defence systems are mediated via cytokines and it is thought that the link between these immune mechanisms is through dendritic cells (Tsoumakidou *et al.*, 2008).

4.2 Proteinase activated receptors 1, 3 and 4

PAR1 was the first of the proteinase activated receptor family to be discovered by researchers studying the receptor mediating actions of thrombin (O'Brien *et al.*, 2001). This receptor is expressed not only in immune cells, neurons, and epithelium but also in cancer-associated fibroblasts, mast cells and macrophages in tumour microenvironments. PAR1 activation by thrombin leads to proliferation of mesenchymal cells such as endothelial cells, procollagen synthesis in smooth muscle cells and up-regulation of IL-8 release from fibroblasts (Jin *et al.*, 2003). PAR1 stimulates macrophages to synthesise and secrete thrombin as well as other growth factors, resulting in enhanced cell proliferation (Liu *et al.*, 2017), likely through TGF- β activation mediated by the enzyme FXa (Lin *et al.*, 2015).

PAR3 is typically expressed by tissues of hematopoietic origin and large bone marrow cells known as megakaryocytes that produce platelets. Although PAR3 is also a receptor cleaved by thrombin, expression on human platelets suggests a function distinctly diverse from that of PAR1. Thrombin-mediated PAR-3 activation results in ERK phosphorylation and an increase in the production of IL-8 (Ostrowska & Reiser, 2008). PAR3 also has been investigated with regards to a regulatory role on PAR1 function. One such study (McLaughlin *et al.*, 2007) highlighted that PAR1/3 heterodimers are formed constitutively and thus the activated dimeric complex induces distinct signalling involving selective coupling to G α_{13} as compared with the PAR-1/1 homodimer. PAR3 has also been reported to interact with PAR4 in a novel mechanism, acting as a cofactor for the cleavage and activation of PAR4 by thrombin (Nakanishi-matsui *et al.*, 2000).

PAR4 was initially identified by database searches using domains of the other three members of the PAR family (Kahn, Zheng, *et al.*, 1998). This receptor is reported to be expressed on lung, thyroid, testis, small intestine, pancreas (Rudinga, Khan & Kong, 2018), human and mouse platelets (Bretschneider *et al.*, 2003). This seemingly accounts for the continued ability of platelets derived from PAR3 knockout mice to respond to thrombin (Xu *et al.*, 1998). PAR4 is thought to have arose from a

remote gene duplication and subsequent translocation event (Kahn, *et al.*, 1998). One of the signalling mechanisms reported for PAR4 which culminate in cellular function is calcium mobilisation via activation of the PLC β complex and consequent phosphoinositide hydrolysis (Coughlin, 2000). This PAR4-induced movement of calcium promotes the activity of several kinases and phosphatases which are regulated by calcium, causing wide ranging effects (Coughlin, 2005). Examples of these kinases and phosphatases include MAPKs and PKCs (Kahn, Zheng, *et al.*, 1998). As a result of this activation, several key platelet responses induced by GPCR-dependent calcium mobilisation are mediated, including secretion of platelet storage granules and integrin activation, both critical for efficient platelet accumulation (French & Hamilton, 2016).

4.3 Proteinase activated receptor 2 (PAR2)

PAR2 was first discovered in mice serendipitously during a screening of a mouse genomic library (Nystedt *et al.*, 1994). This PAR subtype is expressed systemically throughout the human body. It is upregulated in various disorders such as obesity, diabetes and metabolic syndrome (Nystedt *et al.*, 1995). PAR2 activation stimulates inflammatory pathways that impair cellular metabolism, induce insulin resistance and promote conditions such as obesity and diabetes (Samad & Ruf, 2013). While coagulation proteases activate PARs to regulate haemostasis, thrombosis, and cardiovascular function, PAR2 is also activated in extra-vascular locations, and by a wide range of serine proteases (Rothmeier & Ruf, 2012). These proteases include trypsin, tissue kallikreins, coagulation factors VIIa and Xa, mast cell tryptase and transmembrane serine proteases (see Table 1.4). The cleavage of PAR2 by trypsin and mast cell tryptase can regulate the activities of endothelial cells, epithelial cells, smooth muscle cells and macrophages in a variety of tissues (Kang *et al.*, 2005). There is mounting evidence indicating an important role for PAR2 in mediation of pain, for example in the context of inflammation and hypersensitivity (Bao, Hou & Hua, 2014). These responses are pillars in the pathogenesis in many chronic diseases, including COPD. PAR2 agonists are able to regulate the expression and release of a wide range of bioactive mediators such as cytokines, prostanoids, neuropeptides and NO (Déry *et al.*, 1998), which may underpin diverse functional responses.

4.3.1 PAR2 mechanism of activation

Activation of PAR2 (Figure 1.7) occurs through a proteolytic mechanism catalysed by proteases binding to and cleaving the extracellular N-terminal domain of the receptor at specific sites for example the canonical tethered ligand exposed, SLIGKV-NH₂ (Jin *et al.*, 2003). This unveils a new N-terminus that acts as a tethered ligand which binds to the receptor and induces intracellular signalling by binding to the second extracellular loop (Soh *et al.*, 2010). PAR2 couples to G protein α subunits G $\alpha_{q/11}$, G α_i or G $\alpha_{12/13}$.

G

PAR2 N Terminal amino acid sequence:

MRSPSAAWLLGAAILLAASLSCSGTIOGTNRSSKGRSLIGKVDGTSHVTGKGVTVETVFSDEF
SASVLTGKLTTFVFLPI

Figure 1.7 Mechanism of PAR2 activation. PAR2 activation is regulated by (A) direct proteolytic cleavage at the N-terminus, (B) homo or hetero co-factor mechanism of activation with other PARs and transactivation of the receptor through the cleaved tethered ligand. (C) compartmentalisation of the activated receptor on the cell surface, (D) then leads to degradation or recycling by endosomal trafficking, (E) posttranslational alterations such as phosphorylation. Followed by the final step (F), co-localisation with other receptors and cofactors (Heuberger & Schuepbach, 2019). C-Terminus (red arrow) and N-terminus (blue arrow) as well as enzyme cleavage site (A) which exposes a tethered ligand. The protein regions coded by the first exons are underlined and the arg residues involved in receptor cleavage and activation are shown in red. The activating ligand which is untethered by cleavage at the arg residues can be seen in blue (Liu *et al.*, 2020).

Independent of proteolytic cleavage, PAR2 can be activated experimentally by synthetic peptides developed to mimic the amino acid sequence of the exposed tethered ligand during proteolytic cleavage. These peptides bind to the receptor causing activation (Heuberger & Schuepbach, 2019). Activation of the receptor also prompts G protein-independent pathways through recruitment of the adaptor protein β -arrestin to the carboxyl-terminal tail of PAR2 (Rothmeier & Ruf, 2012). Ligand-induced biased signalling through GPCR is an evolving research area which has promising advantages from fine tuning compounds to specifically modulate one intracellular pathway associated with disease pathology, without affecting other pathways associated with the same receptor and normal physiology (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). In addition to activation, the disarming of PAR2 can also occur through proteases causing removal of a section of the N-terminus including the activating tethered ligand sequence (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2007). Examples include neutrophil elastase and cathepsin G, which inhibit PAR2 by proteolysis of the extracellular domain downstream from the trypsin cleavage site (Dulon *et al.*, 2003).

Originally, receptor-mediated signalling was portrayed as a linear process which involved one singular agonist and a host of potential targets within a specific receptor family, for example, α and β -adrenoceptors and a second messenger (e.g., cAMP or cGMP-triggered response). If differing responses were triggered by the same receptor in varying tissues, the differences were attributed to different second messenger effectors in the different tissue types. It is now understood that an individual receptor can couple to multiple pathways even in the same cell, for example different G proteins or β -arrestins, to drive different responses (Little *et al.*, 2016). Kenakin (1995) proposed that the simplest way an agonist could activate multiple pathways is via the 'strength of signal' generated by chemically different drugs or ligands which selectively activate a specific pathway. The best form of evidence in support of biased agonism would be if two different agonists could display antagonistic effects of differing signalling pathways in the same system. Ligand-induced biased signalling through G protein coupled receptors is also an evolving research area which has promising advantages from fine tuning compounds to specifically modulating one intracellular pathway associated with disease pathology, without affecting other pathways associated with the same receptor and normal physiology (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). Perry *et al.*, 2002, confirmed that the β -arrestins bind cAMP phosphodiesterases of the PDE4D family using mouse embryonic fibroblasts derived from β -arrestin1^{-/-} and β -arrestin2^{-/-} deficient mice. Once β_2 AR is activated, β -arrestin2 recruits PDE4D isoforms into a complex with the activated PAR2, facilitating cAMP degradation at a quicker rate. This reduces the rate of PKA activation, and thus β -arrestin not only slows the rate of β_2 AR/Gs-stimulated cAMP generation, but in a synchronized fashion escalates the rate of cAMP degradation in proximity to the receptor-adenylate-cyclase signalling unit (Perry *et al.*, 2002). In terms of ASM, it could be suggested this is a likely mechanism for bronchodilation via PAR2 due to the reduction in cAMP.

4.3.2 PAR2 in vasculature

PAR2 has been found to be expressed on several tissues throughout the body in both murine and humans (Moffatt & Cocks, 1998) however, the physiological role of PAR2 is still undefined. Most of our knowledge on PAR2 in smooth muscle comes from studies in a vascular smooth muscle context in both human and murine settings. Evidence that PAR2 is physiologically expressed on the vascular tissue suggests that it typically participates in the control of vascular homeostasis (Cicala, 2002) and vascular remodelling in the lung (Kwapiszewska *et al.*, 2012). Roles for PAR2 including vasodilation, tissue remodelling and proliferation in smooth muscle have also been demonstrated in various studies using known PAR2 activators (Saifeddine *et al.*, 1996; Magazine, King & Srivastava, 1996; Moffatt & Cocks, 1998; Sobey, Moffatt & Cocks, 1999; Hamilton, Frauman & Cocks, 2001; McGuire *et al.*, 2002; Villari *et al.*, 2017).

4.3.3 PAR2 in airway smooth muscle

It has long been considered that PARs may be involved in the pathophysiology of respiratory disorders. This is underpinned by observations of elevated levels of PAR-activating proteases such as tryptase and thrombin in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid from patients with pulmonary inflammation (Idell *et al.*, 1987). PAR2 has been identified to be present in human airways, both in the bronchial epithelium and also the bronchial smooth muscle (Kagota *et al.*, 2016). Studies in various animal models have found contradictory findings in regard to the functional role of PAR2 in the airways, reporting both bronchodilation and bronchoconstriction (Cocks *et al.*, 1999; Lan *et al.*, 2000; Ricciardolo *et al.*, 2000; Chambers *et al.*, 2001). A study demonstrating a protective role for PARs in the airways showed that activation of PAR2 causes the relaxation of airway preparations from mouse, rat, guinea-pig and humans by the release of a cyclooxygenase product from the epithelium (Cocks *et al.*, 1999). This physiological protective response in isolated airways was also seen in anaesthetised rats where PAR2 activation resulted in a marked and prolonged inhibition of bronchoconstriction (Cocks *et al.*, 1999). It was also found that following desensitisation of PAR2, the response to trypsin recovered rapidly by mechanisms of *de novo* synthesis and trafficking of proteins. The use of protein-trafficking inhibitor, brefeldin A, prevented the recovery of the PAR2-dependent relaxation observed. This finding indicated that there is a rapid PAR2 turnover from intracellular stores in airway epithelium (Cocks *et al.*, 1999). Thus trypsin released from the epithelium could initiate powerful bronchoprotection in the airways via activation of PAR2 in the epithelium (Cocks *et al.*, 1999). It has been reported that PAR2 may be

responsible for the modulation of airway relaxation, investigated via trypsin-mediated activation in bronchial epithelial cells (Cocks *et al.*, 1999). Similar bronchodilatory responses were found in murine airways but with relaxation unaltered following removal of the epithelium (Lan *et al.*, 2000). Partly contrasting results were reported in guinea pig airways upon PAR2 activation however, resulting in bronchoconstriction *in vivo* and either contraction or relaxation *in vitro* (Ricciardolo *et al.*, 2000). However, it was observed in this study that relaxation of main bronchi in response to prior carbachol (CCh) contraction was abolished or reversed via removal of the epithelial layer, administration of indomethacin and NOS inhibition (Ricciardolo *et al.*, 2000).

Jiang *et al.* (2017) found that MAPK signalling occurs in response to trypsin following mutagenesis of the tethered ligand region of PAR2 but only the SLAAAA-tethered ligand sequence activated Ca²⁺ mobilisation and no other responses and thus indicating that the SL residues may be of importance. If this could be controlled the pathological role of PAR2-mediated hypercontractility in asthma and COPD patients could be inhibited and the protective bronchodilation via PAR2 could be enhanced (Walker & Defea, 2014).

A study was carried out to investigate the relationship between PAR activation and α -smooth muscle actin expression in fibroblasts. This cell type is of interest in terms of ASM due to the evidence which suggested the number of fibroblasts directly correlates with the thickness of basement reticular membrane (Holgate *et al.*, 2003). This, alongside the increasing number of sub-epithelial fibroblasts reported in airways of asthmatics, suggests that these cells are primarily involved in airway wall remodelling in asthma and other chronic respiratory diseases (Holgate *et al.*, 2003). It was found that archetypal activators of PARs such as thrombin, trypsin, and PAR1 and PAR2 agonist peptides, stimulated transient increases in intracellular calcium and promoted the expression of α -smooth muscle actin (Asokanathan *et al.*, 2015). Airway fibroblasts from asthmatic patients demonstrated an increase in the ability to differentiate into myofibroblasts. These cells possess ultrastructural features intermediate between fibroblasts and smooth muscle cells (Michalik *et al.*, 2009). The study also reported that both proteolytic and peptidic PAR activators stimulated the release of IL-6 and IL-8; the combined stimulation of PAR1 and PAR2 also promoted additive release of these cytokines (Asokanathan *et al.*, 2015). The collated results from these studies suggest an important role for the PARs (specifically 1 and 2) in the modulation of inflammation and the remodelling of the airways.

Several studies provide convincing evidence that activation of PAR2 by different proteases or in complex with other receptors provoke distinct signalling outcomes (Soh *et al.*, 2010). These selective cleavages by extracellular proteases enable PAR2 to act as a sensor on the surface of the cell and permit regulation of intracellular signalling and cell function in response to changes in a particular extracellular protease (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). In terms of PAR2 activators, the key product of human mast cell activation is the trypsin-like serine protease, mast-cell tryptase (Carroll *et al.*, 2021). There is recognition this enzyme is an important mediator of allergic inflammation and tissue remodelling (Marone *et al.*, 2000; Saito, 2005), and its putative contribution in chronic respiratory disease, to airway smooth muscle cell hyperplasia through the activation of PAR2, merits further investigation. In the context of the lung, TSLP has been shown to be induced by proteases which react with PAR2 (Demehri *et al.*, 2009). This raises the prospect of differentially controlling individual signalling pathways linked to different state of disease.

Origin	Protease	Source	Major Cleavage site
Mammalian	Trypsin	Acinar cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷
	Tryptase	Mast cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷
	Chymase	Mast cells, endothelial cells, fibroblasts	G ³⁵ R ³⁶
	Matriptase	Epithelial cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷
	Neutrophil Elastase	Neutrophils	A ⁶⁶ S ⁶⁷
	Proteinase-3	Neutrophils	D ⁶² E ⁶³

	Plasmin	Endothelial cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷
	Mast cell Tryptase	Mast cells	R ³⁶ S ³⁷
	Tissue Factors	Alveolar macrophages Epithelial cells	unknown
	FXa	Bovine plasma	R ³⁶ S ³⁷
Non- Mammalian	Bromelain	Pineapple	unknown
	Cockroach E1-E3	Cockroach	R ³⁶ S ³⁷
	Gingipain R	Porphyromonas Gingivalis	unknown
	LepA	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	unknown
	EPa	Fish oil	S ³⁷ L ³⁸
	<i>S.pneumoniae</i> proteases	Streptococcus pneumoniae	unknown
	<i>P.acnes</i> proteases	<i>Propionibacterium</i> <i>acnes</i>	unknown
	ficin	Figs latex	unknown
	papain	Papaya	unknown
	PenC	Penicillium citrinum	R ³⁶ S ³⁷

Table 1.4 PAR2 activating proteases. List of known PAR2 activating proteases alongside their source, origin and major cleavage site (Koshikawa *et al.*, 1998; Schwartz *et al.*, 2003; List, Bugge & Szabo, 2006; Kida *et al.*, 2008; van der Poll, 2008; Korkmaz *et al.*, 2010; Chen *et al.*, 2011; Deryugina & Quigley, 2012; Pavan *et al.*, 2012; De Stoppelaar *et al.*, 2013; Achermann *et al.*, 2014; Krystel-Whittemore, Dileepan & Wood, 2016; Castro *et al.*, 2017; Polley *et al.*, 2017; Dell'italia, Collawn & Ferrario, 2018; Heuberger & Schuepbach, 2019; Wang *et al.*, 2019; Ward, 2020).

The ability of PAR2 to have both protective and pathological roles in the airways has been suggested to be due to PAR2 signalling through two independent pathways: a β -arrestin-dependent pathway which promotes leukocyte migration, and also a G-protein pathway required for prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂) production and subsequent bronchodilation (Nichols *et al.*, 2012) and which interacts with adrenergic mechanisms (Figure 1.8). Nichols *et al.* demonstrated that airway smooth muscle relaxation was mediated by PGE₂ and levels of this prostaglandin were significantly increased in the bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) derived from both WT and β -arrestin^{-/-} mice, indicating that β -arrestin is not required for this PAR2-mediated response (Nichols *et al.*, 2012). However, it was also shown that the inflammatory leukocyte infiltration response in the asthma model was β -arrestin-2 dependent. These results are consistent with other studies demonstrating independent β -arrestin and G-protein-dependent signalling pathways downstream of PAR2 culminating in divergent responses (Ge *et al.*, 2003; Zoudilova *et al.*, 2010; Zhao, Metcalf & Bunnett, 2014). A further complexity of PAR-dependent responses mentioned above is the phenomenon of transactivation. Thus dual signalling pathways activated by ligand binding at both the β -2 adrenergic receptor (β ₂AR; as noted above a key modulator of ASM tone) and PAR2 give rise to both beneficial and detrimental effects in asthma and highlights the β -arrestin-dependent signalling as the link which underlies the parallels between the two (Walker *et al.*, 2011).

Originally, receptor-mediated signalling was portrayed as a linear process which involved one singular agonist and a host of potential targets within a specific receptor family, for example, α and β -adrenoceptors and a second messenger (e.g., cAMP or cGMP-triggered response). If differing responses were triggered by the same receptor in varying tissues, the differences were attributed to different second messenger effectors in the different tissue types. It is now understood that an individual receptor can couple to multiple pathways even in the same cell, for example different G proteins or β -arrestins, to drive different responses (Little *et al.*, 2016). Kenakin (1995) proposed that the simplest way an agonist could activate multiple pathways is via the 'strength of signal' generated by chemically different drugs or ligands which selectively activate a specific pathway. The best form of evidence in support of

biased agonism would be if two different agonists could display antagonistic effects of differing signalling pathways in the same system. Ligand-induced biased signalling through G protein coupled receptors is also an evolving research area which has promising advantages from fine tuning compounds to specifically modulating one intracellular pathway associated with disease pathology, without affecting other pathways associated with the same receptor and normal physiology (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). Perry *et al.*, 2002, confirmed that the β -arrestins bind cAMP phosphodiesterases of the PDE4D family using mouse embryonic fibroblasts derived from β -arrestin1^{-/-} and β -arrestin2^{-/-} deficient mice. Once β_2 AR is activated, β -arrestin2 recruits PDE4D isoforms into a complex with the activated PAR2, facilitating cAMP degradation at a quicker rate. This reduces the rate of PKA activation, and thus β -arrestin not only slows the rate of β_2 AR/Gs-stimulated cAMP generation, but in a synchronized fashion escalates the rate of cAMP degradation in proximity to the receptor–adenylate-cyclase signalling unit (Perry *et al.*, 2002). In terms of ASM, it could be suggested this is a likely mechanism for bronchodilation via PAR2 due to the reduction in cAMP.

G protein-coupled receptors utilise at least two signal transduction pathways to elicit cellular responses. These pathways include the traditional G protein-dependent, and the more recently discovered β -arrestin-dependent signalling pathway (Walker & DeFea, 2014). The central role of G-protein dependent signalling is also consistent with the potential involvement of the G-protein coupled receptor PAR2 in the regulation of ASM contractility in COPD. Once β_2 AR is activated, β -arrestin2 recruits PDE4D isoforms into a complex with the activated PAR2, facilitating cAMP degradation at a quicker rate. This reduces the rate of PKA activation, and thus β -arrestin not only slows the rate of β_2 AR/Gs-stimulated cAMP generation, but in a synchronized fashion escalates the rate of cAMP degradation in proximity to the receptor–adenylate-cyclase signalling unit (Perry *et al.*, 2002). In terms of ASM, it could be suggested this is a likely mechanism for bronchodilation via PAR2 due to the reduction in cAMP.

Interestingly, the two pathways are also temporally separable, with β -arrestin signalling sometimes occurring before the G-protein signalling pathway and at other times, exhibiting a delayed or prolonged signal (Ahn *et al.*, 2004; Zoudilova *et al.*, 2007). Some studies have highlighted co-localisation of β -arrestin-1 and β -arrestin-2 following PAR2 activation induces ERK1/2 signalling (Stalheim *et al.*, 2005). Another example of divergent PAR2 signalling in different tissue types is in pancreatic duct cells. In this context PAR2 activation has been shown to have noticeable effects on intracellular Ca²⁺ and protein kinase C (PKC) to stimulate fluid and mucin secretion (Liddle, 2018). Murine studies have highlighted that PAR2 activation can play opposing roles in allergic asthma by both providing potent bronchorelaxation and mediating inflammation (Nichols *et al.*, 2012). Nichols *et al.* 2012, demonstrated that β -arrestin2^{-/-} mice showed a large decrease in tissue leukocyte numbers and a simultaneous decrease in the production of proinflammatory cytokines, whereas PAR2-dependent bronchorelaxation was unaffected.

Figure 1.8 Dual signalling pathways. Activation of PAR2 or β_2 AR leads to both β -arrestin and G protein-dependent signaling. Bronchorelaxation occurs as a result of activation of the G protein-dependent pathway, compared with a pro-asthmatic response via the β -arrestin-2-dependent pathway. Reproduced using Biorender with permission from Walker & Defea (2014).

The suggestion that bronchorelaxation and inflammation are mediated via two independent signalling pathways, allows scope for therapeutic targets to be developed in terms of “biased” or “pathway-specific” ligands that favourably activate or prevent one signalling pathway over the other (Walker *et al.*, 2011). Thus dual signalling pathways activated by ligand binding at the β_2 AR and PAR2 give rise to both beneficial and detrimental effects in asthma and highlights the β -arrestin-dependent signalling as the link which underlies the parallels between the two (Walker *et al.*, 2011). These results co-align with other studies which demonstrate independent signalling pathways downstream of PAR2 (Ge *et al.*, 2003; Zhao, Metcalf & Bunnett, 2014).

5. Conclusion

The rate of discovery and development of new molecules targeting PAR2 has accelerated over recent years; a recent key example would be the creation of more potent PAR2 antagonists and better understanding of both allosteric and orthosteric binding sites (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). Investigation and development of both antagonists and agonists of the receptor allows for future research to better define the role of the receptor in a lung setting (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). Thus far in the emerging literature it appears that agonists may be present therapeutic value in relation to regulating PAR2 function in a lung setting, due to apparent bronchodilatory effects. On the other hand, however, it may also be beneficial to antagonise PAR2 effects in mediating inflammation to control excessive ASM proliferation and remodelling. The best approach may depend on whether PAR2-targeted therapies are intended for the short or long-term. Increased knowledge in terms of biased signaling induced by particular ligands could lead the way to more specific pharmacological agents to selectively target undesirable downstream activities. As presented in this chapter, the current literature collectively demonstrates important PAR2 functions in ASM. Even still, the exact roles and mechanisms of PAR2 in terms of ASM function have not yet been well elucidated. Furthermore, much of the research to date has been targeted towards asthma and not COPD, leaving considerable scope for investigation of PAR2 as a therapeutic target in the latter disease. Clearly, then, there is a foundation of research signposting the need for future research on PAR2 in the pathogenesis of COPD.

6. Aims

This project investigated the role of proteinase-activated receptor-2 (PAR2) in airway smooth muscle (ASM). As opposing roles have been reported for PAR2 in the airway, both as a bronchorelaxant and an inflammatory mediator, it is unclear still what the exact nature of its roles are in normal and diseased lungs. PAR2 plays a key role in multiple pathological scenarios featuring inflammation, and therefore investigation of PAR2 in regulation of airway function, characteristically dysregulated in chronic bronchitis (Miotto *et al.*, 2002), is the central aim of this doctoral work – and could inform new avenues for developing novel therapies for COPD (Dulon *et al.*, 2003).

Chapter 2:

General Methods

2. General Methods

2.1 Ethics and home office approval

This project utilised *ex vivo* tissues arising from Schedule 1 culls of C57BL/6 mice sourced externally or generated under authority of PPL numbers P989A202D (surplus tissue gathered according to 3Rs principles) and PP4978148 (authorising breeding and maintenance providing murine tissue for the INTERREG-funded BREATH COPD research programme, of which this PhD study is part). Surplus tissues used for the CIA section of the study (Chapter 6) were obtained as kind gifts from the institute of Inflammation, Immunity, and Infection at the University of Glasgow, arising from animals maintained in the University of Glasgow Biological Services Units in accordance with the Home Office UK Licenses P8C60C865, I675F0C46, and ID5D5F18C, and the Ethics Review Board of the University of Glasgow. Procedures were conducted in full compliance with Home Office (HO) regulations and a competent Home Office approved staff member with a personal license performed the cull. Local ethical scrutiny and approval was through AWERBs at UWS and the University of Glasgow. All experimental studies were designed to take account of the principle of replacement, reduction, and refinement (3Rs) so as to minimise the use of individual animals while gaining maximum scientific benefit. For the duration of this project there was no opportunity to replace the *ex vivo* model utilised with cells as this was performed in a whole tissue setting. Reduction was implemented by utilising tissue that was a byproduct of other projects in order to reduce animal usage. Finally, refinement was implemented by ensuring that the animals had appropriate housing with food and water available *ad libitum* and housed in appropriate groups. Some of the experiments outlined involved the use of murine tissue collected from C57BL/6 male and female mice which were being culled as part of another procedure. This also included maximising the tissues excised from these animals for utilisation where appropriate. A Home Office approved staff member with a personal licence performed the cull. A ScotPIL training course certificate was obtained following training: species mouse, in the following areas: E1/L, PIL A, PIL B and PIL C (number: SAB/SCT-W17/106).

2.2 Laboratory facilities

Animals sourced from Envigo (Hillcrest, UK) were housed in the Biological Unit at University of the West of Scotland, Paisley Campus. The majority of animals used within this study were from in-house breeding. The mice were maintained within a 12-hour light/dark cycle with daily health monitoring food and water available *ad libitum*. The mice were housed in Tecniplast S.P.A individually vented cages (Tecniplast, 13103812, Italy).

2.2.1 General reagents and buffers

All general reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (UK), Thermo Fisher Scientific (UK), Invitrogen (UK), and of the highest purity available. The buffers used within this project were prepared as indicated in Table 2.1 below.

Buffer	Source
ELISA wash buffer	1 x PBS, 0.05 % (v/v) Tween-20
ELISA coating buffer	1 x PBS (from ELISA kits) Invitrogen
Stop solution	1M H ₂ SO ₄
Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS)	PBS from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Without CaCl ₂ + MgCl ₂)
Krebs Buffer	NaCl 119 mM, KCl 4.7 mM, MgSO ₄ 1.2 mM, KH ₂ PO ₄ 1.2 mM, CaCl ₂ 2.5 mM, NaHCO ₃ 25 mM, Glucose 5.5 mM dH ₂ O 998 mL/L 10 X stock. Glucose & NaHCO ₃ added fresh daily. Gas with 95 % O ₂ / 5 % C O ₂ .
HEPES buffer	25 mM buffered to pH 7.4 with NaOH
Hanks Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS)	HBSS from Sigma (With NaHCO ₃) (Without Phenol Red, MgSO ₄ & CaCl ₂)

Table 2.1 List of general reagents and buffers. Recipes for reagents and buffers used in the methods of this project.

2.3 Model selection

2.3.1 PAR2^{-/-} murine model

The Centre for Musculoskeletal science (CMS) group has previous experience with use of various inflammatory and arthritic models in rodents. Early in the project the decision was made to use both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2-deficient mouse models based upon the ability to perform definitive loss-of-function experiments and having been widely used previously by the CMS group. A selection of C57BL/6J wild type mice used were sourced from Envigo (Hillcrest, UK) but the primary source of murine tissue came from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} mice from the UWS Paisley C57BL/6J heterozygous breeding colony. As mentioned previously, a PAR2-deficient murine model was previously created by Ferrell *et al.*, 2003. Briefly, homologous recombination in embryonic stem cells (ES) was utilised to create a null allele of the *F2rl1* gene (encoding PAR2) which also included a β -galactosidase reporter gene. A genomic library was screened with a PAR2 cDNA probe to isolate cloned DNA to construct the targeting vector. The targeting vector had a total of 9 kb of cloned genomic DNA which flanked both sides of exon 2 (Figure 2.1). An 813-nucleotide internal region of exon 2 contained as a restriction fragment was removed and replaced with a reporter cassette known as TAG3/IRES/lacZpA/MC1neopA (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003).

Figure 2.1 Gene disruption strategy for the generation of PAR2-deficient mice. The Structure of the PAR2 targeting vector (top), the wild-type PAR2 allele (middle) and the targeted allele (bottom). The generation resulted from replacement recombination at the dashed crosses. The null allele was generated by the substitution of a reporter cassette, which can be seen as the dark purple and connecting light blue boxes, for most of the exon 2 sequence which can be seen as a dark grey box on the wild-type allele. Non-exon containing chromosomal and cloned genomic DNA sequence can be seen as a thick solid black line and pBluescript plasmid sequence can be identified as a thin solid black line. The restriction enzyme sites, *Clal* (C), *HindIII* (H), *KpnI* (K), *NotI* (N), and *Sall* (S) are highlighted by small arrows and respective letters. The sizes of the relevant restriction fragments are indicated by dashed lines. This figure was adapted from Ferrell *et al.*, 2003 and created using Biorender.com.

Preliminary studies exploited surplus tissue from mice harbouring a floxed PAR2 allele (*F2rl1^{fl/fl}*), obtained from the colony bred at UWS, for optimisation work in accordance with the 3Rs guidelines (Aske & Waugh, 2017). The study has utilised PAR2^{-/-} and PAR2^{+/+} genotypes. Within these, two types of airways were used in order to investigate the functional effect of PAR2 activity, alongside parenchymal tissue being utilised for histological purposes. The airways of murine tissue were used to allow an insight into both the expression and the functional role of the receptor of interest, and lung tissue analysis also allows for further, histological information on the receptor in a relevant setting to

COPD. Collectively, appropriate analysis of these two tissue types has contributed to a better understanding of the role of the receptor in the respiratory system. Surplus lung tissue was also taken from a strain of DBA1 mice upon completion of a collagen induced arthritis (CIA) procedure conducted in Glasgow University, in order to study pathological lung changes in this model of inflammatory arthritis.

2.3.2 Generation of a collagen induced arthritis (CIA) murine model

The induction of the CIA model was done externally at the Institute of Inflammation, Immunity and Infection at the University of Glasgow and this study used surplus respiratory tissue generated. CIA was induced in 8–10-week-old male DBA/1 mice (Envigo) on day 0 by intradermal immunisation with bovine type II collagen (MD Biosciences) in Freund’s complete adjuvant (CFA). On day 21, mice received 100 mg of collagen in PBS intraperitoneally. Disease scores were measured every 24 h on a scale from 0 to 4 for each paw. Animals reaching an overall score of 10 or more were immediately euthanised. Animals were maintained in the University of Glasgow Biological Services Units in accordance with the Home Office UK Licenses P8C60C865, I675F0C46, and ID5D5F18C, and the Ethics Review Board of the University of Glasgow. Mice were maintained under 12 h light/dark cycles and standard temperature (20–25 °C) and humidity (40–50 %) (Wang *et al.*, 2021). Following euthanasia by terminal anaesthesia, the lungs were stored directly in 10% (w/v) formalin for fixation for 24 h, before being transferred to 70 % (v/v) ethanol prior to tissue processing. Subsequent to tissue processing the samples then followed the same histological and immunohistochemical analysis described later in section ‘2.7 Histology’ within this chapter.

2.4 Genotyping

Ear tag biopsies were taken from offspring of heterozygous pairings following weaning at 4-5 weeks, for genotyping of the animals. The biopsies taken were collected into 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes (Star labs, UK) and stored at -20 °C until they could be processed for the genotyping protocol (as described below). To isolate genomic DNA from the ear tag biopsies, the Phire Tissue Direct kit from (Thermo Scientific, UK) was used following the instructions provided by the manufacturer. A brief overview of the protocol is as follows; dilution buffer (20 µL) containing a DNA release additive (0.5 µL) was added to each of the ear biopsy samples and incubated for a period of 5 min at room temperature (RT) followed by a 2 min incubation at 98 °C. The Eppendorfs containing the samples were then vortexed and centrifuged for 5 s and the supernatant liquid which contained the DNA was collected. At this point in the procedure the supernatant liquid was either stored at -20 °C for use at a later point or used immediately in a polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with the use of primers generating products specific for wild type or disrupted *F2r11* alleles. At this point, 1 µL of the DNA sample was added to a PCR tube (Thermo Fisher, UK) along with 1 µL of each of the three primers (Primer Design, sequences in Table 2.2 below) which were used at 10 µM, 10 µL of the ready to use Phire Mastermix (Thermo Scientific, UK) and 6 µL of sterile water. The samples were then vortexed and centrifuged for 5 seconds and the tubes thereafter were transferred to a PCR machine (Thermal Cycle, Applied Biosystems) to undergo a specific genotyping thermal cycle program.

Primer	Sequence (5'- 3')	Concentration	Barcode ID
1	AAAGGCAGAGGGCTATCCGA	10 µM	021943979
2	CCTGGAGAACTTGTGGAGC	10 µM	021943988
3	GCCTGCTTGCCGAATATCAT	10 µM	021943995

Table 2.2 Genotyping primer sequences. Table contains details from each of the 3 primers which are used to genotype the animals from the Paisley UWS colony. Column 1 contains the primer number, column 2 the primer sequence from 5'- 3', column 3 the working concentration that the primers are used at within the reaction and finally column 4 contains the barcode ID from primer design related to each primer.

Details of the PCR machine program were as follows; stage 1 involved 5 min at 90 °C, followed by stage 2 which comprised of 25 cycles of 10 s at 98 °C, 10 s at 57 °C and 30 s at 72 °C and stage 3 concluded the program with 5 min at 72 °C followed by a hold step at 4 °C. The PCR products were subject to electrophoresis on a 2 % (w/v) agarose gel which was composed of 2.6 g of agarose (Biorad)

along with 2 μL of ethidium bromide solution (10 mg/mL) (Thermo Scientific, UK) with 130 mL of 1X Tris borate EDTA (TBE) buffer (Thermo Scientific, UK). A DNA ladder (Thermo Scientific, 15628019) was loaded to the gel at a volume of 5 μL along with 10 μL of each sample. The gel was then electrophoresed for a period of approximately 1 hour at 120 V in 1X TBE buffer using a VWR Perfect Blue power supply (VWR, Model 700-1316) and a VWR 10 well 1.5 mm tank (VWR, 700-0743). A homozygous WT sample produced a product size of 302 base pairs (bp) and for a homozygous KO sample the PCR product size was in the range of 482-512 bp. An annotated DNA ladder with appropriate sizes for each genotype can be seen in Figure 2.2 below. The heterozygous product samples contained both bands within the gel. Results were analysed using a UV transilluminator (Clever Scientific, UK).

Figure 2.2 Gel Electrophoresis results from a typical genotyping experiment. Ear tag samples were taken and treated using Phire Tissue Direct kit (Thermo Scientific, UK) and ran on a 2 % (w/v) agarose gel. The DNA ladder on the left side of the image shows the band sizes identified for the $\text{PAR2}^{+/+}$ sample product of 302 bp and the $\text{PAR2}^{-/-}$ sample product of 482-512 bp. Both the $\text{PAR2}^{+/+}$ and the $\text{PAR2}^{-/-}$ samples are shown to have one appropriate band each whilst the HET samples contain both the $\text{PAR2}^{+/+}$ and $\text{PAR2}^{-/-}$ bands as shown above. HET sample lane 3, $\text{PAR2}^{-/-}$ sample lane 4 and $\text{PAR2}^{+/+}$ samples lanes 1, 2, 5, 6, 7 & 8.

2.5 Murine *ex vivo* sample preparation

2.5.1 Schedule 1 method of humane sacrifice

Mice were terminated by a competent Schedule 1 approved member of staff, using the method of rising CO_2 in a sealed chamber. Following this, death was confirmed by cardiac puncture performed using a 26-gauge needle and 1 mL syringe.

2.5.2 Tissue dissection and preparation

Tissue was required for use in a range of experimental procedures, primarily wire myography, histology. Immediately following termination of the animal, hair was removed from the ventral surface and skin layer incised to enter into the abdomen before penetrating the diaphragm to gain access to the lungs. The organs were exposed via cutting straight through the middle of the ribcage; at this point the heart was used as an anchor to prevent damage to the tissue of interest and the organs and airways were removed. Following the removal of the trachea, lungs and heart, the tissue was then placed immediately in cold Krebs' solution pH 7.4 pre-gassed with 95 % O_2 / 5 % CO_2 and pinned out appropriately for fine dissection which involves the removal of the heart and all adipose and connective tissue to allow a better visualisation of the lungs and trachea as can be seen in Figure 2.3 below. Instruments used for the dissection of tissue are listed in Table 2.3.

Instrument	Supplier	Catalogue Number
Student Standard, Pattern Forceps	Fine Science Tools, UK	91100-12
Student Dumont #5 Forceps	Fine Science Tools, UK	91150-20
Student Dumont #7 Forceps	Fine Science Tools, UK	91197-00
Student Bone Scissors	Fine Science Tools, UK	91604-09
Fine Scissors – Tungsten Carbide	Fine Science Tools, UK	14568-12
Student Fine Scissors	Fine Science Tools, UK	91460-11

Vannas Spring Scissors – 2.5 mm Cutting Edge	Fine Science Tools, UK	15000-08
Instrument Case	Fine Science Tools, UK	20830-04
Insect Pins	Fine Science Tools, UK	26000-30

Table 2.3 Surgical Instruments used for murine tissue dissection. List of instruments used for the gross and fine dissection of murine tissue alongside the supplier and relevant catalogue number for each instrument used.

Figure 2.3 Dissection of Murine airways and lungs. Fine dissection of murine Trachea (A), Primary bronchi (B), and lungs (C) to allow visualisation of primary bronchi and trachea following removal from the body. Identification of 2 adjacent cartilage rings, used for measuring method of ring length can be seen in (D). Dissection was carried out using Student Dumont #5 forceps, Student Fine Scissors, Student Bone Scissors and Vannas Spring Scissors 2.5 mm (Fine Science Tools, UK). The representative image was taken using a Zeiss Stemi 2000 microscope (Zeiss, 0000016557).

This allowed clear visualisation for harvesting the trachea/bronchi for either wire myography (airway rings) or histology. Subsequently, for experimentation which involved vascular tissue an adapted dissection was performed to ensure tissues of interest remained intact. The same gross dissection was carried out to remove the airways and lungs from the body, however during the fine dissection a different approach was taken. The heart was left attached for a longer period of time to allow visualisation of the pulmonary arteries from the heart to the lungs as can be seen in Figure 2.4 below.

Figure 2.4 Fine dissection of murine Vascular tissue. Fine dissection of murine airways and lungs was adapted to allow visualisation of primary bronchi (A) and trachea (B) following removal from the body but also the pulmonary arteries (C). Dissection was carried out using Student Dumont #5 forceps, Student Fine Scissors, Student Bone Scissors and Vannas Spring Scissors 2.5 mm (Fine Science Tools, UK). The representative image was taken using a Zeiss Stemi 2000 microscope (Zeiss, 0000016557).

2.5.3 Airway preparation for isometric tension studies

Segments of airways (trachea and primary bronchi) were cut into rings using fine scissors at a maximum length of 2 mm or using 2 adjacent cartilage rings as a measuring method which can be seen in Figure 2.3 above. Airway rings were mounted onto two 40 μm diameter stainless steel wires in a 4-channel myograph (Danish Myo Technology M610, Aarhus, Denmark) for isometric tension recording (captured by LabChart 7, ADInstruments Ltd) as can be seen in Figure 2.5 below.

Figure 2.5 Mounted myograph. Murine bronchial ring (A) mounted by two 40 μm diameter stainless steel wires (B) held in place by screws (C) in one bath of a 4-channel myograph (Danish Myo Technology M610, Aarhus, Denmark) for isometric tension recording (captured by LabChart 7, ADInstruments Ltd).

The airways were allowed to equilibrate for up to 10 min before stepwise changes in the passive tension-internal circumference were performed in order to achieve a stable resting tension of 4 mN for bronchial rings and 5 mN for tracheal rings (optimal tension based on reported values from Liu, Yang & Folz, 2006, Lee-Gosselin *et al.*, 2015, Mikami *et al.*, 2018). Vessels were allowed to equilibrate for a further 20 min at this level of stretch before starting experimental protocols.

2.6 Assessment of airway responsiveness with wire myograph

2.6.1 Standardised airway assessment

Following mounting of the airway rings, the tissue was left to equilibrate with 95 % O₂ / 5 % CO₂ in each bath at a temperature of 37 °C, before stretching to achieve 4 mN of resting tension for bronchial tissue and 5 mN of resting tension for tracheal tissue. Subsequently, tissues were exposed to a depolarizing provocation of KCl (80 mM), to prime the tissue for further experimentation and to provide a non-receptor-mediated level of contraction for each ring. Such data is valuable as a contraction “reference point” to compare contraction produced by receptor-based agonists. The rationale for this is that should an experimental condition lead to altered contraction then this could be due to either a modification of the contractile potential of the cells (e.g., possibly due to alteration in actin/myosin crossover capacity (Taylor *et al.*, 2019)) or due to changes in the receptor profile (e.g., increase or decrease in receptor population could lead to changes in contraction (Brozovich *et al.*, 2016)). Comparison of receptor-dependent contraction to the non-receptor dependent contraction (i.e., induced by KCl) gives an insight in to the likely mechanism. Following the priming with KCl, the baths were washed out three times with Krebs solution. Following this, a muscarinic receptor agonist, acetylcholine, was used as a contractile agent, before stimulation with a known PAR2 activating agonist, Trypsin or FLIGRLO-NH₂. Table 2.4 below lists a range of drugs and reagents used specifically throughout this study to target receptors of interest and for non-receptor dependent muscle functional assessment. All drugs and solutions used were added directly to the myograph chambers and were removed through air-suction (method adapted from Hamilton and MacKenzie, 2015). This default method of airway contraction was utilised in all protocols with adaptations for each section of the study noted in the subsequent sections below.

<i>Drug</i>	<i>Mechanism of Action</i>	<i>Concentration Range</i>
Acetylcholine (ACh)	Muscarinic receptor agonist	1 µM
Potassium Chloride (KCl)	Depolarising agent	80 mM
Trypsin	PAR2 agonist	10 U
2-Furoyl-LIGRLO-amide	PAR2 selective agonist peptide	0.01 – 10 µM
2-Furoyl-OLIGRL-amide	Scrambled peptide	0.01 – 10 µM
Superoxide Dismutase (SOD)	Antioxidant	100-500 U

Table 2.4 List of drugs used for wire myography experimentation. List of drugs which were utilised during wire myography experimentation. Details also provided of the concentration range each drug was used at and their mechanism of action.

2.6.2 Airway contractility assessment in male and female tissue

Male and female PAR2^{+/+} tissue was utilised and bronchial and tracheal contractile responsiveness in response to PAR2 activation was investigated. The basic airway contraction protocol described above in section ‘2.6.1’ of this chapter was used and following the addition of acetylcholine, once a steady state of contraction was achieved using (ACh 10⁻⁶ M), trypsin (10 U/mL⁻¹) was added to indicate the response likely attributable to PAR2 in the different sex samples. Following washout, the tissue was then left to recover for a period of 30-45 min before following the protocol described above but with the addition of PAR2 agonist peptide 2-Furoyl-LIGRLO-amide at 0.01-10 µM (Dundalk Institute of Technology, DKIT, Ireland). Subsequently, an internal control was carried out using a scrambled peptide at 0.01-10 µM (2-Furoyl-OLIGRL-NH₂) also a kind gift from Dr Nicholas Mullins, DkIT, to validate the PAR2 peptide specificity. The full experimental procedure was reproduced using tracheal tissue from both male and female PAR2^{+/+} tissue.

2.6.3 Heterozygous vs. homozygous derived PAR2^{-/-} mice

Bronchial and tracheal tissue was obtained from both heterozygous and homozygous derived mice to compare functional response from differing PAR2^{-/-} origins. The protocol used was the same as the protocol listed in section above '2.6.1' of this chapter.

2.6.4 Airway assessment following exposure to pathology-relevant challenges

Due to COPD being a multifactorial disease, there is a necessity to investigate the effects of various disease relevant insults on the ASM function. A selection of challenges typical of different disease stages were chosen to be explored, oxidative stress as an environmental/smoking-linked challenge which affects COPD patients across all disease stages and impact of age on ASM functionality (Kirkham & Barnes, 2013, Banerjee *et al.*, 2014).

2.6.4.1 Oxidative stress in the airways

Airway rings from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} samples were stored within a 96 well plate, in 200 µl of DMEM, 1 % (v/v) Pen/Strep, pH 7.4. Tissue sections were incubated overnight (typically 22 h) at 4 °C to act as a control while matched tissue sections were incubated over the same time period at 37 °C in a 95 % O₂ / 5 % CO₂ incubator. This protocol is adapted from a study by Aman *et al.*, (2010) who demonstrated that this method caused an oxidative stress-induced elevation in PAR2 in mouse aorta in the 37 °C incubated tissues, which was absent in those incubated at 4 °C (Aman *et al.*, 2010). The standard protocol described above in section '2.6.1' of this chapter.

2.6.4.2 Antioxidant incubation to reverse/validate oxidative stress induction

Airway rings from PAR2^{+/+} samples were stored within a 96 well plate, in 200 µl of DMEM, pH 7.4 in the absence of superoxide dismutase (SOD) (Sigma, S5395-15KU) as a control condition in (10 % FCS (v/v), 1 % Pen/Strep (v/v)). Airway rings were also stored in 200 µl total well volumes with concentrations of 100, 250 and 500 U SOD at both 37 °C and 4 °C. Tissue sections were incubated overnight (typically 22 h) at 4 °C to act as a control setting and similarly matched tissue sections were incubated over a same period of time at 37 °C in a 95 % O₂ / 5 % CO₂ incubator. This protocol is based on study by Aman *et al.*, (2010) whom used antioxidants in the same conditions used to impose oxidative stress to then reverse the observations. The same standard protocol for airway assessment was used as described in section '2.6.1' of this chapter. This same protocol was carried out again using another antioxidant, catalase (Sigma, C1345-1G) to further confirm the effects of antioxidants on the condition and unravel the mechanism behind the response observed. The same concentrations and conditions were used and repeated as was done with the SOD experiments detailed.

2.6.4.3 ≤ 4 Months cf. ≥ 12 Months

Bronchial tissue was obtained from both PAR2^{+/+} young adult mice and older adult mice and PAR2^{-/-} young adult mice and older adult mice and functionality in response to PAR2 activation was investigated. Bronchial rings from ≥ 12 months murine tissue obtained under PPL: PP4978148 which allows for maintenance of mice up to the age of ≥ 12 months, were mounted into two of the baths and bronchial rings from young mice (culled at ≤ 4 months) were mounted into the remaining baths. The same assessment was carried out as in the standard protocol described in section '2.6.1' of this chapter. The choice of these age groups was based on the information provided on mice maturity by the Jackson Laboratory, and the timeline for an ageing mouse can be seen in Figure 2.6 below. In human COPD, most patients present with reduced lung function from middle age (Duncan, 2016).

Figure 2.6 Life phase equivalencies of murine vs human. Life history stages in C57BL/6J mice in comparison to human beings. Reproduced with permission from Flurkey, Curren, and Harrison, 2007.

2.6.5 Data and statistical analysis

Results were analysed and expressed as the mean and SEM from at least $n=3$ experiments. All statistical analyses and related generation of graphs were performed using GraphPad Prism 7 (GraphPad, San Diego, CA, USA). Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM; n values represent the number of animals used with no more than one vessel segment per protocol per animal. Vessel ring contractions in response to KCl and ACh are expressed as the force generated in units of $\text{mN}\cdot\text{mm}^{-1}$ (standardised to mm length of each bronchial or tracheal ring) and also, for trypsin and FLIGRL standardised to ACh and expressed as percentage (%) relaxation of the ACh-induced contraction for that individual ring. Concentration-response curves were created, and statistical comparisons (t-test or one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's post-hoc test as appropriate) made with the aid of a computer programme, GraphPad Prism; $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

2.7 Histology

2.7.1 Tissue fixation and processing

Immediately following termination, the airways and lungs were dissected free of the carcass and care taken not to twist, tear, bend or overstretch the tissue, this procedure is fully described in section '2.5.2 Tissue Dissection and preparation'. The sections of tissue were then placed directly into 10 % (v/v) buffered formalin for a minimum period of 4 h before being transferred into 70 % (v/v) ethanol for storage; alternatively, they were placed directly into the processor following excision for fixation. Before being placed into the processor, the tissue samples were placed into individual cassettes (CellPath, UK System II HEX cassette EAD-0102-03A and System II HEX Cassette lid EAE-0102-

03A). If smaller tissue samples are being processed CellPath polyester acid resistant bags (EBF-0300-02P) were used to secure the tissue within the cassette. Once in the Thermo Scientific Excelsior AS tissue processor model A82310100, the samples were processed (beginning from the fixative stage if not previously fixed) and subsequently passed through various concentrations of ethanol (EtOH) and finally xylene to dehydrate the samples. The exact details of the routine overnight processing programme that was used can be found in Table 2.5.

Step	Reagent	Temp (°C)	Time (hh:mm)	Vac	Drain time (sec)	
1	10 % Formalin	amb	0:30	Off	30	
2	10 % Formalin	amb	0:30	Off	60	
3	Dehydrant Group (Alcohol)	75 %	30	1:00	On	30
4		90 %	30	1:00	On	30
5		95 %	30	1:00	On	30
6		100 %	30	1:00	On	30
7		100 %	30	1:00	On	30
8		100 %	30	1:00	On	60
9	Clearant Group (Xylene)	30	1:00	On	30	
10		30	1:00	On	30	
11		30	1:00	On	120	
12	Infiltration Group (Wax)	62	1:20	On	120	
13		62	1:20	On	120	
14		62	1:20	On	120	

Table 2.5 Full Thermo Scientific Excelsior AS tissue routine overnight processing programme. Full breakdown of the routine overnight tissue processing programme utilised during the histological analysis of all tissue samples. The Table highlights the order of the reagents used alongside the temperature and time for each part of the processing.

2.7.2 Embedding

Once processed the tissue sections are then directly embedded in 60 °C paraffin wax (Lamb wax, Fisher scientific, 12624077) using the Thermo Scientific HistoStar embedding workstation. First of all, in this process of embedding, the base of the mould is prefilled with 60 °C paraffin wax. From there the tissue is added to the wax using tweezers and then the mould is placed onto the 5 °C cold spot until the wax becomes translucent. At this point in the procedure, placement, and orientation of the samples within the wax blocks were performed quickly, important for the next step of cutting the sections onto slides. Following this, the original cassette in which the tissue was processed was placed on top of the mould containing the tissue. This was then filled up with 60 °C paraffin wax. Once the wax had been placed into the cassettes containing the tissue, the blocks were then placed onto the cold plate section of the embedding station. The blocks were left to cool and harden at -12 °C on the HistoStar cold module section of the embedding station (Thermo Scientific).

2.7.3 Microtome

Following the embedding portion of the technique the paraffin blocks were then cut using the Thermo Scientific HM 355S automated microtome with Coolcut module and Section Transfer System. These tissue sections were then cut onto Starfrost slides (Cellpath, UK, MBB-0302-55A) at a depth of 5 µM. The sections were cut at a velocity of 25, water speed of 10, water bath temperature of 42 °C and a blade angle of 9 °C. The sections were then dried overnight onto slides (Starfrost microscope slides, Cellpath, UK, MBB-0302-55A) using a Heraeus instruments oven at 65 °C bonding the tissue to the slide prior to staining procedures.

2.7.4 Haematoxylin and eosin staining

Haematoxylin and eosin stain kit (Vector Laboratories, UK, H-3502) was used for characterisation of tissue via the haematoxylin (nuclear) and cytoplasmic component staining by eosin. The staining was carried out based on the protocol provided by the supplier. The tissue sections were dewaxed using xylene for 2 min followed by rehydration of the sections through various decreasing concentrations of EtOH (100 %, 90 %, 80 %, 70 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. Following this step, the slides were stained

using an adequate amount of haematoxylin to completely cover the tissue sections and incubated for 5 min. The slides were then rinsed in 2 changes of distilled water (dH₂O) for approximately 15 seconds each wash with the purpose of removing any excess stain. Thereafter, tissue sections were then incubated for 10-15 seconds with a sufficient amount of bluing reagent to convert the haematoxylin from red to the customary blue colour. Again, the slides were then rinsed in 2 changes of dH₂O for approximately 15 seconds to wash off any excess stain. The slides were then dipped in 100 % (v/v) ethanol for 10 seconds and then blotted to remove excess. The sections were then incubated with an adequate amount of eosin Y solution and incubated for 2-3 min. The slides were then dehydrated through various increasing concentrations of EtOH (70 %, 80 %, 90 %, 100 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. Lastly, the slides were cleared for 2 min in xylene before mounting the coverslips (Cellpath, UK, SAJ-2250-03A) using DPX mounting media (Cellpath, UK, SEA-1304-00A).

2.7.5 Masson's Trichrome stain

Masson's Trichrome stain (Abcam, UK, ab150686) was used with the intention of histological visualisation of connective tissue and smooth muscle in murine lung tissue sections both paraffin-embedded and also frozen sections. In the context of the lung, the stain can be interpreted as blue signifying the presence of collagen, muscle fibres staining red, and the nuclei of cells stained black/blue. The staining was carried out based on the protocol provided by the supplier. Bouin's fluid (composed of saturated picric acid, formaldehyde, and glacial acetic acid) was preheated in a water bath at 56 °C before starting the protocol. The tissue sections were dewaxed using xylene for 2 min followed by rehydration of the sections through various decreasing concentrations of EtOH (100 %, 90 %, 80 %, 70 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. The slides were then placed in the preheated Bouin's fluid for 60 min followed by a 10 min cooling period. This solution was used as it was advised to be a good fixative for use when soft and delicate tissue structures must be preserved to the slide. Following this step, the slides were then rinsed in tap water until the sections were completely clear, followed by one rinse in dH₂O. Next, equal parts of Weigert's (A) and Weigert's (B) (components include haematoxylin, ferric chloride, and hydrochloric acid) were mixed together, and the slides were stained for 5 min with working Weigert's haematoxylin. This solution is mixed freshly as ferric chloride, which is one of the components, acts as an oxidiser and so the working solution does not remain stable for a period longer than 8 days. The slides were then rinsed again in running tap water for 2 min to remove any excess stain. Biebrich scarlet/acid fuchsin solution (composed of glacial acetic acid, distilled water, biebrich scarlet, acid fuchsin) was then added to the slides for an incubation period of 15 min, followed by a further rinse in distilled water. The sections were then differentiated in phosphomolybdic/phosphotungstic acid solution for 10-15 min for the desired effect of removing the red stain from the collagen. Without a rinsing step, aniline blue solution was added to the slides for 5-10 min. The sections were then rinsed in distilled water to remove excess stain before applying 1 % acetic acid (v/v) to the slides for 3-5 min. The slides were then dehydrated through various increasing concentrations of EtOH (70 %, 80 %, 90 %, 100 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. Lastly, the slides were cleared for 2 min in xylene before mounting the coverslips (Cellpath, UK, SAJ-2250-03A) using DPX mounting media (Cellpath, UK, SEA-1304-00A).

2.7.6 Immunohistochemistry

ImmPRESS HRP Horse Anti-Rabbit IgG (peroxidase) polymer detection kit (Vector laboratories, UK, MP-7401) was used for detection of various antibodies on murine tissue. The ImmPRESS polymer kit is an enzymatic, ready to use, non-biotin method of amplification. The tissue sections were dewaxed using xylene for 2 min followed by rehydration of the sections through various decreasing concentrations of EtOH (100 %, 90 %, 80 %, 70 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. For antigen unmasking of PAR2, Unitrieve was used at a temperature of 65 °C using a water bath for a period of 1 hour. For other antigens, an antigen retrieval buffer (100 X Citrate buffer pH 6.0 composed of Mixture 1 % (v/v) hydrochloric acid, 1.5 % (v/v) 2-butoxyethanol) was used at a concentration of 1 X (Abcam, UK, ab93678) at 80 °C in the water bath for an incubation of 15 min. The blocking of endogenous peroxidases was then carried out by incubating the slides in 1 % (v/v) hydrogen peroxide (Sigma, H1009-100 mL) in MeOH (Thermo Fisher, BP1105-4) for 30 min. Following this incubation, the slides were then washed for 5 min twice in 1 X PBS pH 7.4. At this point in the protocol, an Immedge pen

(Vector laboratories, UK, H-4001) was used to draw a wax ring around each specific tissue section to allow easy distinguishability between tissue sections and to contain reagents. The tissue sections were then incubated for 20 min with ready to use 2.5 % (v/v) normal horse blocking serum (Merck, H0146-10 mL). Following this incubation, the primary antibody was diluted in 800 µL of PBS/BSA 0.5 % (w/v) and 200 µL of horse serum. At this stage were incubated either for 2 h at RT or overnight at 4 °C. The slides were then washed for 5 min in 1 X PBS followed by a 30 min incubation with the ImmPRESS reagent provided with the kit which acts as the secondary antibody reagent. This incubation was followed by 2 x 5 min washes in 1 X PBS. Finally, the sections were incubated in peroxidase substrate solution until the desired stain intensity developed; the peroxidase substrate solution used was impact DAB peroxidase (HRP) Substrate (Vector laboratories, UK, SK-4105). The sections were then rinsed in tap water and counterstained using haematoxylin. The slides were then dehydrated through various increasing concentrations of EtOH (70 %, 80 %, 90 %, 100 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. Lastly, the slides were cleared for 2 min in xylene before mounting the coverslips (Cellpath, UK, SAJ-2250-03A) using DPX mounting media (Cellpath, UK, SEA-1304-00A).

2.7.7 Mouse on mouse kit (M.O.M.)

ImmPRESS Peroxidase polymer M.O.M. kit (Vector laboratories, UK, MP-2400) was used to detect mouse antibodies bound to mouse tissue. The main conflict with using mouse primary antibodies for immunohistochemical detection on mouse tissue is the failure to differentiate between the mouse primary antibody and endogenous mouse immunoglobulins which can therefore result in high background staining which can obscure specific staining. The M.O.M. kit eliminates this issue by using a proprietary M.O.M. mouse IgG blocking reagent which includes a specialised ImmPRESS anti-mouse IgG to considerably reduce the undesired binding to native immunoglobulins. All of the steps within this protocol were carried out at RT. The tissue sections were dewaxed using xylene for 2 min followed by rehydration of the sections through various decreasing concentrations of EtOH (100 %, 90 %, 80 %, 70 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. For antigen unmasking, an antigen retrieval buffer (100 X Citrate buffer pH 6.0) was used (Abcam, UK, ab93678) at 80 °C in the water bath for an incubation of 15 min. The sections were then washed for 2 min twice in 1 X PBS. Following this, sections were incubated for a 1 h in working solution of M.O.M., mouse IgG blocking reagent, prepared by adding 2 drops of stock solution (approx. 45 µL) to 2.5 mL of 1 X PBS. After 60 min incubation the sections were then washed for a further 2 min twice in 1 X PBS. The next step involved the sections being incubated for 5 min in ready to use 2.5 % (v/v) normal horse serum; following this the excess serum was blotted off and the primary antibody prepared. The antibody was diluted in ready to use 2.5 % (v/v) horse serum and the sections were incubated with the prepared diluted primary antibody for 30 min at RT. Following this incubation, the slides were then washed for 2 min twice in 1 X PBS. The vector M.O.M. ImmPRESS reagent was then applied to the sections for a 10 min incubation period before being washed for 2 x 5 min periods in 1 X PBS. Finally, the peroxidase substrate solution, impact DAB peroxidase (HRP) Substrate (Vector laboratories, UK, SK-4105) was used until the desired stain intensity was developed. The sections were then rinsed in tap water and counterstained using haematoxylin. The slides were then dehydrated through increasing concentrations of EtOH (70 %, 80 %, 90 %, 100 % EtOH; v/v) for 2 min each. Lastly, the slides were cleared for 2 min in xylene before mounting the coverslips (Cellpath, UK, SAJ-2250-03A) using DPX mounting media (Cellpath, UK, SEA-1304-00A). All of the antibodies used for immunohistochemistry and the relevant dilutions and isotypes can be found in Table 2.6.

Target	Primary	Isotype	Company	Catalogue Number	Dilution IHC
PAR2	Rabbit Polyclonal 600 µg/mL	Rabbit Polyclonal IgG	Alomone Labs, Jerusalem, Israel	APR-032	1:400
Smooth Muscle Actin	Mouse Monoclonal IgG ¹ 200 µg/mL	Mouse Monoclonal IgG ¹	Santa Cruz Biotechnology, California, United States	sc-53142	1:50

Neutrophil Elastase	Rabbit Polyclonal IgG 73 µg/mL	Rabbit Polyclonal IgG	Abcam, UK	Ab21595	1:200
Superoxide Dismutase	Rabbit Polyclonal IgG 50 µg/mL	Rabbit Polyclonal IgG	Abcam, UK	Ab13498	1:100

Table 2.6 Antibodies used for Immunohistochemistry. Primary antibodies and associated isotypes are detailed with the dilutions used for each technique and the company and catalogue number.

2.7.8 Zeiss Axio Scan Z.1 image capture

Once stained, the slides are scanned using Zeiss Axio scanner Z.1 and images obtained with specific settings. The scan profile used for all slide scanning was ‘BF H&E 20x EDF’ which translates to brightfield, haematoxylin and eosin with a 20 x objective lens and an extended depth of field imaging. The camera was a Hitachi HV-F202SCL, and the settings included resolution of 2592x1944 - 12 bit and an exposure time of 15 ms with a 70 % intensity.

2.7.9 Zen Blue image analysis

Image analysis using Zeiss Zen Blue software (airways)

ZEN image analysis software (Zeiss, Blue, UK) was used to analyse ten ROIs (examples can be found in Figure 2.7) were selected with a constant area of approximately 20,900 µm² for each sample using the circle tool and taking the area measurement from within that, ideally identifying an individual airway for analysis. Three sections of the airway wall were then selected and an average thickness was taken using the ‘distance’ tool. Finally, the results were analysed and expressed as the mean and SEM from the number of experiments carried out, and statistical comparisons were made using Student’s unpaired t test.

Figure 2.7 CIA Airway image analysis. Lung lobular tissue was taken from 3 collagen-induced arthritis murine samples and 4 naïve samples. All samples were stained with Masson’s Trichrome stain (Abcam) and small airways identified within a set ROI within the parenchymal tissue. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio Scanner Z.1 and analysed using ZEN software. (A) Naïve airway (n=4); (B) CIA model airway (n=3); (A-B) three alveolar walls selected for measurement (n=4-3) each measurement was made using the distance tool.

Image analysis using Zeiss Zen Blue software (alveolar)

ZEN image analysis software (Zeiss, Blue, UK) was used to analyse ten regions of interest (examples can be found in Figure 2.8) were selected with a constant area of approximately $1,600 \mu\text{m}^2$ for each sample using the circle tool and taking the area measurement from within that, identifying an individual alveolus for analysis. Total cells present within this region of interest were counted using the tool named 'events'. Subsequently, three septal walls were selected and an average thickness of the three measured using the 'distance' tool.

Figure 2.8 CIA Model alveolar analysis. Lung Parenchymal tissue was taken from 3 collagen-induced arthritis murine samples and 4 naïve samples. All samples were stained with Masson's Trichrome stain (Abcam) and alveoli identified within a set ROI within the parenchymal tissue. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio Scanner Z.1 and analysed using ZEN software. (A-C) naïve parenchyma; (B-D) CIA model parenchyma; (A-B) region of interest selected for total cell count, using circle tool to obtain the region of interest and events tool to count each individual cell; (C-D) three alveolar walls selected for measurement ($n=3-4$) each measurement was made using the distance tool.

Structural Differentiation (Arterioles vs. Airways)

A key distinction that was utilised to differentiate between arterioles and airways was the epithelial layer. This ciliated pseudostratified epithelial layer is a key identifying feature for the airways that differs to the arterioles. Similarly, the non-nucleated erythrocytes can often be seen in the lumen of the arterioles and are absent from the airways, thus allowing easy identification. The two structures often run parallel with the airways being larger in size compared with the arterioles.

2.7.10 StrataQuest image analysis

Image analysis using TissueGnostics StrataQuest software

StrataQuest software (version 7.0.1.175, Tissue Gnostics, Vienna) was used to analyse the average mean intensity and tissue density of various stains within each sample group. In the first instance, the files containing the samples for analysis were opened and a cache of the image built as can be seen in Figure 2.9 below, which allowed the data to be stored so that future requests and commands for that particular data could be produced faster.

Figure 2.9 StrataQuest Cache builder. The selected files are opened, and a cache of the image is built by the software. The red box on the image identifies the task manager, where the progress for the cache building can be monitored for each sample.

Once the cache had been built for each sample, the regions of interest (ROI) were then added to each sample section. The region of interest size was selected and standardised based on the specific tissue being analysed. For example, throughout this study, parenchyma, small airways, and arterioles were all analysed and various sizes of regions of interest used as can be seen in Figure 2.10 with specific area sizes shown in Table 2.7 below.

Figure 2.10 Region of interest set-up. To select a standardised ROI, the button circled in blue is chosen and the ROI selected. The green arrow shows the ROI stamp that appears following the selection of the ROI button. This stamp is then used to place ROIs evenly across the tissue section, as can be seen in the figure. Finally, the red box shows the list of samples within the project and the ROIs within each sample.

Within each sample stained with an antibody, 6 ROIs were selected throughout the stained sections for each tissue type and 6 ROIs stained with the isotype were also selected. For samples stained with either trichrome or haematoxylin and eosin stains 10 ROIs were selected using the standardised areas shown in Table 2.7 below. Once the ROIs were established within each section, an in-depth analysis window was opened by double clicking on one of the samples from the project items list identified within Figure 8 above. The analysis window shown in Figure 2.11 below, shows the different parameter options for set-up of each project. The first step of analysis was the selection of reference shades using the colour picker tool which can be seen in the red circle. The reference shades are then selected using this tool and listed in the blue box below the colour picker for each marker and haematoxylin. Other parameters are also set using the tabs in the purple square to determine different settings for the analysis of the samples within the project. Standardised nuclear parameters are set for nuclear segmentation, for example nuclear detection was set within the software for up to specific recommended sizes. There is also a parameter set which identifies and excludes artifacts smaller than 1 μm in size from the analysis. The different standardised parameters set within the projects can be seen in Table 2.7 below.

Figure 2.11 Project parameters set-up. Several parameters are selected within each project to allow for standardised analysis across all samples. The reference shades (blue box) selected using the colour picker tool (red circle) allow for the software to identify specific colours as positive stains due to the absorbance wavelengths corresponding to the reference shades selected for each dye. The exterior ring mask chosen from the other parameter tabs (purple box) allows the software to identify and associate any positive stain within the distance of the exterior ring mask from each identified cell.

Tissue type	ROI size (mm ²)	Exterior ring mask (µm)	Number of reference shades
Parenchyma	0.15	0.44	5
Airways	0.03	0.44	5
Arterioles	0.009	0.44	5

Table 2.7. StrataQuest analysis sample information. The selected ROI standardised size used for analysis alongside the exterior ring mask size and number of reference shades identified are detailed within this table.

Once the parameters had all been set and ROIs selected the analysis was begun by selecting the Analyse button highlighted in the red circle in Figure 2.12 below. Once the analysis was completed of all the samples, the status changed from 'not processed' to 'processed' in the project items list. Finally, the statistics report was generated from the project analysis by clicking on the statistics report button circled in blue on Figure 2.12 below.

Figure 2.12 Sample Processing. Once all parameters are set, the analysis begins by selecting the analyse button identified in the red circle above. Once the analysis is complete, the statistics report is generated by selecting the statistics report button identified in blue above.

Finally, the statistics report is produced as a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and the data then managed using Excel and analysed using Prism 7 (GraphPad, San Diego).

2.8 Primary cell culture

2.8.1 Cell culture and maintenance

Primary human bronchial smooth muscle cells (hBSMC) were purchased commercially after isolation from bronchi tissue of various patients. Three different batches of (hBSMCs) derived from to 3 donors were purchased from Lonza (CC-2576) and 2 from Promocell (C-12561); the donor details can be seen in the table below. All cells utilised were between passage 2 and 6. All information for the above patients can be seen in Table 2.8.

Company	Product Code	Lot Number	Sex	Age	Race	Tissue Localisation	Pathology
Lonza	CC-2576	0000581076	male	57	Hispanic	Bronchi/Main Bronchi	Healthy
Promocell	C-12561	397Z013.3	male	64	Caucasian	Bronchi/Main Bronchi	Healthy
Promocell	C-12561	432Z016.3	female	56	Caucasian	Bronchi/Main Bronchi	Healthy
Lonza	CC-2576	0000613768	Male	83	Caucasian	Bronchi/Main Bronchi	Healthy
Lonza	CC-2576	18TL138668	Male	65	Caucasian	Bronchi/Main Bronchi	Healthy
Lonza	CC-2576	18TL127528	Female	30	Hispanic	Bronchi/Main Bronchi	Healthy

Table 2.8 Bronchial Smooth Muscle patient information. Company and catalogue number alongside generic information on race, pathology, sex, and age from each of the bronchial smooth muscle cell patients detailed within this table.

All cell work was undertaken in a class II tissue culture facility. The cells were cultured in a Panasonic incubator (MCO-19MUVPE) at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂ in complete growth medium ready-to-use (Promocell, C-27062), composed of basal medium plus supplement (Promocell, C-39267) with 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin (Gibco, 15140-122). The medium was changed every two days until cells were approximately 80 % confluent and ready to be passaged. For the subculture of these cells, the media was removed, and the cells were washed with DPBS (Lonza, 17-512F) and Accutase (Promocell, C-41310); the enzymatic dissociation solution was added to detach the cells. Cells were incubated 3 min at 37 °C in the presence of Accutase and then harvested in complete bronchial smooth muscle media. The cell suspension was centrifuged at 1400 rpm for 5 min (Thermo Scientific Heraeus Labofuge 400), the supernatant liquid discarded, and the pellet was then resuspended in complete media.

For automated cell counting, 30 µL of Trypan Blue (Sigma, T8154-100 mL) was mixed with an equal volume of cell suspension. This mix (10 µL) was then loaded onto cell counting slides (Biorad, 1450011), counted using a Biorad TC20 automated cell counter and seeded accordingly. Cells were also counted manually in some instances using a Neubauer haemocytometer counting chamber 0.1 mm² (Neubauer, A51000) and Trypan Blue dye exclusion. An equal 1:1 mixture of cells and Trypan Blue was created and 10 µL of this suspension pipetted under a coverslip on a haemocytometer and visualised using an inverted phase contrast microscope (Motic AE31). The number of unstained cells (non-blue viable cell population) in each corner quadrant of the haemocytometer was counted. The total viable cell number was calculated using Equation 1 below.

$$\text{Number of cells per mL} = \left(\frac{N}{4}\right) * 2 * 10,000$$

Where N = total cell count & 2 is dilution factor.

Equation 2.1 Calculation for cell quantification.

2.8.2 Cryopreservation & thawing

Following expansion of the cells, the media was removed, and the cells were washed with DPBS (Lonza, 17-512F) and Accutase (Promocell, C-41310), the enzymatic dissociation solution was added to detach the cells. Cells were incubated 3 min at 37 °C in the presence of Accutase and then harvested in complete bronchial smooth muscle media. The cell suspension was centrifuged at 350 g for 5 min (Thermo Scientific Heraeus Labofuge 400), the supernatant liquid discarded, and the pellet was then resuspended in sterile freezing medium (70 % complete media, 20 % (v/v) foetal bovine serum (Gibco, 26140-079) and 10 % (v/v) dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) (Sigma, 472301-1L). Cells were counted as described above) and approximately 2 million cells were aliquoted into each cryovial (Starlab, E3110-6122). To thaw cells, the cryovial was transferred to a 37 °C water bath and allowed to defrost. Once thawed, the cells were then placed into a T25 cm² flask with 5 mL of complete media.

2.8.3 MTT viability assay (Tetrazolium dye, [3-(4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide])

Mitochondrial respiration was measured in this assay as a surrogate for viability, to provide an estimate of cell proliferation over a longer period of time. Cells were seeded in a 96 well plate at a density of 0.01 x 10⁶ cells per well 24 h before stimulation to allow time for the cells to adhere to the plate. Following each relevant stimulation, MTT powder (Merck, M5655) was dissolved at 5 mg/mL in sterile PBS and sterilised through the use of a 0.22 µm filter, whilst in a dark environment. The media was replaced with 100 µL/well of serum-free fresh media and 10 µL of MTT solution was added to each well. The plate was incubated in the dark at 37 °C in the CO₂ incubator for 3 h. Finally, the media was removed from each well and the precipitate at the bottom of the plate was dissolved in 80 µL of DMSO per well. The plate was then incubated for 10 min at 37 °C and subsequently read on a plate reader (Biotek, ELX 800) at absorbance of 595 nm using GEN5 1.08 Software.

2.8.4 Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)

The levels of interleukin (IL)-8, IL-6, IL-1 β and tumour necrosis factor (TNF)- α from conditioned media were determined using commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs), as per manufacturer's instructions (all Invitrogen, UK). Briefly, 96 well ELISA plates (Greiner Microlon, Merck, United States) were coated with 100 μ L per well of appropriate capture antibody in coating buffer, sealed and incubated overnight at 4 $^{\circ}$ C. Following incubation, wells were aspirated and washed three times with 200 μ L per well of wash buffer (1X PBS/0.05 % (v/v) Tween-20) with a 1-minute soaking time in between washes and the plate then blotted on absorbent paper to remove residual buffer. The wells were then blocked with 200 μ L per well of X1 ELISA/ELISPOT assay diluent (X5 stock diluted with deionised water and supplied with the kit) and incubated at RT for 1 hour. Wells were again washed, and standards prepared (recombinant protein supplied with the kit) by two-fold dilutions and pipetted in duplicate to form an 8-point standard curve and read on a plate reader (Biotek ELX 800) at absorbance of 595 nm using GEN5 1.08 Software. The concentrations used were specific to the analyte being measured. Individual analyte information and the range of standards for each can be seen below in Table 2.9.

Analyte	Coating Antibody	Detection Antibody	Range of Standards	Catalogue number
IL-6	250x	250x	2-200 pg/mL	88-7066-86
IL-8	250x	250x	2-250 pg/mL	88-8086-88
TNF- α	250x	250x	4-500 pg/mL	88-7346-88

Table 2.9 Antibodies and standards used for enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays. Company and catalogue number alongside generic information Antibody concentration and range for each assay standard.

2.8.5 Immunofluorescence

A sterile treated 13 mm cover slip (Thermo Fisher, 174950) was placed into each well of a 24 well tissue culture plate and 0.05×10^6 cells added in 500 μ L of complete media and the cells then allowed to adhere. After a period of 24 h, cells were then fixed with 4 % paraformaldehyde (Life Technologies, FB002). PBS was then added to each well and the plate stored at 4 $^{\circ}$ C until the immunofluorescence (IF) protocol was commenced. Firstly, the membranes were permeabilised with Triton X-100 (Sigma, T9284) in 0.1% (v/v) phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Lonza, 17-512F) and cells blocked with 5 % (v/v) horse serum (Thermo Fisher, 16050130) in Triton X-100 in 0.5 % (v/v) PBS (IF buffer). Primary antibody (200 μ L), which is also prepared in IF buffer, was added to each well and the cells incubated overnight at 4 $^{\circ}$ C. The following day, the primary antibody was aspirated, and the coverslips washed three times in PBS for 10 min. The appropriate fluorescently labelled secondary antibody Invitrogen (A48276) Alexa Fluor-488, Goat anti-human IgG, was added to each well and incubated with the cells for 1 hour at RT. Finally, the cover slips were washed twice with PBS and treated with 2 μ g/mL Hoechst reagent (Life Technologies, H3570), washed a further twice with PBS and then mounted onto slides using DPX (di-styrene, plasticizer, and xylene) mounting medium (Cell Path, SEA1304-00A). Images were captured using an Olympus IX71 microscope using the DAPI filter (excitation and emission wavelength of 358/461 nm) and the GFP filter (excitation and emission wavelength of 488/509 nm) using 10, 20 and 100 X objective lens and analysed subsequently using ImageJ software to merge the images with the different filters used. The final concentration of primary and secondary antibodies used in the IF protocol are summarised in Table 2.10. Appropriate isotype controls were included for all experiments.

Target	Primary	Isotype	Company	Catalogue Number	Dilution IHC	Dilution IF
PAR2	Rabbit Polyclonal 0.6 mg/mL	Rabbit Polyclonal IgG	Alomone Labs, Jerusalem, Israel	APR-32	1:400	1:200

Table 2.10 Antibody used for Immunofluorescence. Primary antibody and associated isotypes are detailed with the dilutions used for each technique and the company and catalogue number.

2.8.6 Intracellular calcium influx

Cells were seeded at a density of 3×10^4 per well into a 96-well black clear bottomed plates (Thermo, 1653050) 24 h prior to the experiment. Each vial of the calcium indicators Fluo-4 NW (Invitrogen, F36206) were resuspended in 10 mL of assay buffer and probenecid resuspended in 1 mL of water (Invitrogen, P36400). Probenecid is commonly used to inhibit cellular transport and therefore reduces the baseline signal within the assay. 1 mL of the dye solution was taken to create a 1:8 dilution and 90 μ L of probenecid added to the dye made up as stated in the protocol. 1 mL of the dye solution (before probenecid was added) was added to 7 mL of assay buffer and 80 μ L of probenecid added. The media was aspirated from the plate and 90 μ L of the dye solution was added to each well and the plate then incubated for 45 min at 37 °C. The plate was then read on the Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader using SkanIT 6.0 software (Thermo). The full protocol can be seen below in Figure 2.13.

D

Figure 2.13 Varioskan LUX plate reader protocol for intracellular calcium influx assay. Following the seeding of cells into a 96-well clear bottom black plate and pre-incubation with the calcium dye, the assay is then placed into the Varioskan LUX and the SkanIT 6.0 software used. The first step in the protocol involves the plate layout set up and selection of the correct plate used and labelling of each well based on stimulation and cell type. Next the protocol is determined, with the measurement order of reading each well and pre-run checks such as temperature set (A). The well loop set is then added (B), followed by the kinetic loop step which involves the total reading time of 2 min 30 sec for each well and a 1 sec kinetic interval set, with continuous shaking of the plate throughout (C). The dispense step is next on the protocol with a total of 10 μL of stimulation being added at reading 10 of each well (D). Finally, the fluorescence step involves the assay being read at excitation and emission wavelength of 488/509 nm (E). Panel (F) shows an example trace produced during the reading of a well.

Each drug was added at reading number 10 as and when those wells were being read for a total reading duration of 2 min and 30 s. The drugs were made 10-fold more concentrated than the desired well concentration, as can be seen in Table 2.11. The results were analysed using Prism 7 (GraphPad, San Diego).

Drug	Stock Concentration	Well Concentration	Company	Catalogue Number
FLIGRLO-NH ₂	1 mM	100 µM	Dundalk Institute of Technology	-
FLIGRLO-NH ₂	100 µM	10 µM	Dundalk Institute of Technology	-
FLIGRLO-NH ₂	10 µM	1 µM	Dundalk Institute of Technology	-
FLIGRLO-NH ₂	1 µM	100 nM	Dundalk Institute of Technology	-
FLIGRLO-NH ₂	100 nM	10 nM	Dundalk Institute of Technology	-
FOLIGRL-NH ₂	100 µM	10 µM	Dundalk Institute of Technology	-
Trypsin	100 U	10 U	Sigma, UK	T0303-1G
Matriptase	100 nM	10 nM	Biotechnie, United States	3946-SEB-010
Matriptase	10 nM	1 nM	Biotechnie, United States	3946-SEB-010
Matriptase	1 nM	0.1 nM	Biotechnie, United States	3946-SEB-010
Acetylcholine	10 µM	1 µM	Sigma, UK	A2661
Blank	Assay Buffer	Assay Buffer	Invitrogen, UK	F36206

Table 2.11 Drugs and concentrations. Drugs and associated working (well) concentrations are detailed with the company and catalogue number.

Chapter 3:
Characterisation of PAR2
roles in hBSMC and isolated
murine airways

3 Characterisation of PAR2 roles in hBSMC and isolated murine airways

3.1 Introduction

In order to assess potential effects of PAR2 activity in COPD it is important to understand the role of the receptor at a cellular level, as well as in isolated airways. The contractile capabilities of ASM are a key aspect to be considered in terms of respiratory pathology in the airways of COPD patients (Yan *et al.*, 2018). However, these cells also secrete extracellular matrix, cytokines and chemokines and can exhibit excessive proliferation (Pan, Conaway and Deshpande, 2019), all processes of relevance to disease and which PAR2 has been reported to modulated in pulmonary or other contexts. PAR2 has been identified in human airways, situated both in the bronchial epithelium and also the bronchial smooth muscle (Kagota *et al.*, 2016). Studies in various animal models have found contradictory findings in regard to the functional role of PAR2 in the airways, reporting both bronchodilation and bronchoconstriction (Cocks *et al.*, 1999; Lan *et al.*, 2000; Ricciardolo *et al.*, 2000; Chambers *et al.*, 2001).

Initial work described in this chapter was performed to confirm previously reported PAR2 expression in hBSM cells using immunofluorescence. As inflammation is a key feature of COPD disease pathology and recognised to be mediated by PAR2 in various other diseases (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003; Rayees *et al.*, 2020), the examination of levels of inflammatory mediators IL-6, IL-8, and TNF- α following PAR2 stimulation was assessed. These cytokines are typically associated with COPD having been found to be upregulated in BAL fluid of COPD patients and are candidates as biomarkers of disease severity (El-Shimy *et al.*, 2014). Pathogenesis of COPD can be driven by the process of inflammatory cells releasing proteases and various mediators such as cytokines and chemokines, which contribute to chronic inflammation and tissue remodelling (Heuberger *et al.*, 2015). Finally, calcium signalling is a key process in regulating smooth muscle tone and other pathogenic mechanisms including airway remodelling and proliferation (Hill-Eubanks *et al.*, 2011; Sun *et al.*, 2016). Thus, a potential role of PAR2 in the mechanism of calcium signalling in these cells was investigated. In parallel, the functional capacity of the receptor in the airways was also assessed utilising the technique of wire myography to measure isometric tension in response to PAR2 activation.

The experiments described within this section of the study were designed to yield an improved understanding of the role of the receptor in bronchial smooth muscle, providing a basis to inform future investigations of PAR2 as a potential therapeutic target for chronic respiratory conditions such as COPD.

3.2 Hypothesis

PAR2 has reported roles in key processes such as bronchodilation and airway inflammation. Aspects of these roles are likely to be mediated by PAR2 expressed on ASM cells.

3.3 Aims

The primary aims for this study were as follows:

- 1) Confirm PAR2 expression in human BSMC (hBSMC)
- 2) Determine if PAR2 plays a role in the secretion of proinflammatory cytokines in hBSMC
- 3) Investigate if PAR2 stimulation elicits calcium flux in hBSMC
- 4) Examine the role of PAR2 in regulating contractility in isolated murine airways

3.4 Methods

The methods used are documented fully in Sections 2.6 and 2.8. Expression of PAR2 in hBSMC was carried out using the technique of immunofluorescence (Section 2.8.5) to investigate the expression of the receptor in this cell type. All experiments utilised cells between passage 2 and 6. An MTT cell viability assay, (see 2.8.3) was carried out to investigate potential cytotoxicity of any reagents used. ELISA (2.8.4) was carried out to examine secreted levels of relevant pro-inflammatory cytokines. Calcium signalling in hBSMC was studied using a Fluo-4 NW calcium assay kit (2.8.6) using a range

of PAR2 activators. Finally, functional response to PAR2 activation (in terms of regulation of tone) was investigated using wire myography in mixed sex C57BL/6J mice (Section 2.6.1).

The data presented in this section of the study are generated from a total of 6 healthy donors both male and female of varying age, weight, and ethnic origin. All donor details in full, can be found in Section 2.8.1. COPD-diseased cells were not within this study due to poor survival/growth rate of cultures.

Morphology and growth of hBSMC

The culturing of hBSMC was monitored over a period of 7 days to confirm expected behaviour of the cultures, including morphology and growth rate (Figure 3.1) (Gounni *et al.*, 2005). Cultures at 90 % confluency, typically day 7 of culture, were passaged and re-seeded for use in experimentation. The images were captured using an inverted phase contrast microscope (Motic, AE31) and Motic camera attachment. The representative images were captured at a magnification of 100 X.

Figure 3.1 Culture and growth of hBSMC. Cells (hBSMC) were seeded at 250,000 cells/mL and cultured in a 25 cm³ flask (Corning, UK), in Promocell (C-22062) ready to use smooth muscle growth medium with 1 % (v/v) pen/strep. The images were subsequently captured at days 1, 3, 5 & 7 using an inverted phase contrast microscope (Motic, AE31) and Motic camera attachment. The representative images were captured at a magnification of 100 X.

3.5 Results

3.5.1 PAR2 expression in hBSMC

The expression of PAR2 was investigated by immunofluorescence to confirm that the receptor of interest was present in hBSMC. Briefly, the cells were subject to immunofluorescence and basic imaging to confirm expression and assess location of PAR2 in the cell (Figure 3.2). PAR2 can be seen throughout the cytoplasm of the cells and at a higher magnification, the staining appears localised in a largely perinuclear, punctate fashion throughout each cell, consistent with sequestration of receptor predominantly within intracellular vesicles (Cunningham *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 3.2 Expression of PAR2 in hBSMC. Primary cells were cultured in Promocell media and seeded onto coverslips 24 h before immunofluorescence processing. PAR2 was stained using Alomone (APR-32) PAR2 antibody and fluorescently labelled secondary antibody Alexa Fluor-488, and DAPI nuclear counterstain. Representative images (n=3 donors) were captured using an Olympus IX71 microscope using the DAPI (blue) filter (excitation and emission wavelength of 358/461 nm) and the GFP filter (excitation and emission wavelength of 488/509 nm) at magnifications of 10, 20 and 100 X and analysed subsequently using ImageJ software to merge images.

3.5.2 Assessment of hBSMC viability

Metabolic activity (measured by MTT reduction to formazan) was assessed in this assay as a surrogate for cell viability, to determine potential cytotoxicity of reagents to be used in downstream assays. These included PAR2 activating peptide, FLIGRLO-NH₂ and PAR2-activating proteases matriptase and trypsin, as well as acetylcholine (Figure 3.3). Various PAR2 activators were used in this study to allow an in-depth assessment of the selectivity of the reagents, as trypsin has been previously reported to have off-target effects (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019). The data presented in Figure 3.3 show that FLIGRLO-NH₂, matriptase, trypsin and acetylcholine did not appear to have significant cytotoxic effects on hBSMC at timepoints up to 72 h (at concentrations used in downstream assays). MTT assays can also be used to assess proliferation rate, and PAR2 activation has indeed been linked to enhanced proliferation in other cell types (Berger *et al.*, 2001). The data suggest no effect on proliferation of any of the reagents tested, though any such response may have been masked by density of cell seeding or short experimental duration.

Figure 3.3 Assessment of cell viability of hBSMC in response to experimental reagents. Primary hBSMC were cultured in Promocell media and seeded 24 h before stimulation with FLIGRLO-NH₂, matriptase, trypsin (10 U/mL⁻¹) and acetylcholine (1 μM). Following each stimulation timepoint, the supernatant media was removed from the cells and MTT added for a 3-hour incubation period before reading on a plate reader (Biotek, ELX 800) at absorbance of 595 nm using GEN5 1.08 software. Representative graphs are shown of the quantification of the % cell viability following stimulation with each drug and relevant controls at time points of 4 (A), 24 (B) 48 (C) and 72 h (D). Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post hoc test and data presented as the mean ± SEM (n=3) measured in triplicate.

3.5.3 Effect of PAR2 activation on cytokine secretion from hBSMC

Interleukin-6

A number of studies have well documented that IL-6, a pleiotropic proinflammatory cytokine, plays an important role in the pathogenesis of COPD (Bartoli *et al.*, 2009; Saha *et al.*, 2009). Higher levels of IL-6 in both the serum and sputum of COPD patients are linked with an impairment and decline of lung function (Donaldson *et al.*, 2005; Yende *et al.*, 2006; He *et al.*, 2009). PAR2 activation has been reported to upregulate IL-6 in human dermal microvascular endothelial cells in a time and concentration-dependent manner (Shpacovitch *et al.*, 2002). Similar studies in human kidney epithelial cells (Vesey *et al.*, 2013) and monocytes (Johansson *et al.*, 2005) have shown that PAR2 activation results in an increase in IL-6 secretion. Secretion of IL-6 by hBSMC was investigated following stimulation with known PAR2 activators. The PAR2 activators used were FLIGRLO-NH₂ and matriptase (Figure 3.4 A). The media for analysis of the cytokine were collected from cells in a 96-well plate format seeded 24 h before experimentation. Subsequently 24 h after seeding, the cells were stimulated with various concentrations of FLIGRLO-NH₂ and matriptase at various timepoints of 4, 24, 48 and 72 h.

The maximum stimulation of IL-6 secretion was observed with 100 μM FLIGRLO-NH₂ at 72 h, from 124 pg/mL unstimulated to 654 pg/mL. However, no statistical significance was observed. An accumulation of IL-6 secretion was observed in the unstimulated from 48 pg/mL at 4 h to 124 pg/mL at 72 h in the FLIGRLO-NH₂ experiments. Similar accumulations of IL-6 were observed in the unstimulated samples up to 72 h in the matriptase experiments. The maximum stimulation of IL-6 secretion by matriptase was observed at 48 h, from 99 pg/mL unstimulated to 162 pg/mL (0.1 nM), though this did not reach statistical significance. However, statistically significant IL-6 secretion in response to matriptase at the early 4 h timepoint was observed at 1 nM (119.2 ± 14.9) compared to unstimulated (43.2 ± 16.9), and also at 100 nM (130.1 ± 12.2). An interesting observation was found at 72 h matriptase stimulation, with a decrease in IL-6 secretion observed at all concentrations, perhaps indicating inhibition, although this effect did not reach significance. When comparing the two PAR2 agonists, FLIGRLO-NH₂ appeared to be more effective than matriptase at stimulating IL-6 secretion from hBSMC, though any responses observed were modest in magnitude, perhaps exacerbated by heterogeneity in patient donor response.

Figure 3.4 Effect of PAR2 activation on IL-6 secretion in hBSMC. Primary hBSMC were cultured in Promocell media and seeded 24 h before stimulation with FLIGRLO-NH₂ & matriptase at concentrations indicated. Following each stimulation timepoint, the supernatant media was removed from the cells and IL-6 ELISA performed before reading on a plate reader (Biotek, ELX 800) at absorbance of 595 nm using GEN5 1.08 Software. Graphs are shown of the quantification of IL-6 release following stimulation with PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ (A) and matriptase (B) and relevant unstimulated controls at various time points of 4, 24, 48 and 72 h. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post hoc test and are presented as the mean \pm SEM (n=3) **P* < 0.05 *cf.* unstimulated, measured in triplicate.

Interleukin-8

IL-8 is an important pro-inflammatory cytokine and chemokine which is implicated in the inflammation of the airways due to its role as a neutrophil chemoattractant (Matheson *et al.*, 2006) in the pathogenesis of COPD (Chung, 2001). The induction of cytokine release in COPD is often thought to be due to the effect of inhaled toxins, specifically cigarette smoke (Mio *et al.*, 1997). This is supported by an early study which revealed an increase in IL-8 secretion in the BAL of smokers compared with non-smokers (Kuschner *et al.*, 1996). This was further supported by a study of bronchial epithelial cells which showed an increase in IL-8 secretion post exposure to cigarette smoke extract (Mio *et al.*, 1997). In a study of gastrointestinal epithelial cells, stimulation with PAR2 agonists elicited an increase in IL-8 secretion (Tanaka *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, work in human lung A549 cells found that activation of PAR2 resulted in an increase in IL-8 secretion (Moriyuki *et al.*, 2008).

Recent work in our laboratory has indicated that antagonism of PAR2 in COPD airway epithelial cells resulted in a reduction in IL-8 secretion, further suggesting a role for PAR2 in mediating production of this pro-inflammatory cytokine in airways (Bailo *et al.*, 2020). Here, secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-8 was investigated in hBSMC following stimulation with known PAR2 activators, FLIGRLO-NH₂ (Figure 3.5, A) and matriptase (Figure 3.5, B). The maximum stimulated level of IL-8 secretion was observed at 48 h, from 1198 pg/mL unstimulated to 1538 pg/mL (10 μM FLIGRLO-NH₂). An accumulation of IL-8 secretion was observed in unstimulated samples from 480 pg/mL at 4 h to 1198 pg/mL at 48 h in the FLIGRLO-NH₂ experiments. No significant changes in cytokine secretion were observed following stimulation with FLIGRLO-NH₂ at any of the timepoints. Similar unstimulated accumulation of IL-8 was observed in the matriptase experiments, from 81 pg/mL at 4 h to 273 pg/mL at 72 h. The maximum stimulation of IL-8 secretion by matriptase was observed at 72 h, from 273 pg/mL unstimulated to 662 pg/mL (100 nM), though not attaining significance. As for IL-6, it appeared that FLIGRLO-NH₂ was a more effective stimulator of IL-8 secretion than matriptase in hBSMC, notwithstanding the modest effects and donor cell response heterogeneity observed.

Figure 3.5 Effect of PAR2 activation on IL-8 secretion in hBSMC. Primary hBSMC were cultured in Promocell media and seeded 24 h before stimulation with FLIGRLO-NH₂ & matriptase at concentrations indicated. Following each stimulation timepoint, the supernatant media was removed from the cells and IL-8 ELISA performed before reading on a plate reader (Biotek, ELX 800) at absorbance of 595 nm using GEN5 1.08 Software. Graphs are shown of the quantification of IL-8 release following stimulation with PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ (A) and matriptase (B) and relevant unstimulated controls at various time points of 4, 24, 48 and 72 h. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post hoc test and are presented as the mean \pm SEM (n=3) measured in triplicate.

Tumour necrosis factor- α

The pathophysiologic role of pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α is suggested by the high levels of the cytokine in BAL and sputum of patients with asthma and COPD (Thomas, 2001; Erzurum, 2006; Jude *et al.*, 2008) and it has been reported to participate in the development of disease (Yao *et al.*, 2019). A study investigating biomarkers of COPD has indicated that raised levels of TNF- α can be used as a biomarker of the systemic inflammatory response involved in stable COPD patients (Karadag *et al.*, 2008). The ASM is of particular interest in relation to TNF- α , investigated in a study which unravelled a signalling network that causes ASM proliferation in response to TNF- α and subsequently leads to remodelling processes such as ASM hyperplasia (Knobloch *et al.*, 2016). Thus, a possible role for TNF- α in causing airway remodelling in an inflammatory setting was investigated in the context of PAR2, since PAR2 activity has been reported to induce TNF- α secretion elsewhere (McCarthy, Reeves and McElvaney, 2016).

The maximum stimulation of TNF- α secretion was observed at 4 h, from 16 pg/mL unstimulated to 47 pg/mL at 100 μ M FLIGRLO-NH₂. However, a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in TNF- α secretion was observed at 24 h following the same stimulation (2.3 ± 1.5 pg/mL) compared with unstimulated (15.4 ± 3.3 pg/mL). When matriptase was used to stimulate PAR2 activity, the maximum stimulation was observed at 24 h, from 78 pg/mL basal to 179 pg/mL (100 nM matriptase). However, no significant change in cytokine secretion was observed following stimulation with matriptase at any of the timepoints or concentrations.

Figure 3.6 Effect of PAR2 activation on TNF α secretion in hBSMC. Primary hBSMC were cultured in Promocell media and seeded 24 h before stimulation with FLIGRLO-NH₂ & matriptase at concentrations indicated. Following each stimulation timepoint, the supernatant media was removed from the cells and TNF- α ELISA performed before reading on a plate reader (Biotek, ELX 800) at absorbance of 595 nm using GEN5 1.08 Software. Graphs are shown of the quantification of TNF- α release following stimulation with PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ (A) and matriptase (B) and relevant unstimulated controls at various time points of 4, 24, 48 and 72 h. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post hoc test and are presented as the mean \pm SEM (n=3) **P* < 0.05 *cf.* measured in triplicate.

To summarise, the PAR2-stimulated cytokine profile in hBSMC suggests tentatively that FLIGRLO-NH₂ is a more effective, if modest, stimulator of IL-6 and IL-8 secretion compared with matriptase. However, no consistent and persistent significant effect was observed for any cytokine studied. It was also observed that IL-8 was secreted at higher levels compared to the other cytokines in hBSMC. With little significant change being observed in secretion compared to the unstimulated control, there was little evidence to support a significant role for PAR2 in pro-inflammatory cytokine secretion from hBSMC.

3.5.4 Effect of PAR2 activation on calcium flux in hBSMC

Intracellular calcium flux induced by PAR2 activators in hBSMC was investigated. PAR2 has previously been reported to stimulate Ca²⁺ signalling in human airway smooth muscle cells (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019). The PAR2 activators used were FLIGRLO-NH₂ (Figure 3.7, A), matriptase, (Figure 3.7, B) and trypsin (Figure 3.7, C). Additionally acetylcholine (Figure 3.7, D) was used, as it is expected to stimulate Ca²⁺ flux (Kuo and Ehrlich, 2015), and it is commonly used as a pre-contraction agent in isometric tension assays (Pinart *et al.*, 2013). One concentration of trypsin and acetylcholine were used as standard conditions, based on numerous previous studies.

A concentration-dependent increase in intracellular Ca²⁺ in response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ was observed compared to control. A significant increase ($P < 0.01$) in relative fluorescent units (RFU) was detected at 10 μ M FLIGRLO-NH₂ (2.9 ± 0.4) compared with the blank control (0.6 ± 0.1) (Figure 3.7). Similarly, a highly significant increase ($P < 0.001$) in RFU was observed at 100 μ M FLIGRLO-NH₂ (4.1 ± 0.6) compared with the blank (0.6 ± 0.1). The scrambled peptide elicited a modest increase in fluorescence similar to the blank. The response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ occurred in the first 30 seconds post stimulation and began to decrease at 40 seconds before plateauing at approximately 50 % of the maximum response for the remainder of the protocol.

When stimulated with matriptase, no significant changes in intracellular Ca²⁺ were observed compared with the control, although the maximum concentration used appeared to elicit a response not attaining significance. Following trypsin stimulation, a similar non-significant response can be seen in comparison with the blank control, similar to the results observed with lower concentrations of the PAR2 activating peptide, FLIGRLO-NH₂. Finally, when stimulated with a known smooth muscle contractile agent, Ach, a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in Ca²⁺ was observed compared with the control. The response to acetylcholine appeared distinct to that arising from PAR2 stimulation, occurring rapidly in a period of 10 seconds post stimulation, and being sustained for the length of the procedure. To summarise, the data presented in Figure 3.7 shows that in hBSMC PAR2 activation, at least using PAR2-activating peptide, caused a dose-dependent calcium flux. Because Ca²⁺ flux was induced by a PAR2 agonist, although in a manner distinct from that induced by Ach, and since this process is important to regulation of ASM tone (Mahn *et al.*, 2010; Bhallamudi *et al.*, 2020; Zhang *et al.*, 2019), albeit among a multitude of processes (Clapham, 2007), it was decided to investigate the impact of PAR2 regulation on airway contractility in isolated murine tissues.

Figure 3.7 Effect of PAR2 activation or acetylcholine on calcium flux in hBSMC. Cells were cultured and seeded 24 h prior to experimentation. Quantification of intracellular calcium flux was made following stimulation with various concentrations of PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ (A), matriptase (B), trypsin 10 U/mL⁻¹ (C) and acetylcholine 1 μM (D), with relevant controls throughout and representative trace images shown (panels on R). The plate was read at an excitation and emission wavelength set to 579/610 nm and SkanIT 6.0 software used. Statistical analysis was carried out using two-way ANOVA (A & B) and Student's paired t test with Welch's correction (C & D) and are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=6) **P* < 0.05 *cf.* Blank, ***P* < 0.01 *cf.* Blank, ****P* < 0.001 *cf.* Blank.

3.5.5 Effect of PAR2 activation on isolated murine airway tone

An early study reported that in human airways, PAR2 activation in airway smooth muscle resulted in Ca^{2+} mobilisation and subsequently a contraction (Schmidlin *et al.*, 2001). Contradictory findings indicating a bronchodilatory role for PAR2 in ASM were described in both rat and murine airways (Cocks *et al.*, 1999; Chambers *et al.*, 2001). These discrepancies suggest a need for future investigation to clarify the role of PAR2 in the airways and so here, investigation into the effect of PAR2 in isolated murine airways was carried out using a range of PAR2 activators. The dilatory response was investigated in depth using pre-contracted airway tissue.

Experiments were performed using bronchial (Figure 3.8) and tracheal (Figure 3.9) rings from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} animals using a PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ and scrambled peptide FOLIGRL-NH₂ as a negative control. A proteolytic PAR2 activator, trypsin, was also used in both bronchial and tracheal rings from both genotypes. Using the PAR2-specific agonist peptide, in addition to trypsin, was intended to confirm that any relaxation observed was definitely mediated by PAR2 rather than a non-specific effect. Using the PAR2^{-/-} model would allow further definitive confirmation that observed effects using both trypsin and FLIGRLO-NH₂ were mediated through PAR2. The response of airway rings to PAR2 activation was examined using *ex vivo* methods of measuring isometric tension, with PAR2 agonists added following pre-contraction with acetylcholine.

The results showed that at all peptide concentrations, FLIGRLO-NH₂ administration appeared to result in a bronchodilatory effect, with this becoming significant compared to the scrambled peptide at 1 μM ($42.4 \pm 11.0 \%$), increasing up to 10 μM ($77.0 \pm 8.4 \%$). This relaxation was reduced significantly in response to FOLIGRL-NH₂ when compared with the FLIGRLO-NH₂ response.

There was no significant FLIGRLO-NH₂ dependent response observed at any concentration in the PAR2^{-/-} tissue (Figure 3.8, B), consistent with the FLIGRLO-NH₂ response being fully dependent on PAR2.

When targeting PAR2 using trypsin in bronchial rings, there was again no significant PAR2-dependent relaxation in the PAR2^{-/-} ($1.1 \pm 0.5 \%$), compared with the PAR2^{+/+} tissue ($65.4 \pm 7.6 \%$) (Figure 3.8, D). These data therefore confirm that the trypsin-dependent bronchodilatory effect was dependent on the presence of PAR2. In summary, the data presented in Figure 3.8 shows that PAR2 has a potent bronchodilatory role in regulating the contractility of isolated murine bronchial rings.

Figure 3.8 PAR2-dependent bronchodilatory response in murine PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} bronchial rings. Bronchial rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Investigation of the PAR2-dependent response was examined using a known PAR2 specific peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ and scrambled sequence FOLIGRL-NH₂ as a control at indicated concentrations, alongside PAR2 activator trypsin. FLIGRLO-NH₂ and FOLIGRL-NH₂ was used at various concentrations in PAR2^{+/+} bronchial rings (n=10) (A) and PAR2^{-/-} bronchial rings (n=11) (B). Comparison of both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} bronchial rings in response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ (C) with representative trace images (D). PAR2 agonist trypsin (10 U/mL⁻¹) was used in both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} bronchial rings (E) and representative trace images (F). The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of the PAR2 agonist during the acetylcholine (1 μM) contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100% respectively. Bars beneath traces represent reagent addition times. Statistical analysis was carried out using two-way ANOVA with selected Bonferroni post-hoc test (A, B & C) and Student's unpaired t test with Welch's correction (E) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM ***P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001.

The results observed in the tracheal rings revealed a response similar to that of the bronchial tissue showing that at all peptide concentrations, FLIGRLO-NH₂ administration (Figure 3.9 A, C) resulted in a dilatory effect, with this becoming significant compared to the scrambled peptide at 1 μM (39.6 ± 6.8 %) and increasing up to 10 μM (62.2 ± 6.3 %). There was no response to FOLIGRL-NH₂ at any concentration used. There was no significant response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ (nor scrambled peptide) addition at any concentration in the PAR2^{-/-} tissue (Figure 3.9, Panel B). The data presented are consistent with the FLIGRLO-NH₂ response being fully dependent on PAR2.

When targeting PAR2 with trypsin in tracheal rings, there was a highly significant relaxation response observed in the PAR2^{+/+} tissue (60.0 ± 4.5 %), which was essentially abolished in the PAR2^{-/-} comparator tissue (1.4 ± 0.8 %) (Figure 3.9, D). In summary, the data presented in Figure 3.9 shows that PAR2 has a significant dilatory role in isolated murine tracheal rings similar to that observed in primary bronchi.

Figure 3.9 PAR2-dependent response in murine PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} tracheal rings. Tracheal rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Investigation of the PAR2-dependent relaxant response was examined using a known PAR2 specific peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ and scrambled sequence of the peptide FOLIGRL-NH₂ as a control at indicated concentrations, alongside a known PAR2 agonist trypsin. FLIGRLO-NH₂ and FOLIGRL-NH₂ was used at various concentrations in PAR2^{+/+} tracheal rings (n=11) (A) and PAR2^{-/-} tracheal rings (n=7) (B). Comparison of both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} tracheal rings in response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ (C) with representative trace images (D). PAR2 agonist trypsin (10 U/mL⁻¹) was used in both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} tracheal rings (E) and representative trace images shown (F). The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of the PAR2 agonist during the acetylcholine (1 μM) contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100% respectively. Bars beneath traces represent reagent addition times. Statistical analysis was carried out using two-way ANOVA with selected Bonferroni post-hoc test (A, B & C) and Student's unpaired t test with Welch's correction (E) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM p<0.05.

3.5.6 PAR2 functional response in male and female isolated murine airways

To determine if sex had an impact on the bronchodilatory role of PAR2, a study was carried out investigating the differences in response between sexes in isolated murine airways. There have been reports of sex differences in COPD prevalence such as a lower FEV₁ in women and more severe disease in subjects with COPD (Carey *et al.*, 2007; Sørheim *et al.*, 2010; Barnes, 2016; Ntritsos *et al.*, 2018) Thus it was of interest with regard to potential for future tailored therapies to see if PAR2 had a similar bronchodilatory role in both males and females. This was carried out in male and female PAR2^{+/+} bronchial (Figure 3.10) and tracheal rings (Figure 3.11) using the specific PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ and a scrambled sequence FOLIGRL-NH₂ as a negative control. Trypsin was also used in both bronchial and tracheal rings from animals of both sexes. The role of PAR2 activation was examined using *ex vivo* methods of measuring isometric tension and PAR2 agonists were added following pre-contraction with acetylcholine.

The results showed a clear dose-dependent response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ in PAR2^{+/+} bronchial rings (Figure 3.10, A) that was comparable in tissue from both males and females, and which was absent in the case of the negative control FOLIGRL-NH₂ (Figure 3.10, B). There was no significant difference detected at any peptide concentration between tissue from age-matched males (59.1 ± 9.3 %) and females (60.7 ± 1.3 %) (Figure 3.10, A). When targeting PAR2 with trypsin in bronchial rings, again there was no significant change in PAR2-dependent relaxation in the male (50.7 ± 9.3 %) compared with the female tissue (57.7 ± 11.2 %) (Figure 3.10, E).

The slope of the relaxation curve for each sex was similar in the bronchial analysis using FLIGRLO-NH₂. However, when stimulated with trypsin, the relaxation curve appeared steeper in the male tissue compared with the female rings, which appeared as a more gradual relaxation indicating a faster rate of relaxation in males stimulated with trypsin. In summary, the data presented in Figure 3.10 shows that PAR2 was able to exert a comparable degree of bronchodilatory response in bronchial rings of both male and female samples, although the rate of rate of relaxation appeared to differ dependent on the PAR2 activator used.

Figure 3.10 Comparison of PAR2-dependent response in male and female murine PAR2^{+/+} isolated murine bronchi. Bronchial rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} murine male and female samples (n=7) and mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Investigation of the PAR2-dependent bronchodilatory response was examined using a PAR2-specific agonist peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ (A) and scrambled sequence of the peptide FOLIGRL-NH₂ (C) as a control at indicated concentrations with representative images shown (B & D), alongside trypsin (10 U/mL⁻¹) (E) with representative images (F). The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of the PAR2 agonist and during the acetylcholine (1 μM) contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100% respectively. Bars beneath traces indicate reagent addition times. Statistical analysis was carried out using two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post-hoc test, and unpaired Student's t test for the trypsin analysis. Data are presented as the mean ± SEM.

The results observed in the tracheal tissue experiments again showed a clear dose-dependent response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ in PAR2^{+/+} tracheal rings that was nullified in the case of the negative control FOLIGRL-NH₂ (Figure 3.11 A, B). There was no significant difference identified between the response of tracheal rings from either sex at any concentration of FLIGRLO-NH₂, with maximal relaxation observed at 10 μM male (60.2 ± 10.4 %) and female (63.9 ± 8.5 %) tissue (Figure 3.11 A). Again, no response was observed in either male or female rings to the scrambled peptide sequence (Figure 3.11 B).

When targeting PAR2 with trypsin in tracheal rings, there was again no significant change in PAR2-dependent relaxation in the male (57.0 ± 7.7 %) compared with the female tissue (62.4 ± 5.8 %) (Figure 3.11 E). There is no change identified in relaxation with FLIGRLO-NH₂, however unlike the differences observed in the male and female bronchial relaxation rate observed with trypsin, there is no such change observed in the tracheal rings. In summary, the data presented in Figure 3.11 shows that the PAR2-dependent relaxation in tracheal rings shows no significant difference between male and female samples.

Figure 3.11 Comparison of PAR2-dependent response in male and female murine PAR2^{+/+} isolated murine trachea. Tracheal rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} murine male and female samples (n=6) and mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Investigation of the PAR2-dependent bronchodilatory response was examined using a PAR2-specific agonist peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ (A) and representative trace image (B) scrambled sequence of the peptide FOLIGRL-NH₂ (C) as a control at indicated concentrations with representative images (D), alongside a known PAR2 agonist trypsin (10 U/mL⁻¹) (E) with representative images (F). The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of the PAR2 agonist and during the acetylcholine (1 μM) contraction were assigned values of 0 % and 100 % respectively. Bars beneath traces indicate reagent addition times. Statistical analysis was carried out using two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post-hoc test and unpaired Student's t test for the trypsin analysis. Data are presented as the mean ± SEM.

3.6 Discussion

This study explored putative roles for PAR2 in hBSMC and the impact of PAR2 activation on smooth muscle tone in isolated murine airways.

PAR2 was found to be present intracellularly in hBSMC, presenting predominantly in a punctate fashion. Although not assessed here, it would be interesting to investigate subcellular redistribution of the receptor upon stimulation, as previously reported by studies using kidney cells investigating trafficking of PAR2 using trypsin to activate the receptor (Déry *et al.*, 1999; Ayoub & Pin, 2013). Utilisation of confocal microscopy would facilitate such studies, aiding visualisation of the receptor within the plasma membrane by resolving a narrower depth of focus (Smyth and Shaw, 2008; Castillo-Badillo, Cabrera-Wrooman and García-Sáinz, 2014).

A previous study by Schmidlin, investigating the expression and function of PAR2 in human airway smooth muscle cells and isolated human bronchi also showed the presence of PAR2 using immunofluorescence microscopy (Schmidlin *et al.*, 2001). PAR2 expression was also found in hBSMC through immunohistochemical staining of bronchial rings (Miotto *et al.*, 2002). The expression of PAR2 observed in the hBSMC, supported by findings in the literature, confirm that PAR2 is present in the ASM and supported further investigation on the role of the receptor in this tissue. A new antibody from Alomone (APR-32) was utilised in this study, as standard tools such as SAM-11 (Santa Cruz) have sometimes been unreliable in previous IHC studies within our lab.

PAR2 is widely reported to play a role in modulating inflammation and has been reported to be a key player in chronic diseases which effect the joints such as rheumatoid arthritis (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003) and osteoarthritis (Huesa *et al.*, 2016). There have also been reports of PAR2 being involved in inflammatory conditions in the lungs such as asthma (Kim *et al.*, 2019) and thus investigation into the role of the receptor in the context of COPD would appear merited and timely. Multiple cytokines orchestrate an inflammatory response in airway diseases such as COPD through the recruitment of inflammatory cells (Barnes, 2009). To investigate a putative role for PAR2 in the context of hBSMC inflammation in COPD, proinflammatory cytokine secretion was studied, due to the widely reported involvement of cytokines in orchestrating an inflammatory response in the airway (Pearson *et al.*, 2015; Barnes, 2018).

The overall level of IL-6 secretion in PAR2-stimulated cells appeared marginally higher than control, with FLIGRLO-NH₂ generally eliciting a greater response than the protease matriptase, although few significant changes were demonstrated. Evidence indicates that IL-6 levels are increased in bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) in COPD patients, this increase being commonly associated with a decrease in lung function (Soler *et al.*, 1999). These findings suggested a role for IL-6 in the chronic inflammatory state that causes disease progression in COPD (Bhowmik *et al.*, 2000). The findings presented in this study indicate that PAR2, at least expressed in BSM, may not be a direct modulator of IL-6 secretion, which may be modulated more effectively via the epithelial layer of the airways. These findings are supported by multiple studies showing increased levels of IL-6 production and secretion from damaged airway epithelia (e.g. Chow *et al.*, 2010). Indeed, recent data from our laboratory indicate that human primary airway epithelial cells respond robustly to PAR2 activation to increase IL-6 secretion (Bailo *et al.*, 2020).

Another cytokine increased in COPD and long recognised as a key factor in the disease is IL-8; this increase being triggered by cigarette smoke inhalation and other irritants (Zhang *et al.*, 2011). Previous studies have shown that cigarette smoke enhances the release of IL-8 from both dendritic cells (Mortaz *et al.*, 2009) and airway smooth muscle cells (Gosens *et al.*, 2009), suggesting that cigarette smoke exposure may be sufficient to explain the release of amplified levels of IL-8 in COPD airways. Thus, PAR2-stimulated IL-8 secretion from hBSMC was investigated here. However, no significant stimulation of IL-8 production above basal accumulation was observed.

Recent work in our laboratory using human primary epithelial cells from both healthy donors and COPD patients has revealed that PAR2 antagonism can reduce the levels of both IL-8 and IL-6 secretion (Bailo

et al., 2020). Although the findings presented here suggest that IL-8 secretion may not be modulated by PAR2 in airway smooth muscle specifically, it remains plausible that PAR2 could play an important role in a disease setting. Other sources of cytokine secretion include inflammatory cells that are involved in the remodelling of the airways and parenchymal destruction characteristic of emphysema. In COPD, these cells predominantly include neutrophils, macrophages, and T lymphocytes (CD8+ and CD4+) (Cosio & Majo, 2002), these cells being found in the airways, tissues and circulation of patients with COPD, during both stable disease and exacerbations (Bafadhel, Pavord and Russell, 2017).

The final cytokine examined was TNF- α , and data again indicated little effect of PAR2 stimulation in hBSMC, despite a regulatory role being reported in other cell types (Kang *et al.*, 2005; Steven *et al.*, 2013). Overall, it appears that if hBSMC are a significant source of pro-inflammatory mediators that may be important in disease, then little evidence was found in this study to indicate that these effects are mediated by PAR2 activation in these cells, at least not in cells from healthy donors.

Changes in intracellular Ca²⁺ are key to the function of smooth muscle and these changes can be sustained, cell-wide increases or localised changes. Smooth muscle contractility is regulated by changes in intracellular Ca²⁺ concentrations, which typically is in the form of a cell-wide increase associated with actin-myosin cross-bridge formation (Hill-Eubanks *et al.*, 2011). This is of interest in the context of COPD due to the hypercontractility reported in patients with COPD (Yan *et al.*, 2018a), although it must be noted that Ca²⁺ signalling is associated with a host of intracellular functions (Jude *et al.*, 2008). In order to gain insight into mechanisms potentially underlying such hypercontractility, the role of PAR2 was investigated in terms of its potential function in mobilising calcium in bronchial smooth muscle cells. Earlier studies in various animal models have found contradictory findings in regard to the functional role of PAR2 in the airways, reporting either bronchodilation or bronchoconstriction (Cocks *et al.*, 1999; Lan *et al.*, 2000; Ricciardolo *et al.*, 2000; Chambers *et al.*, 2001).

Within this study, a dose-dependent Ca²⁺ increase in response to PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ was observed indicating that when PAR2 is activated directly in the smooth muscle at the tethered ligand binding site, an influx of calcium occurred. However, when the cells were stimulated with protease PAR2 activators, matriptase and trypsin, only a slight (if any) increase in intracellular Ca²⁺ was observed. It is unclear why FLIGRLO-NH₂ appeared more potent at inducing intracellular calcium increase than the cognate proteases, though effects such as steric hindrance may play a role (Grimsey, Soto and Trejo, 2011). The findings of this study were further supported by PAR2-agonist induced Ca²⁺ signalling in ASM, however trypsin also reportedly induced calcium signalling (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019). Studies provide convincing evidence that activation of PAR2 by different proteases or in complex with other receptors provoke distinct signalling outcomes (Soh *et al.*, 2010). These selective cleavages by extracellular proteases enable PAR2 to regulate intracellular signalling and cell function in response to changes in a particular extracellular protease (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). By comparison, the neurotransmitter acetylcholine, which is reported to bind to the M₃ subtype of muscarinic receptors (Fryer and Jacoby, 1998), induced a significant and rapid increase in intracellular Ca²⁺, as has been previously suggested in isolated cells to mirror tissue responses (Placeres-Uray *et al.*, 2013; Brozovich *et al.*, 2016).

These observations suggest that PAR2 targeting directly on hBSMC generates calcium flux, consistent with literature reports of PAR2 causing both bronchoconstriction and bronchorelaxation in the airways. The phenomenon of contrasting responses reported could be due to receptor activation in differing cell types. For example, PAR2 in isolated airways could be activated via the epithelial layer causing bronchodilation but when activated at a smooth muscle cellular level the activation results in contraction. Distinct roles for different PAR2-modulating proteases, activating specific signalling pathways, could also be investigated.

Changes in airway structure and function are key to the pathogenesis of diseases such as COPD and asthma and the mechanisms resulting in these changes require exploration (Fehrenbach, Wagner and Wegmann, 2017). It has long been suggested that PARs are involved in the pathophysiology of various respiratory disorders, an idea arising due to observations of elevated levels of known PAR-activating

proteases such as tryptase in BAL fluid (Idell *et al.*, 1987). Murine studies have highlighted that PAR2 activation can play both pathological and protective roles in allergic asthma by mediating both potent bronchorelaxation and increased inflammation (Nichols *et al.*, 2012), and early studies reported bronchoconstriction (Schmidlin *et al.*, 2001). The response in the isolated murine airways following PAR2 activation in this study was confirmed as PAR2-dependent through the use of a PAR2^{-/-} model, in which FLIGRLO-NH₂ stimulated relaxation did not occur in the airways. These findings are the first to utilise a PAR2^{-/-} model to confirm a role for PAR2 in bronchorelaxation of pre-contracted murine airways. A differing response which could occur is the possibility that PAR2 agonists may cause a contraction in the absence of prior acetylcholine pre-contraction. The studies within this thesis have not extended to investigating this possibility and these aspects need to be further investigated to define the role of PAR2 more clearly.

An investigation into sex-specific differences in PAR2 response revealed no significant changes in PAR2-dependent relaxation in response to both trypsin and FLIGRLO-NH₂ in either bronchial or tracheal rings from male compared to female airways. The roles of sex and related hormones in lung function and disease are complex and not completely understood (Carey *et al.*, 2007). Historically, COPD has been more prevalent in men than women, predominantly due to higher smoking rates in males (Carey *et al.*, 2007). However, in females, reproductive processes such as pregnancy and menstruation impact asthma, suggesting that respiratory function is influenced by female sex hormones and menstrual cycle phase (Driver *et al.*, 2005; Stanford *et al.*, 2006). A previous study investigating the role of PAR2 in aortic rings of heterozygous (PAR2^{+/-}) mice included a study of sex-based effects. This investigation found relaxation of mouse aortas via activation of PAR2 using FLIGRLO-NH₂ was higher in females compared with males (Hennessey and McGuire, 2013). However, the data from isolated airways in this study highlights that the response to PAR2 activation is unaltered in scale between sexes. The reasons for this discrepancy are currently unclear but may reflect differences in the role of reproductive hormones in the regulation of vascular compared to airway smooth muscle. Historically, COPD had been predominantly in males however in recent years female COPD patients have been associated with more severe disease and decline in lung function. This has been suggested to be due to susceptibility to the lung-damaging impact of cigarette smoke (Sørheim *et al.*, 2010).

Limitations of this study include a lack of sample groups for comparison, for example the hBSMC used were from healthy patients only. To further enhance this study investigation into different disease groups such as COPD and non-obstructive smoker, alongside the healthy patients, would allow for a better characterisation of the role of PAR2 in a general state and in disease pathology. Indeed, cells from one COPD patient donor were sourced commercially for this study but were found impractical to expand sufficiently to support significant experimentation, due to the cells being less vigorous in proliferative capacity. This practical limitation may nevertheless prove interesting to explore in future work. Further studies could utilise a small number of cultures from diseased patients for comparison with healthy donors utilising immunofluorescence, to examine PAR2 subcellular distribution basally and following receptor activation. Collagen gel contraction assays, performed at the University of Leicester within the Infection, Immunity and Inflammation group provide a cellular link to the wire myography and provide a model to see if PAR2 could cause direct contraction in hBSMC (Saunders *et al.*, 2020). A further limitation to this study was the utilisation of only primary bronchial and tracheal rings from murine samples. Having access to secondary and tertiary bronchial rings would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of the interactions in the small airways. The further limitation to using murine bronchi and tracheal rings within the study, is that the tissue is from murine samples only and the results are not supported by human work.

To further develop this study the ability to gain bronchial tissue from human biopsy samples for functional analysis would be beneficial in characterising PAR2 response in parallel with the murine tissue samples. Subsequently, the use of PAR2 activator matriptase in *ex vivo* functional studies would allow a comparison with the studies carried out at cellular level in the calcium flux and ELISA assays, although this was considered impractical due to the expense of large quantities of this protease required for the relatively large volumes of myography chambers. Equally, other PAR2-activating proteases implicated in chronic respiratory disease such as neutrophil elastase, mast cell tryptase and proteinase-

3 (Krystel-Whittemore, Dileepan and Wood, 2016; Castro *et al.*, 2017; Heuberger *et al.*, 2020; Ward, 2020) could have been included in the present study, since different PAR activators are known to instigate distinct effects through biased signalling (Hollenberg *et al.*, 2014; Zhao, Metcalf and Bunnett, 2014; Jiang *et al.*, 2017).

Further enhancement of the cytokine secretion profile could be investigated through examining other cytokines involved in COPD pathology such as IL-1 β , IL-32 and TSLP (Barnes, 2009), since this study examined only 3 mediators (though all were known PAR2 effectors). Another limitation includes the lack of investigation into potential synergistic effects of PAR2. The receptor may be activated to greater effect in combination with other stimuli, as many factors converge to drive pathology (Barnes, 2009; Khalaf *et al.*, 2017). These factors include oxidative stress, which is a known driver of COPD pathology (Rahman, 2005).

3.7 Conclusion

The characterisation of PAR2 in this chapter provides for an improved understanding of the role of PAR2 at a cellular level in hBSMC and in an isolated whole tissue setting, building on previous findings, and confirming a bronchodilatory effect.

In the analysis of cytokine levels following PAR2 stimulation in hBSMC, it was highlighted that PAR2 appeared to have no substantial role in modulating IL-6, IL-8 or TNF- α secretion. Thus, in contrast to the situation in airway epithelial cells (Bailo *et al.*, 2020), there appears to be little evidence of a substantial role for PAR2 activation in isolated hBSMC in mediating inflammatory responses. Investigation into the intracellular calcium levels of hBSMC revealed that activation of PAR2 in these cells results in a dose-dependent increase in intracellular Ca²⁺. The isolated airway studies have provided a greater understanding of the response to PAR2 in a healthy animal, whilst allowing consideration of variables such as airway type and sex (with no significant difference in the PAR2-dependent response between male and female airways). Use of the PAR2^{-/-} model confirmed that the responses to trypsin and FLIGRLO-NH₂ were PAR2-dependent.

Understanding of the role of PAR2 in isolated airway tissues provides important baseline characterisation of a 'typical' PAR2 response out-with a disease context. These findings thus lay the groundwork for proceeding to further examine the role of PAR2 under disease relevant challenges in the forthcoming chapters of this thesis.

Chapter 4:
**Effect of Oxidative stress on
PAR2 regulation of ASM
function and lung tissue**

4 Effect of oxidative stress on PAR2 regulation of ASM function and lung tissue

4.1 Introduction

To determine the effects of PAR2 in modulating physiological characteristics of BSM in a context similar to that which may be experienced in the airways of COPD patients, oxidative stress was modelled *ex vivo*. Oxidative stress is a hallmark observed in the progression of disease pathology in people suffering with COPD. Oxidative stress is now recognised as being a major predisposing factor in driving COPD pathogenesis, specifically inflammation, and is reported to be an age-associated feature (Mercado *et al.*, 2015) which contributes to many pathogenic mechanisms (Kirkham & Barnes, 2013). Ageing is thought to be a cause of oxidative stress alongside inhalants such as cigarette smoke and air pollutants (Van Eeden and Sin, 2013). In conditions of oxidative stress, mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways are activated by reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Kamata *et al.*, 2005; Thimraj *et al.*, 2018). The impact of oxidative stress on COPD pathogenesis includes oxidative inactivation of antiproteases, mucus hypersecretion, remodelling of extracellular matrix and mitochondrial respiration (Rahman, 2005). Oxidative stress induced mitochondrial dysfunction in patients with COPD has been reported to enhance inflammation and cell hyperproliferation leading to hyperplasia and hypercontractility of the smooth muscle and subsequent airflow obstruction (Wiegman and Michaeloudes, 2015).

As the primary focus of this study was to investigate the role of PAR2 in a pathological setting relatable to COPD, a hallmark feature of which is the hypercontractility and hyper-reactivity of the airways causing airflow resistance, wire myography was used to measure regulation of ASM tone following oxidative stress induction and activation of PAR2. PAR2 activity is understood to mediate inflammatory processes and thus have an underpinning role in diverse pathologies. Promoting an inflammatory state via the introduction of oxidative stress might thus help elucidate the receptor's role in disease (Eltzschig & Carmeliet, 2011, Cervantes-Gracia *et al.*, 2020), particularly given the utilisation of PAR2-deficient tissues in this study. Receptor expression and key lung function markers were assessed using histological and immunohistochemical methods. This examination allowed for an insight into not only receptor function under these conditions, but also any possible structural alterations to be noted.

4.2 Hypothesis

Despite confirmed roles in inflammatory disease, acute PAR2 activation appears bronchoprotective under normal conditions. This bronchoprotective activity may however be modulated during disease-relevant challenges including oxidative stress, which could contribute to pathology during conditions such as COPD.

4.3 Aims

The overall aim of this study was to understand the role of PAR2 in a disease relevant setting, specifically by 1) determining if PAR2 maintains bronchoprotective effects in an *ex vivo* model of oxidative stress; 3) assessing if PAR2 expression in lung tissue is modulated during this condition.

4.4 Methods

Tissue sections were incubated overnight (typically 22 h) at 4 °C to act as a control while matched tissue sections were incubated over the same time period at 37 °C in a 95 % O₂ / 5 % CO₂ incubator. This protocol is adapted from a study by Aman *et al.*, (2010) who demonstrated that this method caused an oxidative stress-induced elevation in PAR2 in mouse aorta in the 37 °C incubated tissues, which was absent in those incubated at 4 °C (Maeda *et al.*, 2004; Aman *et al.*, 2010). Expression of PAR2 in an oxidative condition was assessed using immunohistochemistry (section 2.7.7). *Ex vivo* functional assessment was carried out using wire myography (section 2.6) to determine the functional response to PAR2 in murine airways, again in an oxidative condition with relevant controls. To confirm the oxidative state induced, an antioxidant (superoxide dismutase 1) was included in some experiments to investigate if the response was reversed or altered.

The data presented in this section of the study are generated from adult mice both male and female. Oxidative stress is a common risk factor associated with COPD and so the impact of oxidative stress on PAR2 dependent regulation of ASM in bronchial and tracheal rings from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} tissue were subject to this condition. The functionality of PAR2 was examined using *ex vivo* methods of measuring isometric tension after the oxidative condition was induced. A known PAR2 agonist, trypsin was used to target PAR2 following pre-contraction with Ach was performed. The full protocol can be found in section '2.6.4.1'.

4.5 Results

4.5.1 PAR2-dependent trypsin response in murine airways in an oxidative stress model

Contractile response to Ach was comparable to control following oxidative stress induction. Trypsin-dependent relaxation of bronchial rings from PAR2^{+/+} mice following a period of oxidative stress, however, was enhanced (54.5 ± 8.5 %) compared with control rings (35.1 ± 3.7 %) (Figure 4.1, A-C). As expected, trypsin-dependent relaxation of PAR2^{-/-} bronchial rings was virtually abolished under oxidative conditions (2.1 ± 0.6 %), similar to the lack of response seen in control (Figure 4.1, A), showing that the enhanced trypsin-dependent relaxation observed following oxidative stress was mediated by PAR2.

The regulation of ASM tone via PAR2 following oxidative stress was also investigated in PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine tracheal rings. Similar to the data observed in bronchial rings, there was a significant increase in trypsin-induced relaxation in tracheal rings from PAR2^{+/+} tissues following after oxidative stress (56.7 ± 10.5 %) compared with control (30.3 ± 2.9 %) (Figure 4.2, A-C). Again, this enhanced response under oxidative conditions was essentially abolished in PAR2^{-/-} tissue rings (2.4 ± 0.4 %) (Figure 4.2, Panel A), similar to control conditions, and Ach-dependent contraction appeared similar to control.

To summarise, the data in Figures 4.1 and 4.2 demonstrate that PAR2-mediated bronchorelaxation was significantly increased in a model of oxidative stress.

Figure 4.1 Effect of an oxidative stress model on PAR2-dependent murine bronchial ring relaxation. Murine bronchial rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and incubated overnight in control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions before mounting to a 4 channel myograph. Quantification of bronchodilatory response to PAR2 agonist trypsin (A), with representative tension recordings (B). Pairwise comparison of control vs. oxidative conditions in matched PAR2^{+/+} (C) and matched PAR2^{-/-} bronchial rings (D). The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of trypsin during the acetylcholine contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100 % respectively. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's post-hoc test (A) and Student's paired t test (C & D) and data are presented as mean ± SEM (n=6) **P* < 0.05 *cf.* treatment or genotype control, ****P* < 0.001.

Figure 4.2 Effect of an oxidative stress model on PAR2-dependent murine tracheal ring relaxation. Murine tracheal rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and incubated overnight in control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions before mounting to a 4 channel myograph. Quantification of bronchodilatory response to PAR2 agonist trypsin (A), with representative tension recordings (B). Pairwise comparison of control vs. oxidative conditions in PAR2^{+/+} (C) and PAR2^{-/-} tracheal rings (D). The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of trypsin during the acetylcholine contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100 % respectively. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's post-hoc test (A) and Student's paired t test (C & D) and data are presented as mean ± SEM (n=6) **P* < 0.05 *cf.* treatment or genotype control, ****P* < 0.001.

4.5.2 Effect of superoxide dismutase on PAR2-dependent bronchorelaxation in an oxidative stress model

Since the treatment to induce oxidative stress was an indirect method, the antioxidant superoxide dismutase (SOD1) was used to ‘rescue’ the effects of increased oxidant generation, to investigate if the impact on PAR2-mediated bronchorelaxation could be reversed. Experiments were performed using bronchial and tracheal rings from PAR2^{+/+} tissue subject to 4 °C or 37 °C overnight incubation. *Ex vivo* isometric tension measurements were made following induction of the stress condition with or without antioxidant incubation. The full protocol can be found in section 2.6.4.2.

Under control conditions, SOD1 incubation resulted in a concentration-dependent decrease in PAR2-dependent relaxation of bronchial rings (14.9 ± 1.1 % at 100 U, 6.9 ± 0.9 % at 250 U and 0.8 ± 0.8 % at 500 U) compared with control (25.4 ± 2.8 %) (Figure 4.3, A).

Under conditions of oxidative stress modelled via 37 °C incubation, SOD1 incubation again resulted in a concentration-dependent decrease in trypsin-dependent relaxation (12.8 ± 3.1 % at 100 U, 13.1 ± 4.5 % at 250 U and 2.6 ± 1.2 % at 500 U) compared with the SOD1-free control rings (46.3 ± 6.4 %) (Figure 4.3, C). As observed previously, in the absence of SOD1 there was a significant increase in trypsin-dependent relaxation was observed in the oxidative sample (46.3 ± 6.4 %) compared to control (25.4 ± 2.8 %). Although SOD1 effectively inhibited the bronchodilatory effect of trypsin under both conditions, at 100 U there was a greater impact on the trypsin response under oxidative conditions, reducing the residual response to the same level as control (Figure 4.3, E).

To summarise, the data shows that the antioxidant SOD1 inhibited trypsin-dependent relaxation under both control and oxidative conditions, whilst further suggesting that the enhanced oxidative response was more sensitive than the control response to moderate levels of antioxidant SOD1, consistent with the 37 °C incubation model indeed resulting in oxidative stress in bronchial rings.

Figure 4.3 Effect of SOD1 incubation on trypsin response in murine bronchial rings. Murine bronchial rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions with indicated concentrations of antioxidant SOD1, and subsequently mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Quantification of bronchodilatory response to PAR2 agonist trypsin after incubation at 4 °C (control) (A) and 37 °C (Oxidative) (C) and both compared (E) in presence of indicated SOD1 activity. Representative tension recordings are shown for 4 °C (B) and 37 °C (D) incubation. The control samples in all panels indicate the absence of SOD1. The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of trypsin during the acetylcholine contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100 % respectively. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way (A, C & E) with Bonferroni post-hoc test and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=6) ***P* < 0.01 *cf.* control, ****P* < 0.001 *cf.* control.

Analogous experiments using tracheal rings following SOD1 incubation similarly indicated a significant concentration-dependent decrease in trypsin-dependent relaxation compared with SOD1-free controls. The 4 °C control tracheal rings treated with SOD1 (19.4 ± 4.8 % at 100 U, 6.5 ± 1.5 % at 250 U and 0.3 ± 0.4 % at 500 U) exhibited significantly decreased relaxation compared with SOD-free controls (30.5 ± 1.5 %) (Figure 4.4, A).

The 37 °C oxidative model tracheal rings similarly exhibited a highly significant decrease in PAR2-dependent relaxation after SOD1 treatment, but in this case the trypsin response was almost abolished by the lowest amount of SOD1 activity used (100 U; 3.5 ± 1.0 %) compared with the 37 °C control rings (42.6 ± 4.4 %) (Figure 4.4, C). Comparing the 4 °C and 37 °C (oxidative) tracheal samples, in the absence of SOD1 an increase in PAR2-dependent relaxation was observed in the oxidative control sample (42.6 ± 4.4 %) compared with control (30.5 ± 1.5 %) (Figure 4.4, E). Incubation with 100 U SOD1 resulted in a significantly lower (almost abolished) relaxation in the oxidative model rings compared to control.

To summarise, the data show, similar to bronchial rings, that the antioxidant SOD1 inhibited trypsin-dependent relaxation of tracheal rings under both control and oxidative conditions, and further suggest that the enhanced oxidative response was more sensitive to moderate levels of antioxidant SOD1 than the control trypsin response.

Figure 4.4 Effect of SOD1 incubation on trypsin response in murine tracheal rings. Murine tracheal rings were dissected from PAR2^{+/+} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions with indicated concentrations of antioxidant SOD1, and subsequently mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Quantification of bronchodilatory response to PAR2 agonist trypsin after incubation at 4 °C (control) (A) and 37 °C (Oxidative) (C) and both compared (E) in presence of indicated SOD1 activity. Representative tension recordings are shown for 4 °C (B) and 37 °C (D) incubation. The control samples in all panels indicate the absence of SOD1. The levels of tension obtained at rest and just prior to the application of trypsin during the acetylcholine contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100 % respectively. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way (A & C) or two-way ANOVA (E) with Bonferroni post-hoc test and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=6) **P* < 0.05 *cf.* control, ***P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001.

4.5.3 Effect of oxidative stress model on superoxide dismutase expression

Antioxidant SOD1 was investigated by immunohistochemical staining in both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} tissue to further investigate the impact of PAR2 due to reported links between the receptor and oxidative stress (Hamilton, Frauman and Cocks, 2001a).

In the PAR2^{+/+} parenchyma, a significant increase in SOD1 expression was observed in the oxidative stress-exposed samples (180.4 ± 16.0 arbitrary units) compared with control (159.2 ± 9.5 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.5, E). Similarly, in the PAR2^{-/-} parenchymal tissue, a highly significant increase in SOD1 expression in the oxidative samples (209.0 ± 5.9 arbitrary units) compared with the control samples (145.7 ± 16.6 arbitrary units) was observed (Figure 4.5, E). When comparing genotypes, PAR2^{-/-} samples appeared to have slightly lower expression under control conditions, but somewhat higher in the oxidative condition (Figure 4.5, E), though it is unclear if this indicates any biological significance. SOD1 staining was apparent in both type I and type II pneumocytes with the staining appearing to be greater under oxidative conditions in both cell types. To summarise, the data in Figure 4.5 shows an increase in antioxidant superoxide dismutase expression in tissue samples exposed to the oxidative stress model compared to control, regardless of PAR2 status.

Figure 4.5 Effect of *ex vivo* oxidative stress on SOD1 expression in murine parenchymal tissue. Murine lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} (n=4) and PAR2^{-/-} (n=3) murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. SOD1 staining (Ab13498) in PAR2^{+/+} 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B) and PAR2^{-/-} 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) parenchyma which was quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (E). Isotypes shown as insets. Pneumocytes type 1 indicated by red arrowheads and pneumocytes type 2 indicated by green arrowheads, in the parenchymal tissue. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA and selected Bonferroni post-hoc test using Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

The airway analysis revealed a significant increase in SOD1 expression in the oxidative stress samples of PAR2^{+/+} mice (182.2 ± 17.8 arbitrary units) compared with the control samples (163.1 ± 10.7 arbitrary units), as well as in PAR2^{-/-} airways (oxidative, 212.9 ± 5.4 arbitrary units and control, 147.1 ± 18.5 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.6, E).

When comparing genotypes, PAR2^{-/-} airway samples, like parenchyma, appeared to have slightly lower expression under control conditions, but somewhat higher in the oxidative condition (Figure 4.6, E). The epithelial layer appeared to show a higher level of expression of SOD1 in the oxidative condition of both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} airways. In the oxidative conditions, the epithelial layer of cells appears to have completely detached from the smooth muscle layer. This is likely to be a histological processing artefact that may be due to delayed fixation, since the tissue was demonstrably maintained sufficient structural integrity to allow normal function, as observed in wire myography assays.

To summarise, Figure 4.6 shows an increase in antioxidant SOD1 expression in airways exposed to an oxidative stress model, regardless of PAR2 presence.

Figure 4.6 Effect of *ex vivo* oxidative stress on SOD1 expression in murine airways. Tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} (n=4) and PAR2^{-/-} (n=3) murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. SOD1 staining in PAR2^{+/+} 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B) and PAR2^{-/-} 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) airways was quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (E). Isotypes shown as insets. In the airways, the epithelial layer is indicated by blue arrowheads and the smooth muscle of the airway indicated by orange arrowheads. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA and selected Bonferroni post-hoc test using Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM ****P* < 0.001.

Arteriole analysis revealed similar observations; a small but significant increase in SOD1 expression was observed in the PAR2^{+/+} oxidative stress-exposed samples (176.3 ± 15.8 arbitrary units) compared with the controls (162.0 ± 9.6 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.7, E). In PAR2^{-/-} arterioles, a more pronounced and significant increase in SOD1 expression was found in the oxidative-exposed samples (210.3 ± 3.9 arbitrary units) compared with to control (108.0 ± 44.3 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.7, E). Comparing genotypes, PAR2^{-/-} samples once again appeared to have lower expression than wild type under control conditions, but higher in the oxidative condition (Figure 4.7, E).

In the smooth muscle layer (yellow arrows in Fig. 4.7) of the arterioles, a higher level of SOD1 expression was apparent in the oxidative conditions of both the PAR2^{+/+} and the PAR2^{-/-} samples. In the control groups, the level of SOD1 expression appeared lower in the PAR2^{-/-} smooth muscle layer compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples. To summarise, the data in Figure 4.7 shows an increase in SOD1 expression in arterioles under oxidative conditions, regardless of PAR2 expression status.

Figure 4.7 Effect of *ex vivo* oxidative stress on SOD1 expression in murine arterioles. Tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} (n=4) and PAR2^{-/-} (n=3) murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. SOD1 expression was assessed in PAR2^{+/+} 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B), and PAR2^{-/-} 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) arterioles, quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (E). Isotypes shown as insets. In the arterioles, the endothelial layer is indicated by purple arrowheads with the smooth muscle being identified through yellow arrowheads. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA and selected Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM *** $P < 0.001$.

4.5.4 Effect of oxidative stress exposure on PAR2 expression in murine tissue

Given the observed enhancement of trypsin-dependent bronchorelaxation under oxidative conditions, the expression of PAR2 in this temperature-induced *ex vivo* oxidative stress model was examined via immunohistochemistry and analysed using both Zen Blue and TissueGnostics Strataquest software. Both methods of analysis were explored to provide qualitatively different analyses including positive cells counting using Zen Blue and average mean stain intensity using the Strataquest software.

Using Zen Blue software, a trend ($P = 0.1$) was observed suggesting an increase in PAR2 expression in the parenchyma of the oxidative samples (58.0 ± 0.1 Arbitrary units) compared with the control samples (32.7 ± 0.03 Arbitrary units) (Figure 4.8, C). Heterogeneity of the response was highlighted in this investigation based on the paired analysis, showing that two animals responded with increased PAR2 expression, whilst two showed no change.

Analysis using Strataquest software showed that in the parenchymal tissue there was a highly significant increase in PAR2 expression in the oxidative samples (13.8 ± 4.8 Arbitrary units) compared with the control samples (3.8 ± 1.2 Arbitrary units) (Figure 4.9, C). The PAR2 staining observed in the parenchymal tissue appears to be present in both type I and II pneumocytes, however predominantly type II with a higher level of expression in the oxidative condition. Cell types were identified and indicating using arrowheads in Figure 4.9, based on cellular morphology and location within the tissue. A similar result was observed in the airways, with staining in both the epithelium and the airway smooth muscle. A significant increase in receptor expression was found in the oxidative airways (3.9 ± 1.2 Arbitrary units) compared with the control airways (2.4 ± 0.9 Arbitrary units) (Figure 4.9, F). The airway smooth muscle exhibited PAR2 expression in both conditions, again appearing to have a higher level of staining in the oxidative condition compared with the control.

In arterioles, a highly significant increase in receptor expression of vessels exposed to oxidative conditions (20.1 ± 6.5 Arbitrary units) compared with the control vessels (2.6 ± 1.5 Arbitrary units) was observed (Figure 4.9, Panel I). The endothelial layer exhibited a higher level of PAR2 expression in the oxidative condition compared with the control. The smooth muscle layer however did not appear to show any change in expression of PAR2, with a low level of expression in both conditions. In both the airways and the arterioles, the epithelial and endothelial layer of cells appear to be detached completely from the smooth muscle layer in the oxidative condition, as observed in the SOD1 immunohistochemical analysis. Despite the airway rings being demonstrably functional after incubation, the tissue (including parenchyma) appeared noticeably less amenable to processing for histology than that freshly fixed post-dissection. Despite these differences, structural features and cell types within the tissue could still be identified with confidence.

The combination of methods of analysis for these samples shows qualitatively similar results from both methods, with significant changes being found using Strataquest software assessing stain intensity (as compared to & cells assigned positive). The ability to make qualitatively distinct assessments on the level of staining and the proportion of positive cells allowed for a more robust expression analysis.

Overall, the data in Figures 4.8 and 4.9 is consistent with increased PAR2 expression in parenchyma, airways and arterioles of the samples subjected to a condition of oxidative stress compared with the controls.

Figure 4.8 Effect of *ex vivo* oxidative stress on PAR2 expression in murine parenchymal tissue. Murine lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy and immunohistochemical staining for PAR2 expression using Alomone antibody (APR-32) in parenchymal tissue. Representative images of PAR2 staining of 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B), with isotype staining using rabbit IgG₁ inset with pneumocytes type 1 indicated by red arrowheads and pneumocytes type 2 indicated by green arrowheads. Quantification of positively stained cells using Zen Blue (C). All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's paired t test and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=4).

Figure 4.9 PAR2 expression in murine tissue in an oxidative stress *ex vivo* model. Murine lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} murine samples and incubated overnight in both the control (4 °C) and oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed and cut into sections for staining. PAR2 expression stained in PAR2^{+/+} using APR-32 in 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B) parenchyma which was quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (C). Airways of 4 °C (D) and 37 °C (E) samples were also immunohistochemically stained using APR-32 and quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (F). PAR2 expression in arterioles of 4 °C (G) and 37 °C (H) samples were stained using APR-32 and quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (I). Isotypes shown as insets. In the parenchyma, pneumocytes type 1 are indicated by red arrowheads and pneumocytes type 2 indicated by green arrowheads. In the airways, the epithelial layer is indicated by blue arrowheads and the smooth muscle of the airway indicated by orange arrowheads. In the arterioles, the endothelial layer is indicated by purple arrowheads with the smooth muscle being identified through yellow arrowheads. All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's paired t test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad) with (n=4) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM ****P* < 0.001.

4.5.5 Effect of oxidative stress exposure on lung collagen

To investigate the impact of oxidative stress on connective tissues in the murine PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} lung, Masson's Trichrome stain was used and staining analysed using TissueGnostics Strataquest (section 2.7.9). The Aniline Blue component of the Trichrome is understood to preferentially indicate the presence of collagen (Rieppo *et al.*, 2019; Al-Mahmood, 2020). This is mostly likely collagen type I in the lung, though this stain does not specifically differentiate between collagen types. The average mean intensity was measured using reference shades which correspond to the Aniline Blue stain.

Upon analysis of the PAR2^{+/+} parenchymal tissue, a highly significant increase in Aniline Blue staining was observed in the tissue exposed to oxidative conditions (29.8 ± 8.6 arbitrary units) compared with

control (14.0 ± 2.4 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.10, E), and similar observations were made in the PAR2^{-/-} parenchymal tissue (oxidative; 45.1 ± 6.0 arbitrary units, control; 34.0 ± 4.7 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.10, E). When comparing genotypes, there was significantly more Aniline Blue staining in PAR2^{-/-} parenchyma in both control and oxidative conditions compared to PAR2^{+/+} parenchyma (Figure 4.10, E). The staining pattern is observed throughout the parenchymal tissue, being present throughout the alveolar structures.

To summarise, Aniline Blue staining and thus collagen levels appeared significantly increased after 24 h exposure to *ex vivo* oxidative stress conditions, and significantly increased in the PAR2^{-/-} tissue.

Figure 4.10 Effect of oxidative stress on collagen content in murine parenchymal tissue. Tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. Collagen was stained using Masson's Trichrome (Aniline Blue) in PAR2^{+/+} 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B) parenchymal tissue (n=4), and PAR2^{-/-} 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) (n=3), and average mean stain intensity quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (E). All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's post hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001

Analysis of the airways revealed similar results to those observed in the parenchymal tissue. Firstly, one notable change in terms of structural architecture of the airways, is the apparent collapse of the lumen in the oxidative samples of both the PAR2^{+/+} and the PAR2^{-/-} tissue. Secondly, the epithelial layer appears to detach from the smooth muscle layer of the airways. These histological changes were consistent throughout the oxidative tissue samples. In the PAR2^{+/+} airways, there was a significant increase in Aniline Blue staining of oxidative stress-exposed samples (32.6 ± 4.7 arbitrary units) compared to control (11.2 ± 2.1 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.11, E). The PAR2^{-/-} airway analysis also suggested a significant increase in collagen content upon oxidative stress (46.7 ± 4.0 Arbitrary units) compared to control (33.7 ± 6.2 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.11, E). When comparing genotypes there was a substantial and significant increase in Aniline Blue staining of PAR2^{-/-} airways compared with wild type tissue, in both control and oxidative stress conditions (Figure 4.11, E). Regarding collagen distribution, more readily apparent areas of staining surround the outer surface of the airway structures, with highest abundance observed in PAR2^{-/-} oxidative stress samples.

To summarise, airways collagen content appeared significantly increased in the oxidative condition of both genotypes compared with control, and significantly increased in the PAR2^{-/-} tissue of both groups compared with the PAR2^{+/+} airways.

Figure 4.11 Effect of oxidative stress on collagen content in murine airways. Tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. Collagen content was assessed using Masson's Trichrome (Aniline Blue) in PAR2^{+/+} 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B) (n=4), and PAR2^{-/-} 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) (n=3) airway tissue and quantified (E) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's post hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM ***P < 0.001.

Finally, the arterioles analysis in PAR2^{+/+} tissue revealed a significant increase in Aniline Blue staining of the oxidative stress condition vessels (34.1 ± 7.2 arbitrary units) compared with control (15.6 ± 2.7 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.12, E). Similar observations were made when analysing the PAR2^{-/-} arterioles, a highly significant increase in the oxidative stress samples (45.1 ± 6.0 arbitrary units) compared with control (34.0 ± 4.7 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.12, E) was seen. When comparing genotypes, PAR2-deficient tissue once again exhibited significantly higher Aniline Blue staining compared with wild type arterioles (Figure 4.12, E). Similar to the airways, collagen distribution appears to predominantly surround the arteriole structures, with the highest stain intensity observed following oxidative stress in the absence of PAR2.

To summarise, collagen content was observed to be significantly increased following oxidative stress conditions in both genotypes, with a greater intensity of staining present in PAR2^{-/-} tissue.

Figure 4.12 Effect of oxidative stress on collagen content in murine arterioles. Tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. Collagen content assessed by Masson's Trichrome stain (Aniline Blue) in PAR2^{+/+} 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B), (n=4), and PAR2^{-/-} 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) (n=3) arteriole tissue, quantified by average mean stain intensity (E) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's post hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM ***P* < 0.01 ****P* < 0.001.

4.5.6 Effect of oxidative stress exposure on smooth muscle content

The airway smooth muscle plays a vital role in regulating airway lumen diameter and thus in a disease such as COPD can have detrimental effects if dysregulated in disease pathology. In COPD the dysregulation of ASM leads to hyperplasia and hypercontractility leading to obstruction of airflow (Chung, 2005). Oxidative stress induced mitochondrial dysfunction in patients with COPD have been reported to enhance inflammation and cell hyperproliferation (Wiegman and Michaeloudes, 2015). There is also increasing evidence suggesting involvement of pulmonary vascular pathology for COPD development. Cigarette smoke may directly affect the pulmonary vasculature leading to vascular remodelling and pulmonary hypertension (Orr, Lewis and Cuttica, 2012). The abundance of smooth muscle was examined by immunohistochemical staining for smooth muscle actin (SMA) following *ex vivo* induction of oxidative stress and analysed using TissueGnostics Strataquest software as described previously.

Parenchyma was not analysed as there was no expectation of significant smooth muscle content. In PAR2^{+/+} airways, there was no significant change observed after induction of oxidative stress, although a trend ($P = 0.1$) toward increased SMA was observed (oxidative; 6.6 ± 2.3 arbitrary units, control; 4.7 ± 1.9 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.13, E). Interestingly, in the PAR2^{-/-} airways, a contrasting result was observed, with a significant decrease in SMA evident in the oxidative stress samples (7.5 ± 2.4 arbitrary units) compared with control (13.1 ± 5.5 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.13, E). Comparing genotypes, control samples showed a significant increase in SMA of the PAR2^{-/-} (13.1 ± 5.5 arbitrary units) compared to the PAR2^{+/+} samples (4.7 ± 1.9 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.13, E), but following oxidative stress SMA content was unchanged regardless of PAR2 status (Figure 4.13, E). Distribution of SMA staining can be seen observed in each panel of Figure 4.13, surrounding the epithelial layer as expected.

To summarise, in wild-type tissues, there was a trend toward increased smooth muscle content. Interestingly, this was reversed in PAR2-deficient tissue, reducing under oxidative stress from an elevated basal level compared to wild-type.

Figure 4.13 Effect of oxidative stress *ex vivo* on SMA content in murine airways. Tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. SMA in PAR2^{+/+} airways of 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B) (n=4) samples and 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) PAR2^{-/-} (n=3) samples was assessed by staining using sc-53142 antibody (indicated by red arrowheads) and average mean intensity quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (E). Isotypes shown as inset images. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA and selected Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM *** P < 0.001.

In arterioles, there was no significant change in SMA content in the PAR2^{+/+} oxidative stress samples (9.2 ± 3.5 arbitrary units) compared with control (6.4 ± 1.9 arbitrary units), but similar to the pattern in airways, oxidative conditions in PAR2^{-/-} arterioles led to a significant decrease in SMA staining (11.4 ± 4.3 arbitrary units) compared with control (24.0 ± 7.1 arbitrary units) (Figure 4.14, E). Again, SMA staining was significantly enhanced in control PAR2^{-/-} arterioles compared to wild type, but no genotype-dependent difference was apparent following oxidative stress induction (Figure 4.14, E). A trend toward increased smooth muscle content was observed in wild-type tissues. Interestingly, this was reversed in PAR2-deficient tissue, reducing under oxidative stress from an elevated basal level compared to wild-type.

Figure 4.14 Effect of oxidative stress *ex vivo* on SMA content in murine arterioles. Tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} murine samples and incubated overnight in either control (4 °C) or oxidative (37 °C) conditions, before being processed for microtomy. SMA in PAR2^{+/+} arterioles of 4 °C (A) and 37 °C (B) (n=4) samples and 4 °C (C) and 37 °C (D) PAR2^{-/-} (n=3) samples was assessed by staining using sc-53142 antibody (indicated by red arrowheads) and average mean intensity quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (E). Isotypes shown as inset images. All images were captured using Zeiss Axioscan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA and selected Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM ***P < 0.001.

Tissue / experiment	Oxidative	
	PAR2 ^{+/+}	PAR2 ^{-/-}
PAR2-dep relaxation (Bronchi)	↑	↓
PAR2-dep relaxation (Trachea)	↑	↓
SOD sensitivity of PAR2 response (Bronchi)	↑	-
SOD sensitivity of PAR2 response (Trachea)	↑	-
Parenchyma / PAR2 expression	↑	-
Airway / PAR2 expression	↑	-
Arterioles / PAR2 expression	↑	-
Parenchyma / SOD expression	↑	↑
Airway / SOD expression	↑	↑
Arterioles / SOD expression	↑	↑
Parenchyma / Collagen Expression	↑	↑
Airways / Collagen Expression	↑	↑
Arterioles / Collagen Expression	↑	↑
Airways / SM Expression	NSD↑	↓
Arterioles / SM Expression	NSD↑	↓

Table 4.1 Summary of results and key findings throughout the investigation into oxidative stress-induced changes.

4.6 Discussion

COPD is a multifactorial disease with many risk factors contributing to pathogenesis (Huertas and Palange, 2011). This chapter utilised both functional and immunohistochemical analyses to explore the impact of the disease-relevant challenge of oxidative stress on lung tissue, with particular regard to the role of PAR2 in modulating bronchodilatation.

A major risk factor for COPD is an environment promoting oxidative stress, which is now recognised as being a major predisposing factor in driving pathogenesis, specifically oxidative inactivation of antiproteases, smooth muscle hyperplasia and remodelling of extracellular matrix, all via inflammation (Kirkham & Barnes, 2013). Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are critical for homeostatic cellular and physiological functions in the lung setting (Zorov, Juhaszova and Sollott, 2014). However, within a pro-oxidant and pro-inflammatory environment, the accumulation of ROS has consequences of tissue

damage and cellular metabolism resulting in cell death (Comhair and Erzurum, 2010). During this investigation into oxidative stress effects, a significant increase in PAR2-dependent relaxation was observed in oxidative conditions in both bronchial and tracheal rings. Due to oxidative stress resulting from an imbalance between the production of ROS and their elimination by protective mechanisms, this subsequently leads to chronic inflammation, which has previously been implicated in both COPD and asthma (Cheeseman & Slater, 1994; Zuo et al., 2019). An increase in pro-inflammatory stimuli, such as ROS, has previously been reported in the literature to cause an increase in PAR2 expression in human endothelial cells (Hamilton, Frauman and Cocks, 2001a). Thus, the increase in ROS as stimuli for inflammation could explain the increase in PAR2 expression and ultimately an increase in PAR2-dependent relaxation. To further understand the impact of the oxidative stress environment on PAR2 expression on the murine tissue, airways, arterioles and parenchymal tissue were all analysed. Significant increases in PAR2 expression across all three tissue types under oxidative conditions, particularly in the airways and arterioles, was consistent with the greater PAR2 relaxant response observed in airways, as well as reports of an increase in PAR2 expression in endothelial cells following inflammatory stimuli (Hamilton *et al.*, 2001; Aman et al., 2010).

The combination of analysis methods for these samples shows qualitatively similar results, with significant changes being found using Strataquest software assessing stain intensity (as compared to cells assigned positive). The analysis using Zen Blue software found a trend showing an increase in PAR2 positive cells in the oxidative parenchymal tissue compared with the control samples. This may reflect possible bias limitations to the Zen Blue analysis when manually selecting positively stained cells compared with the unbiased method of computer determination using Strataquest. The ability to analyse mean intensity of PAR2 in structures such as airways and arterioles within this tissue revealed similar results to those found in the parenchymal tissue in terms of PAR2 expression between the two groups. The ability to make qualitatively distinct assessments on the level of staining and the proportion of positive cells allowed for a more robust expression analysis. A potential caveat to these findings arises due to the apparent histological artefacts particularly affecting the appearance of tissues exposed to oxidative stress conditions. It cannot be excluded that difficulties in processing of these tissues might give rise to altered efficiency of staining. However, it should be noted that staining appeared localised to specific areas and cells, not obviously consistent with a generalised artefactual effect.

Immunohistochemical staining for SOD1 revealed increased content following induction of the oxidative stress model via 37 °C incubation, indicating an adaptive response to elevated ROS in this model. Furthermore, trypsin-dependent airway relaxation was effectively inhibited by exogenous SOD1 addition, with the response under oxidative conditions being particularly sensitive to this enzyme activity.

Antioxidants, specifically SOD1, have the potential to be a therapeutic strategy in inflammatory disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis (Salvemini *et al.*, 1999). The use of SOD1 as an antioxidant and therapeutic agent in acute and chronic inflammatory conditions has been previously reported in the literature (Bowler *et al.*, 2004; Younus, 2018). Further support for the use of SOD1 therapy comes from murine models of asthma, which offer a link between antioxidants and airway hyper-responsiveness. This was shown by transgenic mice overexpressing SOD1 having a decrease in allergen-induced physiological changes in comparison with control samples (Larsen *et al.*, 2000). Similarly, treatment with SOD1 reduces the magnitude of ovalbumin-induced airway hyper-responsiveness in murine models of asthma (Chang and Crapo, 2002). Furthermore in sensitised guinea pigs, SOD1 treatment was given prior to antigen challenge which resulted in the attenuation of the allergen-induced bronchospasm (Masini *et al.*, 2005). These animal models further support the observations made within this study alluding to the ability of SOD1 to attenuate responses in a disease-relevant model. On the other hand, dependence of PAR2 relaxatory (thus protective) responses on ROS may mean that antioxidants may be a double-edged sword in this context. One potential alternative therapeutic strategy may be suggested by the potential to selectively activate PAR2 through biased signalling (Ayoub and Pin, 2013) in order to enhance the PAR2-dependent broncho-relaxation, whilst targeting deleterious effects.

Tissue remodelling is a common feature of COPD pathology and so investigating the impact of risk factors associated with the disease on tissue remodelling is important to understanding disease mechanisms. The most abundant component of the extracellular matrix is collagen type I, which provides structural support and is a primary contributor to lung and airway mechanics (Suki & Bates, 2008; Yue, 2014), and this study found significant increases in collagen abundance under oxidative stress. The involvement of PAR2 in renal injury and fibrosis is consistent with observations made in a study which showed inhibition of trypsin-like proteinases can protect the kidneys and liver from fibrosis by mechanisms involving collagen expression (Okuno *et al.*, 2001; Maekawa *et al.*, 2009). A study also involving the impact of PAR2 on collagen involvement in renal fibrosis supported a role for PAR2 through the use of a PAR2-deficient model. This study revealed a reduction in tubular damage in the obstructed kidneys of PAR2-deficient mice which was associated with decreased tissue fibrosis and collagen synthesis (Chung *et al.*, 2013). Analysis of Masson's Trichrome and Picrosirius Red staining revealed a significantly lower amount of fibrosis in the PAR2-deficient mice (Chung *et al.*, 2013; Kalayarasan *et al.*, 2013). However, the current study produced contrasting results in the context of the lung, whereby the absence of PAR2 resulted in significantly increased collagen content compared to wild type tissue. Furthermore, oxidative stress-dependent collagen increase was observed regardless of PAR2 status, indicating that this phenomenon is PAR2-independent in murine lung. It is possible that the increased lung collagen observed in PAR2-deficient animals resulted from the down-regulation of collagenolytic/gelatinolytic processes (Yamada and Matsumoto, 2017).

The airway smooth muscle is the key factor in airway pathophysiology through its ability to regulate both the diameter and bronchomotor tone and the remodelling observed in COPD patients (Pan, Conaway & Deshpande, 2019). Under control conditions, PAR2 deficiency appeared to increase smooth muscle content of murine lungs, but not under conditions of oxidative stress, a driving mechanism in COPD pathology (Barnes, 2020). Changes in airway structure and function are thought to be vital in the pathogenesis of specific diseases such as COPD and asthma (Fehrenbach *et al.*, 2017). Hypertrophy and hyperplasia of the ASM in COPD can be directly correlated to a decline in lung function and with an increase in severity of airway wall thickening (Hogg *et al.*, 2004). The increase in ASM mass is an essential component of airway remodelling which accounts for airway narrowing and loss of respiratory function in patients with severe asthma and/or COPD (Aubier *et al.*, 2016). In wild type animals expressing PAR2, there was no significant change in airway or arteriole smooth muscle in the oxidative condition, albeit a trend toward increase was observed. It has been previously suggested that PAR2 activity is associated with hypertrophy and hyperplasia of the smooth muscle in the airways, via β -arrestin dependent inflammatory mechanisms (Nichols *et al.*, 2012). A similar response via PAR2 mediating hyperplasia has been reported in the vascular smooth muscle (Wei *et al.*, 2019). In the later study, cells overexpressing PAR2 promoted cell proliferation compared to control cells and also promoted an increase in cyclin-dependent kinase 2 (CDK2) which is a cell division protein which is required for the transition from G1 to S phase of the cell cycle (Wei *et al.*, 2019). These reports of PAR2 roles in causing smooth muscle cell proliferation appear to diverge from the current findings (notwithstanding the observed trend toward modest smooth muscle increase), although discrepancies may arise from the short-term *ex vivo* nature of the oxidative model used here, which is likely too transient and simplistic a system to support observable changes in smooth muscle remodelling.

The current limitations of this study include the immunohistochemistry samples only having a total of n=4; an increase in sample size would enhance the robustness of this investigation. Utilising a model of chemically induced oxidative stress through the use of a reagent such as hydrogen peroxide may also allow for a better understanding of the impact of ROS on PAR2-dependent relaxation (Park *et al.*, 2012; Zhu *et al.*, 2020). The model used within this study was chosen due to the published precedent in vascular tissue (Aman *et al.*, 2010). To progress the histological study, the difference in collagen deposition between the samples within the study could be further investigated using a more collagen specific stain, for example Picrosirius Red stain, which allows quantitative morphometric analysis under polarised light, or collagen specific antibodies such as anti-collagen I and anti-collagen III (Croxford *et al.*, 2013). The Picrosirius red stain would confirm histological visualisation of collagen type I and collagen type III fibres, whilst the antibodies would allow differentiation between specific collagen types, compared with the current stain used which visualises collagenous connective tissue fibres in

general. This is important as these two types of collagen are the main cohorts of collagen identified in the lung and it is unknown if there is a variation in ratio between the two in disease pathology (Harju *et al.*, 2010). A technical limitation that was identified within the study was the use of large airways for the functional assays but small airways (most relevant to COPD pathology) for histological investigation. This was due to the inability to obtain small airways from the lung tissue and mount for the functional assays. Large airways such as tracheal rings could also be used for immunohistochemical studies in the future as were used in the functional assays. A further limitation of the study includes variation of size between structures. This was alleviated where possible with arterioles and airways of similar size being compared, however in some instances this was unachievable due to the cross sections taken and the limited number of structures within those sections. To overcome this, further sections and staining could be performed in order to provide more sample structures for comparison. As previously mentioned, although the tissue was responsive in a functional capacity, it cannot be excluded that there may have been some loss of integrity in the epithelial layer consistent for example with the immunohistochemistry images. The changes observed following over-night incubation lead to apparent structural changes that if genuine may lead to differences in behaviour. There would be difficulties in extending the model beyond the 24-hour period due to any such possible structural changes. An acute condition of oxidative stress using the same method could potentially be investigated for a shorter duration to circumvent some of these issues.

Further work could look to answer the question of whether PAR2 plays a role (by upregulation of receptor activity) in causing enhanced bronchodilation of the airways in COPD disease pathology, potentially through the use of an *in vivo* disease model, such as exposure to cigarette smoke or other noxious challenges (Ghorani *et al.*, 2017). To further probe the mechanisms of the relaxation in both oxidative and control conditions, investigation into cyclo-oxygenase pathway dependence could be examined, given the reported importance of this pathway in mediating PAR2 downstream effects (Chia *et al.*, 2011). Parallel experiments with the presence of SOD1 could be performed using immunohistochemical studies to investigate the potential to rescue the changes observed in markers including collagen and SMA. Investigation into the impact of oxidative stress on cytokine secretion within the tissue would also allow a further understanding in disease pathology and the links between oxidative stress and inflammation.

4.7 Conclusion

The results show that short-term *ex vivo* oxidative stress has an impact on both the function and expression of PAR2, and which may impact on COPD associated features of the lungs and airways involved in remodelling such as collagen and smooth muscle. This indicates the importance of PAR2 as a key factor in BSM pathophysiology due to its ability to attenuate broncho-relaxation in a disease setting. The data confirm a bronchodilatory effect of PAR2 that is dependent on ROS and is not only maintained but enhanced during oxidative stress, at least in this experimental model. This study represents a first insight into the role of PAR2 in modulating bronchial tone in oxidative stress. A more detailed future characterisation will build on this work to further explore pathogenic mechanisms that may be relevant to the development of COPD.

Chapter 5:

Lung Ageing and PAR2

5. Lung Ageing and PAR2

5.1 Introduction

The human lung reaches maturity by age 20-25, and further ageing thereafter is associated with progressive decline in lung function (Sharma & Goodwin, 2006). For example, the airway are less likely to respond to drugs used effectively in younger counterparts (Sharma and Goodwin, 2006). Lungs of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) are known to prematurely age, resulting in the promotion of a persistent inflammatory microenvironment within the airway, and associated hypercontractility and hyperreactivity (Duncan, 2016). The remodelling process includes epithelial hyperplasia and a proliferative state of the airway smooth muscle (ASM), with increased mass comprising hyperplasia and hypertrophy (Chung, 2005). This pathological feature of hypertrophy of the ASM leads to an increased airway resistance which contributes to the symptoms and pathogenesis of COPD. A G-protein coupled receptor known as proteinase activated receptor 2 (PAR2) is a potential therapeutic target for inflammatory conditions such as COPD, with documented roles including the induction of bronchodilation in diseased lungs (Pera and Penn, 2016). These roles for PAR2 have yet to be fully explored in the context of ageing. In the presence of age-related changes significant effects on airway reactivity and response to bronchodilator therapy have been reported (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019).

Ageing is a key risk factor in the progression of COPD pathology (López-Otín *et al.*, 2013). The modulation by PAR2 of physiological and inflammatory responses of murine airway smooth muscle was compared at two defined ages, using wire myography to characterise airway hypercontractility. As the primary focus of this study was to investigate the link between ageing and PAR2, the receptor expression was also determined using histological and immunohistochemical methods. This experimental design enabled characterisation of receptor expression to determine if there were changes in expression during ageing.

The objectives then were two-fold: to elucidate both the effect of the ageing process on PAR2-dependent ASM responsiveness, and the role of PAR2 in age-related structural lung changes.

5.2 Hypothesis

As a non-modifiable risk factor of COPD, ageing is a modulator of physiological and structural changes in the lung, including altered PAR2-mediated airway functionality.

5.3 Aims

The aims of this study were to 1) investigate the effects of ageing on the PAR2-mediated airway smooth muscle response, 2) evaluate the expression of PAR2 in lung tissue from young vs. older mice, and 3) assess the impact of both PAR2 and ageing on structural factors including collagen and smooth muscle.

5.4 Methods

The methods which were used to investigate these risk factors are documented fully in Chapter 2. In summary, the tissue was dissected and prepared for experimentation following the protocols presented in Section 2.6. Expression of PAR2 and smooth muscle actin in both ≥ 12 -month and ≤ 4 -month PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} samples was carried out immunohistochemically to determine the expression of the markers in each of the samples. The full protocol for the immunohistochemical staining is presented in Section 2.7.6. Collagen expression in PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} samples from both age groups was carried out histologically using Masson's trichrome stain, (Section 2.7.5). *Ex vivo* functional assessment using wire myography was carried out to determine the functional airway response to PAR2 activation in murine airways, again at both defined ages in PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} mouse samples. The detailed protocol which was used for the functional assessment of the airway samples is provided in Section 2.6.4.5. The sex, age, and genotype for each of the samples included within this study are detailed in Table 5.1 below. The samples classified as ≥ 12 months were done so based on the Jackson Laboratory classifications. This age range was limited by the Home Office Project License (PL) that this project was governed under. This enabled mice to be maintained for only up to 15 months of age.

Genotype							
PAR2 ^{+/+}				PAR2 ^{-/-}			
≤ 4-month		≥ 12-month		≤ 4-month		≥ 12-month	
Sex	Age	Sex	Age	Sex	Age	Sex	Age
Male	11 weeks 1 day	Male	63 weeks	Male	20 weeks 1 day	Male	54 weeks 4 days
Male	12 weeks 4 days	Male	64 weeks 2 days	Male	20 weeks 2 day	Female	58 weeks 6 days
Male	12 weeks 4 days	Male	64 weeks 2 days	Male	20 weeks 3 day	Female	59 weeks
Female	13 weeks 1 day	Female	64 weeks	Male	20 weeks 4 day	Female	59 weeks 2 days
Female	13 weeks 1 day	Female	64 weeks	Female	13 weeks	Female	64 weeks 2 days
Female	14 weeks 3 days	Female	63 weeks 4 days	Female	13 weeks 3 days	Female	63 weeks
				Female	13 weeks 5 days	Female	63 weeks 2 days

Table 5.1 Genotype, age group, sex and age information for murine tissue used throughout this study.

All the images for the immunohistochemistry analysis within this chapter were taken on Zeiss Zen blue software (Zeiss, UK) the parenchyma at 110 % zoom and both the airways and arterioles at 100 % zoom.

5.5 Results

The data presented in this section of the study are generated from a total of 6 PAR2^{+/+} ≤ 4-month mice, 6 PAR2^{+/+} ≥ 12-month mice, 7 PAR2^{-/-} ≤ 4-month mice and 7 PAR2^{-/-} ≥ 12-month mice; both male and female were included (Table 5.1). The data presented in this chapter are part of a collaborative-study based on the same tissue samples derived from the same mice; the contributions by Kirsty McCallum are identified where presented (Figure Legends) and included to enable wider conclusions to be drawn.

5.5.1 PAR2 agonist response in PAR2^{+/+} murine bronchi

To explore the impact of ageing on PAR2-mediated functionality, bronchial rings from ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month mice were examined using an *ex vivo* method for measuring isometric tension in isolated airways. Following pre-contraction with acetylcholine, a dose response to a known PAR2 activating peptide, FLIGRLO-NH₂, was performed (Figure 5.1, Panel A & B). FOLIGRL-NH₂ is a scrambled sequence of the activating peptide and serves as an internal negative control. A dose response to this negative control (Figure 5.1, Panel C & D) was performed in parallel to allow direct comparison between the two peptides and thus confirm PAR2 specificity of the FLIGRLO-NH₂ peptide.

The results demonstrated a significant ($P < 0.001$) decrease in the relaxant response to PAR2 activation in the ≥ 12-month tissue when stimulated with 1 μM FLIGRLO-NH₂ (9.1 ± 0.4 %) compared with the ≤ 4-month (33.0 ± 9.4 %). A significant ($P < 0.001$) decrease in the relaxant response of PAR2 was also observed in the ≥ 12-month tissue when stimulated with 10 μM FLIGRLO-NH₂ (27.7 ± 7.0 %) compared with the ≤ 4-month (63.8 ± 6.1 %). A similar trend can also be observed for the remaining concentrations of activating peptide used (Figure 5.1, Panel A & B). The PAR2 specificity of FLIGRLO-NH₂ was confirmed by the lack of response to the scrambled peptide FOLIGRL-NH₂ in both the age groups (Figure 5.1, Panel C & D).

Figure 5.1 PAR2 agonist response in PAR2^{+/+} murine bronchi. Bronchial rings from ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month PAR2^{+/+} murine samples were dissected and mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Activation of PAR2 using a known PAR2 agonist FLIGRLO-NH₂ was then carried out in bronchi from both age groups (A) and representative myography traces (B), and response to PAR2 agonist scrambled peptide FOLIGRL-NH₂ (C) and representative myography traces (D). The stable levels of tension obtained before and during acetylcholine-mediated contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100 % respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using the one-way ANOVA and Bonferroni post hoc test; data are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=6), ***P* < 0.01 *cf.* 1 μM ≤ 4-month, ****P* < 0.001 *cf.* 10 μM ≤ 4-month.

PAR2 agonist in PAR2^{-/-} murine bronchi

To further investigate the impact of ageing on PAR2-mediated ASM functionality, bronchial rings from both age groups were examined using wire myography as above. This was performed in this murine model to further confirm that the relaxant response observed was mediated by PAR2. A dose response to a known PAR2 activating peptide (Figure 5.2, Panel A & B), FLIGRLO-NH₂, following pre-contraction with acetylcholine was performed. This demonstrates a virtual absence of the relaxant response in both age groups to FLIGRLO-NH₂.

Figure 5.2 PAR2 agonist in PAR2^{-/-} murine bronchi. Bronchial rings from ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month PAR2^{-/-} murine samples were dissected and mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Activation of PAR2 using a known PAR2 agonist FLIGRLO-NH₂ was then carried out in the ≥ 12-month PAR2^{-/-} bronchi compared with matching bronchi from ≤ 4-month samples (A) and representative traces (B). The stable levels of tension obtained before and during acetylcholine-mediated contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100 % respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using the one-way ANOVA and Bonferroni post hoc test; data are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=7).

Trypsin response in murine bronchi

This section of the study focused on a different aspect of PAR2 activation – involving protease cleavage of the receptor. Again, bronchial rings from PAR2^{-/-} and PAR2^{+/+} mice at two defined age ranges were examined using *ex vivo* wire myography. The use of PAR2^{-/-} tissue enabled the PAR2 specificity of the trypsin to be confirmed. Trypsin addition to Acetylcholine-precontracted bronchi resulted in a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) of the relaxant response of PAR2 in PAR2^{+/+} (67.7 ± 9.1 %) (Figure 5.3, Panel A & B) compared to PAR2^{-/-} tissue from the ≤ 4-month mice (1.4 ± 0.6 %). A significant decrease ($P < 0.01$) was also observed in the ≥ 12-month PAR2^{-/-} tissue (2.5 ± 0.6 %) compared with the ≥ 12-month PAR2^{+/+} tissue (56.3 ± 8.9 %) (Figure 5.3, Panel C & D). The response to trypsin in the PAR2^{+/+} tissue between the ≤ 4-month (67.7 ± 9.1 %) and the ≥ 12-month (56.3 ± 8.9 %) was not significantly different ($P = 0.1$).

Figure 5.3 Trypsin response in murine bronchi. Bronchial rings from ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month $PAR2^{+/+}$ ($n=6$) and ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month $PAR2^{-/-}$ murine samples ($n=7$) were dissected and mounted to a 4 channel myograph. Activation of PAR2 was then performed using a known PAR2 agonist trypsin in ≤ 4 -month $PAR2^{-/-}$ bronchi compared with matching bronchi from ≤ 4 -month $PAR2^{+/+}$ samples (A) and representative images (B). The response to PAR2 activation was also performed in ≥ 12 -month $PAR2^{-/-}$ bronchi compared with matching bronchi from ≥ 12 -month $PAR2^{+/+}$ samples (C) and representative images (D). The stable levels of tension obtained before and during acetylcholine-mediated contraction were assigned values of 0 and 100 % respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using the one-way ANOVA and Bonferroni post hoc test; data are presented as the mean \pm SEM, $**P < 0.01$ cf. $PAR2^{+/+}$, $***P < 0.001$ cf. $PAR2^{+/+}$.

5.5.2 PAR2 expression in murine tissue

To investigate the potential mechanisms leading to the remodelling lung architecture and the loss of functionality observed in the *ex vivo* methods performed using wire myography, the expression of PAR2 was examined via immunohistochemistry and analysed using TissueGnostics Strataquest. Firstly, within each sample stained with the APR-32 Alomone PAR2 antibody, 6 ROIs were selected throughout the stained sections for each tissue type and 6 ROIs stained with the isotype were also selected as the negative control. The average mean intensity was measured using reference shades which correlate to the DAB staining of the PAR2 marker used within each ROI. The results were presented as mean \pm SEM Arbitrary units from the number of experiments carried out. Statistical comparisons were made using a one-way ANOVA and selected Bonferroni post-hoc test.

PAR2 expression in the parenchymal tissue revealed no significant difference ($P = 0.8$) in PAR2 expression in the ≥ 12 -month (34.8 ± 5.2 arbitrary units) compared with the ≤ 4 -month (35.3 ± 5.6 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.4, B). The PAR2 staining observed in the parenchymal tissue appears to be present in both type I (red arrows) and II (green arrows) pneumocytes within the two sample groups. The isotypes for the parenchyma are included as inset images in Figure 5.4, Panel A.

Figure 5.4 PAR2 expression in murine parenchymal tissue. Lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month samples, processed and then cut into sections. PAR2 expression was stained using Alomone (APR-32) PAR2 antibody in ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month parenchyma (A), quantified average mean intensity (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images had isotypes included as inset images (A). All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=6).

Despite no difference in the parenchymal tissue, a significant change was observed in the airways showing a decrease ($P < 0.01$) in PAR2 expression in the ≥ 12-month samples (32.4 ± 4.3 arbitrary units) compared with the ≤ 4-month (38.5 ± 7.1 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.5, B). The staining of the receptor observed in the airways was predominantly in the airway smooth muscle (orange arrows) with a clear decrease in staining in the smooth muscle of the older age group. Compared to this, there was a less staining in the epithelial layer of the airways (blue arrows) in the ≤ 4-month group; no epithelial staining was detected in the ≥ 12-month age group. The isotypes for the airway analysis can be seen in Figure 5.5, Panel A as inset images.

Airways

Figure 5.5 PAR2 expression in murine airways. Lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month samples, processed and then cut into sections. PAR2 expression was stained using Alomone (APR-32) PAR2 antibody in ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month airways (A), quantified average mean intensity (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images had isotypes included as inset images (A). All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM (n=6) ***P* < 0.01.

As seen previously in the airways, a significant decrease (*P* < 0.001) in PAR2 expression was observed in the older group (25.6 ± 3.9 arbitrary units) of the arterioles compared with young samples (37.4 ± 8.2 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.6, B). The expression of PAR2 in the arterioles can be seen in both the endothelium (purple arrows) and the vascular smooth muscle (yellow arrows), with a decrease the expression of the receptor in both cell types of the older age group. The expression of the receptor in both cell types of the older age group. The isotypes for the airway analysis are included in Figure 5.6, Panel A as inset images. To summarise, Figures 5.5 and 5.6 show that PAR2 expression in ≥ 12-month adult murine airways and arterioles was significantly decreased compared with the ≤ 4-month adult counterparts.

Figure 5.6 PAR2 expression in murine arterioles. Lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month samples, processed and then cut into sections. PAR2 expression was stained using Alomone (APR-32) PAR2 antibody in ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month arterioles (A), quantified average mean intensity (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images had isotypes shown as inset images (A). All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using One way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM (n=6) *** $P < 0.001$.

5.5.3 Smooth muscle actin expression in murine tissue

To further examine the remodelling lung architecture of an aged lung as seen in COPD, the expression of smooth muscle was examined using a smooth muscle actin antibody from Santa Cruz (sc-53142) and analysed using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. Statistical comparisons were made as above in the PAR2 analysis.

In the airway analysis, there was a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in smooth muscle actin expression observed in the PAR2^{+/+} tissue of the ≥ 12 -month group (70.1 ± 13.8 arbitrary units) compared with the ≤ 4 -month samples (75.0 ± 30.6 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.7, B). In the PAR2^{-/-} airways, a significant increase ($P < 0.01$) was detected in the older mice (49.4 ± 4.2 arbitrary units) compared with the younger (42.5 ± 5.0 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.7, B). In the comparison between the two genotypes of the ≤ 4 -month samples, a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in smooth muscle actin expression was found between the PAR2^{-/-} samples (42.5 ± 5.0 arbitrary units) and the PAR2^{+/+} samples (75.0 ± 30.6 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.7, B). Finally, in the ≥ 12 -month comparison between the two genotypes, a significant decrease ($P = <0.001$) was observed between the PAR2^{+/+} samples (70.1 ± 13.8 arbitrary units) and the PAR2^{-/-} samples (49.4 ± 4.2 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.7, B). The staining of smooth muscle actin (red arrows) was most evident within the PAR2^{+/+} ≥ 12 -month samples, with this level of expression being reduced in the absence of PAR2 at both age groups. This result indicates, that in the presence of PAR2 and increasing age, the smooth muscle tissue is more abundant. The isotypes for the airway analysis of smooth muscle actin can be seen in Figure 5.7, Panel A as inset images.

Airways

Figure 5.7 Smooth muscle actin expression in murine airways. Lung tissue was dissected from both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month samples, processed and then cut into sections. Smooth muscle actin expression was stained in airways of ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month PAR2^{+/+} (n=6) samples and ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month PAR2^{-/-} (n=7) samples-stained Santa Cruz (sc-53142) smooth muscle actin antibody and quantified average mean intensity of smooth muscle actin (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images had isotypes included as inset images (A). All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM; * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

There was a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in smooth muscle actin expression observed in the PAR2^{+/+} arterioles of the ≥ 12 -month (72.6 ± 8.8 arbitrary units) compared with the ≤ 4 -month samples (92.9 ± 37.9 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.8, B). Within the PAR2^{-/-} arterioles a significant increase ($P < 0.001$) was found in smooth muscle actin expression in the ≥ 12 -month (58.0 ± 3.4 arbitrary units) compared with the ≤ 4 -month samples 51.41 ± 6.26 arbitrary units (Figure 5.8, B). Comparing the genotypes of the ≤ 4 -month samples a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) was found between the PAR2^{-/-} (51.4 ± 6.2 arbitrary units) versus the PAR2^{+/+} samples 72.61 ± 8.83 arbitrary units (Figure 5.8, B). Similarly, for the genotype groups of the ≥ 12 -month samples, a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) was observed when comparing the PAR2^{+/+} (72.6 ± 8.8 arbitrary units) with the PAR2^{-/-} mice (58.0 ± 3.4 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.8, B). The expression of smooth muscle actin was similar to the airways with the highest levels of the staining being in the PAR2^{+/+} samples.

The isotypes for the arterioles analysis of smooth muscle actin can be seen in Figure 5.8, Panel A as inset images. To summarise, Figures 5.7 and 5.8 show a significant decrease in smooth muscle actin expression in the airways and arterioles of the ≥ 12 -month compared with the ≤ 4 -month PAR2^{+/+} samples. Smooth muscle actin expression was significantly increased in the older group of the PAR2^{-/-} tissues compared with the young. The expression of the smooth muscle (red arrows) is higher in the ≤ 4 -month compared with the ≥ 12 -month group of the PAR2^{+/+} samples. This observation was the opposite in the PAR2^{-/-} tissue with a higher level of expression being seen in the older tissue. Finally, an overall significant decrease in smooth muscle actin expression was apparent in the PAR2^{-/-} genotype compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples as seen in the airways. Again, this suggests that in the presence of PAR2, the abundance of smooth muscle is increased.

Figure 5.8 Smooth muscle actin expression in murine arterioles. Lung tissue was dissected from both PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month samples, processed and then cut into sections. Smooth muscle actin expression was stained in arterioles of ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month PAR2^{+/+} (n=6) samples and ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month PAR2^{-/-} (n=7) samples-stained Santa Cruz (sc-53142) smooth muscle actin antibody and quantified average mean intensity of smooth muscle actin (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images had isotypes included as inset images (A). All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM; **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001.

5.5.4 Collagen expression in murine tissue

To investigate the impact of age-related changes the collagen content within the lung, the expression was examined using Abcam Masson's Trichrome Stain Aniline blue (ab150686) and analysed using TissueGnostics Strataquest software and statistically analysed as described above. Within the Masson's Trichrome stain, the use of phosphotungstic and phosphomolybdic acid during the protocol enables a specific binding to the anionic NH₃⁺ groups of the collagens at low pH, as pH few proteins remain acidic at low pH. The retained phototungstic and phosphomolybdic acids then bind to Aniline blue cationic radicals allowing a specific binding to collagen (Rieppo *et al.*, 2019).

Analysis of the parenchyma in PAR2^{+/+} tissue, revealed a significant increase (*P* < 0.001) in Aniline blue expression was observed in the ≥ 12-month tissue (17.3 ± 1.4 arbitrary units) compared with the ≤ 4-month samples (13.8 ± 1.0 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.9, B). A significant decrease (*P* < 0.001) in Aniline blue expression was also observed in the PAR2^{-/-} tissue (7.5 ± 1.7 arbitrary units) compared with the PAR2^{+/+} tissue (13.8 ± 1.0 arbitrary units) of the ≤ 4-month samples (Figure 5.9, B). In the ≥ 12-month samples a significant increase (*P* < 0.001) was discovered in the PAR2^{-/-} parenchymal tissue (8.5 ± 1.6 arbitrary units) compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples (17.3 ± 1.4 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.9, B). No significant change (*P* = 0.5) was observed in the ≤ 4-month (7.5 ± 1.7 arbitrary units) compared with the ≥ 12-month PAR2^{-/-} parenchymal tissue (8.5 ± 1.6 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.9, B).

Figure 5.9 Collagen expression in murine parenchymal tissue. Lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month samples, processed and then cut into sections. Collagen expression was stained using Abcam Masson's Trichrome stain (Aniline Blue) (ab150686) in ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month PAR2^{+/+} (n=6) parenchyma and ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month PAR2^{-/-} (n=7) parenchyma (A), quantified average mean intensity of collagen (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM; *** $P < 0.001$. These experiments were performed in collaboration with Kirsty McCallum.

Analysis of the airways revealed a significant increase ($P < 0.001$) in Aniline blue expression between the ≥ 12 -month (16.6 ± 2.3 arbitrary units) and the ≤ 4 -month PAR2^{+/+} airways (11.3 ± 1.3 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.10, B). Similarly, in the PAR2^{-/-} airways a highly significant increase ($P < 0.01$) was found when comparing the ≥ 12 -month (8.3 ± 0.7 arbitrary units) with the ≤ 4 -month (5.9 ± 0.4 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.10, B). When comparing genotypes of the ≤ 4 -month groups, a significant decrease (P

< 0.001) in expression was detected between the PAR2^{-/-} (5.9 ± 0.4 arbitrary units) compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples (11.3 ± 1.3 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.10, B). Finally, in the ≥ 12-month airways, a highly significant decrease (*P* < 0.001) was also observed in the PAR2^{-/-} (8.3 ± 0.7 arbitrary units) compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples (16.6 ± 2.3 arbitrary units) (Figure 5.10, B).

Figure 5.10 Collagen expression murine airways. Lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month samples, processed and then cut into sections. Collagen expression was stained using Abcam Masson's Trichrome stain (Aniline Blue) (ab150686) in ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month PAR2^{+/+} (n=6) airways and ≤ 4-month and ≥ 12-month PAR2^{-/-} (n=7) airways (A), quantified average mean intensity of collagen (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean ± SEM; ***P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001. These experiments performed in collaboration with Kirsty McCallum.

Analysis of the arterioles revealed a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in Aniline blue expression between the PAR2^{-/-} samples (10.5 ± 1.3 arbitrary units) compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples (18.6 ± 3.7 Arbitrary units) in the ≤ 4 -month groups (Figure 5.11, B). Similarly, a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in Aniline blue expression was also observed between the arterioles of the PAR2^{-/-} (11.5 ± 1.2 Arbitrary units) compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples (18.6 ± 2.4 arbitrary units) of the ≥ 12 -month groups (Figure 5.11, B). To summarise, Figures 5.9, 5.10 and 5.11 show a significant increase in collagen expression in the parenchyma and airways of the older group compared with the young in the PAR2^{+/+}. A significant reduction in collagen expression was also found in both age groups of the PAR2^{-/-} samples in the parenchyma, airways and arterioles when compared with the PAR2^{+/+} samples.

Figure 5.11 Collagen expression in murine arterioles. Lung tissue was dissected from PAR2^{+/+} and PAR2^{-/-} ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month samples, processed and then cut into sections. Collagen expression was stained using Abcam Masson's Trichrome stain (Aniline Blue) (ab150686) in ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month PAR2^{+/+} (n=6) arterioles and ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month PAR2^{-/-} (n=7) arterioles (A), quantified average mean intensity of collagen (B) using TissueGnostics Strataquest software. All images were taken using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images captured using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using one way ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad Software) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM; *** $P < 0.001$.

5.6 Discussion

This study hypothesised that ageing has an impact on PAR2 function and expression in the mouse lung. The novel data presented here supports the potential value of this receptor as a therapeutic target in respiratory diseases such as COPD.

Linked parallel studies on tissue derived from the same mice were by my BREATH colleague, Kirsty McCallum. These detected a significant increase in known ageing markers such as P53 and P16 comparing older tissue with young (personal communication), demonstrating there was a quantifiable age-related difference between the ≤ 4 -month and ≥ 12 -month mice. This confirms the time period between the two time points chosen was of sufficient duration to allow measurable tissue ageing and thus enable investigation of age-related changes in PAR2, smooth muscle actin and collagen expression. A summary of the results provided within this chapter can be seen in table 5.2 below.

Tissue / experiment	WT: Old vs Young	KO: Old vs Young	Young: KO vs WT	Old: KO vs WT
BSM relaxation / FLIGRLO-NH ₂	↓	NSD	-	-
BSM relaxation / Trypsin	-	-	↓	↓
Parenchyma / PAR2 expression	NSD	-	-	-
Airway / PAR2 expression	↓	-	-	-
Arterioles / PAR2 expression	↓	-	-	-
Airway / SMA expression	↓	↑	↓	↓
Arterioles / SMA expression	↓	↑	↓	↓
Parenchyma / collagen expression	↑	Trend ↑	↓	↓
Airway / collagen expression	↑	↑	↓	↓
Arterioles / collagen expression	NSD	Trend ↑	↓	↓

Table 5.2 Summary of results and key findings throughout the investigation into age-dependent changes. Arrows indicate significant change; trend arrows indicate comparisons which did not attain significance. No significant difference is indicated by NSD and comparisons which were not made are represented by a dash.

A significant decrease in PAR2-dependent relaxation of ASM was observed in the ≥ 12 -month PAR2^{+/+} tissue compared with the ≤ 4 -month PAR2^{+/+} tissue. This suggests that with age, PAR2-mediated ASM relaxation is reduced. FLIGRLO-NH₂ selectivity for PAR2 was confirmed by comparing to the scrambled peptide sequence FOLIGRL-NH₂, which caused no response in the bronchial rings (Figure 5.1). The absence of response to the PAR2 agonist, FLIGRLO-NH₂, in PAR2^{-/-} bronchial rings further confirmed the agonist response observed in the wild-type mice was PAR2-dependent (Figure 5.2). The process of ageing has been reported by others to affect the function and the overall structure of the airways and respiratory muscles which results in changes of respiratory flow, a decrease in lung volume and an overall increase in residual volume (Occhipinti *et al.*, 2017). These features all appear progressively with age and could explain at least in part the changes in PAR2-dependent relaxation across the time period studied. At present the only reports of age-dependent changes in PAR2 response was in rat aortic rings (Maruyama *et al.*, 2017). Within this study, the rings were stimulated with both FLIGRLO-NH₂ and also trypsin, and reported that at 20 weeks the PAR2 response was sustained but at 30 weeks the response was lessened (Maruyama *et al.*, 2017). This study revealed that even at an age

of 7.5 months (30 weeks) there is a change in the functional response to PAR2 activation in rat endothelium with age. These findings are thus consistent with the present study on BSM in showing the response to PAR2 stimulation was lessened with age, demonstrating that similar age-related changes in smooth muscle extend across bronchial and vascular compartments – arguing for possibly a common ageing phenomenon in pulmonary smooth muscle tissue. This may have important broader implications to smooth muscle physiology across the body.

The PAR2-mediated BSM response was investigated by comparing WT versus PAR2 knockout mice at both time points. Comparing trypsin to agonist responses also enabled both PAR2 endogenous (protease-cleave) activation and exogenous (agonist) activation to be investigated. The PAR2^{-/-} tissue again was used to confirm the PAR2 specificity of trypsin, ensuring any responses observed were not due to off-target effects in the tissue interrogated. The response to trypsin in the PAR2^{-/-} tissue was abolished confirming that trypsin was mediating the relaxation through PAR2 (Figure 5.3). The response to trypsin did not differ with age in PAR2^{+/+} bronchial rings, although was significantly decreased with age when utilising the PAR2 activating peptide (Figure 5.1), suggesting a tendency for age-related decrease in the PAR2-dependent relaxation. This indicates that there are age-dependent changes in response to varying modes of activation. A study in human colorectal cells identified a difference in calcium signalling depending on the mode of activation of PAR2. The PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂ was found to cause an elevated level of fluorescence excitation ratio compared with trypsin-like protease kallikrein 14, indicates the importance of comparing responses to differing modes of PAR2 activation (Gratio *et al.*, 2011).

Parenchymal PAR2 expression did not differ between the two time points studied (Figure, 5.4), whereas the airway expression was significantly decreased in the older mice (Figure 5.5). Similarly in the arterioles, PAR2 expression was significantly decreased with age. The reduction in BSM expression levels observed may well explain mechanistically why there is a reduction of bronchodilator response to PAR2 activation in the functional airway studies. The reduction of PAR2 expression in the murine lung with age has not previously been reported, and this potentially important finding supports further research to elucidate the underlying mechanisms and establish the pulmonary consequence of such changes. PAR2 expression in the arterioles was significantly decreased in the older mice (Figure 5.6); this is supported by a study (Maruyama *et al.*, 2017) which found a reduction in PAR2 expression on vascular endothelium from aged rat aortas. Further findings from this study also supported an age-related decrease in PAR2-dependent vasodilation.

The significantly decreased expression of smooth muscle actin with age in both the airways and the arterioles of the PAR2^{+/+} group (Figure 5.6 & 5.7) contrasted with the PAR2^{-/-} group, where a significant increase in smooth muscle actin expression was observed with age (Figure 5.7). This reversal of the age-dependent decrease in smooth muscle actin expression in the absence of PAR2 identifies a role for PAR2 in mediating age-dependent loss of smooth muscle actin. Sarcopenia, a condition which involves loss of skeletal muscle mass, quality and strength, is often observed in elderly humans (Limpawattana *et al.*, 2018). Various biomechanical processes including reduction in proliferation, decreased muscle protein synthesis and an increase in oxidative stress have all been suggested as possible causes (Powers *et al.*, 2016). It also has been noted that proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, IL-1 β and TNF- α may play a role in age-related muscle loss (Dalle, Rossmeislova and Koppo, 2017). A link between PAR2 and proinflammatory cytokines has previously been reported in a study highlighting the impact of PAR2 antagonism on reducing cytokine secretion (Vesey *et al.*, 2013; Bailo *et al.*, 2020). This may relate to and explain the decrease in smooth muscle actin expression with age observed in the PAR2^{+/+} lung tissue. Interestingly, however, an increase in the smooth muscle layer is commonly reported in COPD patients, typically associated with concomitant airflow obstruction (Chung, 2005; Bidan *et al.*, 2015; Jones *et al.*, 2016). A study carried out in human samples investigating the impact of ageing in asthma patients also found an increase of the smooth muscle layer in the ‘old’ group of their study compared with the ‘young’ group (Bai *et al.*, 2000). The fact these findings differ from what we report here in the older mouse lung indicates that the ASM hypertrophy seen in asthma reverses what would more typically have been an age-related reduction in the smooth muscle layer. This opens the intriguing possibility that while PAR2 inhibition might reduce age-related reduction in ASM, such inhibitors

might also present a therapeutic approach in inhibiting ASM hypertrophy, and the concomitant increased airway resistance associated with lung pathology. This signposts the need to extend our studies in normal mice to murine COPD models to investigate the nature of smooth muscle changes in COPD. Such further research could then define the nature of the impact of ageing on smooth muscle change contributing to the pathogenesis of COPD.

The significantly decreased expression of collagen in all PAR2^{-/-} lung tissue types at both time points argues for a role for PAR2 in lung remodelling. Lung function is known to decline with age, which subsequently results in poorer mucociliary clearance, loss of elastic recoil, and poorer lung function (Sharma and Goodwin, 2006). In the parenchyma, the expression of collagen significantly increased with age; similarly, an age-related increase in collagen was found in the airways both in the presence and absence of PAR2. As collagen is a key component in the extracellular matrix of the lung and is commonly associated with loss of elastic recoil, a pathological feature of COPD, this makes lung collagen content a key factor in lung pathology (Bidan *et al.*, 2015). A study in rats investigated the impact of ageing on collagen content in rats at various time points. Within this study, a 28-fold increase in collagen content was observed from the 0.5-month to the 32-month groups (Mays, McAnulty and Laurent, 1989). Through the process of chronological ageing, type I collagen typically undergoes post-translational changes such as glycosylation, which results in the formation of advanced glycation end-product (AGE). This subsequently leads to an increase in collagen cross-links (Monnier *et al.*, 2005). The findings in these studies are relevant due to the change in collagen being linked with age-related changes detected using Masson's Trichrome stain. Collagen type I is most likely to be stained with Masson's Trichrome stain in the lung and thus the age-related changes observed parallel the study by Last *et al.*, 1983. The changes in vascular smooth muscle (VSM) suggests that age-related changes in the lung are a general change to all tissue types within this setting and not specific to airway smooth muscle.

While the studies presented in this chapter provide insight into lung ageing, the following limitations are recognized. Firstly, the age range of the ≥ 12 -month samples technically classed as between middle-aged (10-14 months) and aged (18-24 months) according to the Jackson Laboratory (Hagan, 2017). Nevertheless, the significant increase in known markers of ageing, P53 and P16, found by Kirsty McCallum in lung tissue from the same mice used in this chapter, evidenced discernable age-dependent changes over the time window reported in the present study. To further enhance the study an elder group of 18 months onwards could be utilised as an additional sample group as this age range is commonly accepted as 'old' mice. Unfortunately, this was beyond the scope of the present study due to Home Office restrictions on the period these mice could be maintained. Another limitation includes the usage of only bronchial rings in the functional studies which only allowed an insight into PAR2-mediated response in the bronchi. Extending the study to have included tracheal rings would have allowed for a more comprehensive analysis of the airway response to PAR2 activation, particularly in determining if there were differential PAR-mediated responses between these two levels of the respiratory tree, or if the pattern of bronchial response was reflective of the entire airway. In addition to extending the studies to include tracheal tissue, the difference in collagen deposition between the samples within the study could be further investigated histologically using a more collagen specific stain, for example Picrosirius red stain. This stain would support histological visualization of collagen type I and collagen type III fibres, thus enabling differentiation between specific types, compared with the current stain used which visualizes collagenous connective tissue fibres.

5.7 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study presents data that suggests ageing has an impact on PAR2 function in murine airways. The key conclusion is that reduction in airway PAR2 expression with age likely explains the reduced bronchodilator response to exogenous (and possibly endogenous) PAR2 activation – which collectively suggests the bronchoprotective role for PAR2 in normal mice declines with age. This provides scope to further investigate the impact of ageing on the role of PAR2 in the lung. Furthermore, the PAR2 knockout mice studies presented here allowed characterisation of PAR2 influences on airway remodelling in terms of changes in both SMA and collagen expression across the age range studied, and further showed such changes were reflected also in the pulmonary vasculature. Thus, given the

role PAR2 plays in bronchodilation, hypersensitivity and ASM hypertrophy, this receptor potentially represents an important new therapeutic target in lung disease such as COPD and asthma –signposting the need for future research in models of relevant lung pathologies.

Chapter 6:
**Murine collagen induced
arthritis (CIA) as a disease
model to understand lung
pathology in rheumatoid
arthritis and potential
implications for COPD**

6. Murine collagen induced arthritis (CIA) as a disease model to understand lung pathology in rheumatoid arthritis and potential implications for COPD

6.1 Introduction

Although recently developed *in vivo* rodent models are increasingly used to investigate pathological processes in COPD, none fully recapitulate all features nor inherent heterogeneity of human disease. Thus, there is no accepted ‘gold standard’ preclinical model and a plethora of different exposures (cigarette smoke, proteases, air pollutants) are used at diverse dose and duration to model specific features or disease stage (Jones *et al.*, 2017). This represents a limitation within the research field of respiratory disease and thus further model development is required to allow for a more in depth understanding of the disease. A disease which is of particular interest in relation to its co-incidence with COPD is rheumatoid arthritis (RA). A review by Gamble (2007) has demonstrated a link between COPD and inflammation, which provides further evidence that chronic inflammatory conditions such as RA, predispose to COPD (Gamble *et al.*, 2007; Ma *et al.*, 2019; Jung *et al.*, 2021). Although joint disease is the main presenter in RA, there are a number of extra-articular manifestations which include inflammatory lung disease. The two diseases may be associated due to inflammation and increased protease load and thus pro-inflammatory receptors such as PAR2 may be of interest, due to its potential to drive pathology of both joints and lung. This receptor specifically is of relevance due to the reported amelioration of joint damage by PAR2 blockade in this model (Huang *et al.*, 2019; McIntosh *et al.*, 2020).

In common with COPD, airway involvement has also been reported in RA-associated lung pathology, which includes changes to both upper and distal small airways (McGuire *et al.*, 2019). The common manifestations reported include bronchiectasis and excess sputum production, bronchiolitis and airway hyperreactivity (Yunt & Solomon, 2015). In patients with RA, emphysema is thought to develop subsequent to the initiation of destructive airway disease (Jacob *et al.*, 2018). The causes and mechanisms which underly the high incidence of airway lesions remain unclear; the emphysematous lung lesions noted in RA may primarily be related to an airway-centred destruction process (Sakai, 2018). Other studies also suggest that the lung may play a part in the initiation of RA, rather than being a secondary target of autoimmunity or other processes (Demoruelle *et al.*, 2014; Catrina *et al.*, 2017), this initiation perhaps being due to gene and environmental interactions at the mucosal surface of the lung. For example the airways may be a location of initiation of autoimmunity in RA, while the parenchyma may be a target of circulating autoimmune factors leading to nodules, a feature of interstitial lung disease (ILD) (Rangel-Moreno *et al.*, 2006). Collagen induced arthritis (CIA) is a pre-clinical inflammatory arthritis model that has become the accepted gold standard model for RA (Brand *et al.*, 2007), with potential to explore common mechanisms underlying the noted co-morbidity between COPD and RA (Gergianaki and Tsiligianni, 2019). The purpose of this study was therefore to begin to investigate if the CIA model faithfully reproduces RA changes in the lung, not just those in the joint, then to question if such mechanisms could be factors in development of COPD, at least in cases of RA co-morbidity.

6.2 Hypothesis

CIA represents a useful *in vivo* model of lung changes manifesting in RA, and could potentially help to gain insights into mechanisms underpinning development of COPD, particularly for those patients suffering RA co-morbidity.

6.3 Aims

The aim of this study were three-fold, 1) investigate lung morphometric parameters in murine CIA, 2) Assess biomarkers of disease pathology such as collagen levels, smooth muscle abundance, expression of neutrophil elastase and evaluate the expression of PAR2 in the lungs of CIA murine samples, compared with naïve.

6.4 Methods

The methods which were used to investigate airway and lung architecture following CIA are explained thoroughly in Chapter 2. Briefly, prior to the current work, the lung tissue used in this study was harvested from adult DBA/1 male mice, a total of 4 naïve samples and a further 4 which were subject to CIA as part of an unconnected study. The scoring system and the full protocol used for the generation of the CIA model can be found in section 2.3.2, to illustrate the provenance of the samples analysed herein. The sample information for the study can be found in Table 6.1.

Sample Name	Group	CIA Score
N_1	Naive	NS
N_2	Naive	NS
N_3	Naive	NS
N_4	Naive	NS
1_2	CIA	4
2_1	CIA	8
3_1	CIA	11
3_3	CIA	8

Table 6.1. CIA sample information. Sample information for the groups involved in the CIA study with relevant arthritic scores. NS: no score (Brand et al., 2007).

Immediately following termination, the lungs were dissected, fixed and then processed overnight via the use of the Thermo Scientific Excelsior AS tissue processor. The full tissue processing procedure is detailed in Section 2.7.1. Once processed the tissue sections were embedded in paraffin wax and 6 µm sections cut and incubated overnight onto slides. The slides were then stained using Masson's Trichrome stain (Section 2.7.5), in the first instance to analyse the overall lung structure. Samples were then subject to immunohistochemical staining for PAR2 (Section 2.7.6), to investigate the involvement of the receptor, followed by neutrophil elastase, for further mechanistic insight of any pathological changes observed. Slides were scanned using a Zeiss Axio Scanner Z.1 at 20 X magnification and analysed using Zen Blue software (Section 2.7.8) and TissueGnostics Strataquest software. The full details of the method used for analysis using Strataquest can be found in Section 2.7.9. Briefly, the software was used to analyse the average mean intensity and tissue density of various stains within each sample group. Multiple reference shades were selected for each stain and a standardised area for each ROI was selected depending on the tissue section being analysed. An exterior ring mask was used to detect stain present up to a radial distance of the exterior ring mask set for each identified cell. The region of interest area sizes, ring mask and reference shade information can be seen in Table 6.2.

Tissue type	ROI size (mm ²)	Exterior ring mask (µm)	Number of reference shades
Parenchyma	0.15	0.44	5
Airways	0.03	0.44	5
Arterioles	0.01	0.44	5

Table 6.2. Strataquest analysis sample information. The selected ROI standardised size used for analysis alongside the exterior ring mask size and number of reference shades identified are detailed within this table.

Within each sample stained with an antibody, 6 ROIs were selected throughout the stained sections for each tissue type. For samples stained with Masson's Trichrome 10 ROIs were selected using the standardised areas shown in Table 6.2. Analysis of the structural features of the lung pathology of the CIA model was performed using Zen Blue software. The analysis was performed through the selection of ten ROI with an area of almost 1600 µm² for each ROI, all including an alveolus. Total cells within each ROI were counted and three septal walls were measured (Figure 6.1), and an average taken. Results were analysed using the mean ± SEM from the number of experiments carried out and statistical comparisons were made using Student's unpaired t test.

Figure 6.1: Assessment method for lung alveolar morphometry and cell density in the murine CIA model. Murine samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed, and cut into sections before staining with Masson's Trichrome. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio Scanner Z.1 and analysed using Zen Blue software. Total cell count analysed within parenchymal tissue using standardised ROIs for both untreated-naïve control (A) and CIA samples (B) using haematoxylin-stained nuclei. Within the same standardized ROIs used for total cell count, alveolar septal width was also measured selecting three individual walls of the alveoli within the ROI. Representative images illustrating the alveolar septal wall analysis are shown for the naïve in panel (C) and the CIA in panel (D) (n= 4-3)

6.5 Results

6.5.1 Architectural changes to lung parenchymal tissue in CIA

The first phase of analysis looking at structural differences between the two sample groups showed a significant difference in lung architecture between the CIA and naïve lung. The first observation highlighted that the CIA parenchyma appeared less dense compared with that of the naïve parenchymal tissue (Figure 6.2, A, B) and the alveolar septal width also was significantly lower in the CIA samples; $3.50 \pm 0.18 \mu\text{m}$ compared with the naïve samples ($6.79 \pm 0.14 \mu\text{m}$) (Figure 6.2, C). The overall cell count/area was lower in the CIA samples, $9.13 \pm 0.03 \text{ cells/ROI}$ compared with the control $13.48 \pm 0.31 \text{ tissue}$ (Figure 6.2, D). To summarise, Figure 6.2 shows apparent changes in lung structural features, with a significant decrease in alveolar septal width and parenchymal cell density in the CIA samples compared with the untreated-naïve controls.

Figure 6.2: Impact of a CIA model on murine lung parenchymal architecture. Samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis (CIA) for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed, and cut into sections before staining with Masson's Trichrome. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio Scanner Z.1 to assess any difference between tissue density and architecture between naïve parenchyma (A) and CIA parenchyma (B). The analysis of alveolar septal width in both the untreated control and the CIA samples, within a standardized ROI is shown in panel (C). The total cell count, using haematoxylin-stained nuclei in naïve vs CIA within a standardized ROI (0.15 mm²) is shown in panel (D). Representative images selected from naïve (n=4) and CIA (n=3) samples. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's unpaired t test and the data are presented as mean ± SEM ****P* < 0.001.

6.5.2 Small airway thickness in naïve control and CIA lungs

Further analysis was carried out to investigate if remodelling of the small airways occurred in the CIA model using Zen Blue software. The analysis was performed through the selection of ten ROI with a standardised area for each ROI, including an airway within each ROI. The ROI size (0.039 mm²) precluded the analysis of large/major airways. Three measurements were taken from various points throughout the airway wall (Figure 6.3), and an average taken. The results from this investigation show that there is no significant difference between the CIA and naïve lung, however a trend can be observed between the groups meriting further analysis with an increase in sample group size. This trend (*P* = 0.08) suggests that the thickness of the airways of the CIA samples is larger $19.6 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ compared with that of the untreated naïve-control samples $16.8 \pm 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 6.3, Panel B, A respectively). The quantification of the airway wall analysis can be seen in Figure 6.3, C.

Figure 6.3: Airway wall thickness in naïve and CIA model. Mice were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed and cut into sections before staining with Masson's Trichrome. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio Scanner Z.1 and analysed using Zen Blue software. Airway measurements were taken from 3 separate points within an identified airway structure in both the naïve (A) and the CIA (B) samples, representative images shown. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's unpaired t test and the data are presented as mean \pm SEM (C).

6.5.3 Collagen content in CIA murine tissue

To investigate the potential mechanisms leading to the remodelling of lung architecture in the CIA model the collagen content within the tissue was assessed using Masson's Trichrome and analysed using TissueGnostics Strataquest. For the analysis of the average mean intensity using Strataquest, 10 ROIs were selected using the standardised areas shown in Table 6.2. In Masson's Trichrome stain, the use of phosphotungstic and phosphomolybdic acid during the protocol enables a specific binding to the anionic NH_3^+ groups of the collagens at low pH, as few proteins remain acidic at low pH. The retained phototungstic and phosphomolybdic acids then bind to Aniline Blue cationic radicals allowing a specific binding to collagen (Rieppo *et al.*, 2019). The pigment absorbance of specific wavelengths were detected and intensity quantified to measure the average mean intensity of the Aniline Blue staining and the results were presented as mean \pm SEM (arbitrary units) and statistical comparisons were made using Student's unpaired t test. In the parenchymal tissue, a significant increase was observed in the average mean intensity of Aniline Blue stain for collagen in the CIA (41.8 ± 0.4 arbitrary units; Figure 6.4, B) compared with naïve (31.3 ± 0.5 Arbitrary units (A), quantified in Figure 6.5, C) There was no change observed around the airways of the CIA compared to naïve samples (Figure 6.4, D, E & F) or surrounding the arterioles (Figure 6.4, G, H & I). To summarise, Figure 6.4 shows a significant increase in the collagen expression in the parenchymal tissue of the CIA samples compared with the untreated-naïve control. No change was detected in the collagen expression of the airways or the arterioles between the two groups.

Figure 6.4: Relative quantification of collagen in naïve and CIA model lung tissues. Murine samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed and cut into sections before staining. Collagen was stained in naïve and CIA samples using Masson's Trichrome and Aniline Blue quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (histograms) in parenchyma (A-C), airways (D-F) and arterioles (G-I). All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images shown. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's unpaired t test with naïve (n=4) and CIA (n=3) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM *** $P < 0.001$.

6.5.4 Decreased smooth muscle abundance in CIA murine tissue

ASM is recognised to contribute to conditions including asthma and COPD via airway remodelling, hypersensitivity and hypercontractility (Fernandes *et al.*, 2004), ultimately resulting in narrowing of the airways, airflow obstruction and consequent shortness of breath. To investigate the role of smooth muscle in airway remodelling within the CIA model, the smooth muscle content was examined using Masson's Trichrome and analysed using TissueGnostics Strataquest. Smooth muscle staining using Masson's Trichrome (specifically Biebrich scarlet fuchsin stain) has been performed in other tissue types (Chang & Kessler, 2008, Muro *et al.*, 2021). Biebrich scarlet-acid fuchsin solution stains all acidophilic tissue elements such as muscle and collagen. Subsequent addition of phosphomolybdic/phosphotungstic acid is used as a decolouriser causing the Biebrich scarlet-acid fuchsin stain to diffuse out of the collagen fibres while leaving the muscle cells red (Rieppo *et al.*, 2019). The pigment absorbance of specific wavelengths were detected and intensity quantified to measure the average mean intensity of the Biebrich scarlet-acid fuchsin staining and the results were presented as mean \pm SEM (arbitrary units) and statistical comparisons were made using Student's unpaired t test. The analysis of the airways using this stain in combination with the Strataquest software indicated no significant changes between the CIA (Figure 6, B & D) and the naïve samples (Figure 6.5, A & C). However, a slight decrease ($P = 0.17$) was observed in smooth muscle in the CIA samples (51.1 ± 2.8 arbitrary units) compared with the naïve (56.2 ± 1.8 arbitrary units) (Figure 6.5, E). The results from analysis of the arterioles in the two sample groups indicated a significant decrease in smooth muscle in the arterioles of the CIA samples (35.7 ± 1.9 arbitrary units; Figure 6.5, G & I)

compared with the untreated-naïve control (42.7 ± 1.4 arbitrary units; Figure 6.5, F & H). However, in terms of the arterioles, although the statistical analysis revealed significance, it is questionable if such a modest difference would necessarily result in any biological significance (Figure 6.5, J). To summarise, Figure 6.5 shows a significant decrease in smooth muscle expression in the CIA arterioles compared with the untreated-naïve control, with a similar trend observed in the airways.

Figure 6.5: Quantification of smooth muscle in naïve and CIA model lungs. Murine samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed, and cut into sections before staining. Smooth muscle expression was stained using Masson's Trichrome (Biebrich Scarlet red fuchsin) in airways of naïve (A & higher magnification C) and CIA (B & higher magnification D) samples and absorbance of Biebrich Scarlet red fuchsin was used to provide an indicative measure of ASM (indicated by red arrowheads), quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (E). Arterioles of both naïve (F & higher magnification H) and CIA (G & higher magnification I) samples were also stained using Abcam Masson's Trichrome stain (Biebrich Scarlet red fuchsin) and quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (J). All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using the Student's unpaired t test and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM * $P < 0.05$ with naïve (n=4) and CIA (n=3).

6.5.5 Decreased PAR2 expression in CIA murine tissue

To investigate the impact of inflammatory mechanisms in the disease pathology of the CIA model the expression of PAR2 was examined via immunohistochemistry and analysed using both Zen Blue software and TissueGnostics Strataquest. The importance of PAR2 in CIA has been highlighted in a study showing that chronic arthritis is ablated in PAR2-deficient mice, highlighting the essential role for the receptor in chronic inflammation (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003). Firstly, analysis using Zen Blue used the selection of ten ROI with a standardised area. The Zen Blue method of analysis was only performed on the parenchymal ROIs, due to time limitations associated with manual cell counting quantification involved in the analysis with Zen Blue. Within ROI, total number of cells were counted alongside positive cells stained for PAR2 and a percentage of positive cells calculated. For the analysis using Strataquest, within each sample stained with an antibody, 6 ROIs were selected throughout the tissue sections. The results were analysed calculating the mean and SEM and statistical comparisons were made using an unpaired t test. Both methods of analysis were explored to give a more robust analysis, providing qualitatively different analyses; counting positive cells to gain a percentage of the total cells using Zen Blue, and a measure of stain intensity using the Strataquest software.

The results observed via analysis using Zen Blue software (Figure 6.6, C), show a significant decrease in PAR2 expression in the parenchyma of the CIA samples ($31.1 \pm 4.4\%$; Figure 6.6, B) compared with the untreated-naïve control ($45.7 \pm 2.2\%$; Figure 6.6, A). However, the results observed via analysis using Strataquest software (Figure 6.7) indicated that in the parenchymal tissue (Figure 6.7, C), there was no significant change in PAR2 expression intensity in the CIA (23.9 ± 0.8 arbitrary units; Figure 6.7, Panel B) compared with the untreated-naïve control (24.0 ± 0.4 arbitrary units; Figure 6.7, A). In the airways (Figure 6.7, F) there was a small but not significant ($P = 0.2$) decrease in PAR2 expression in the CIA samples (5.7 ± 0.5 arbitrary units; Figure 6.7, E) compared with naïve (7.4 ± 1.4 arbitrary units; Figure 6.7, D). Finally, there was a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in PAR2 expression in the arterioles (quantified in Figure 6.7, I) of the CIA samples (8.5 ± 0.8 arbitrary units; Figure 6.7, H) compared with the untreated-naïve control (11.3 ± 1.1 arbitrary units, Figure 6.7, G).

The expression of PAR2 in the parenchymal tissue appears to be located primarily in the type II pneumocytes, at the junctions of the alveolar walls. In both the airways and the arterioles, it appears that most of the expression is located in the smooth muscle layer surrounding the structures, with lower levels of expression in the epithelial layer. In the parenchymal tissue the expression was unchanged between the two groups, but in the airways and the arterioles, the level of epithelial staining is higher in the naïve compared with the CIA

To summarise, the results of the analyses were method dependent. Figure 6.7 shows a significant decrease in PAR2 expression in the CIA arterioles compared with the untreated-naïve control. The ZEN analysis (Figure 6.6) revealed a significant decrease in positively stained cells in the parenchyma of the CIA sample compared with control, but no change in stain intensity was detected when using Strataquest software (Figure 6.7).

Figure 6.6: Lung parenchymal PAR2 expression in murine CIA. Murine samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed and cut into sections before staining. Immunohistochemical analysis of PAR2 expression in murine parenchymal tissue with representative images (naïve, A & CIA, B) and isotype (rabbit IgG₁) shown as insets. Quantification of the cells positively stained for PAR2 using Zen Blue software in the CIA (n=3) vs naïve samples (n=4) (C). All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected using Zen Blue software. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's unpaired t test; data are presented as the mean \pm SEM * $P < 0.05$.

Figure 6.7: Relative quantification of lung PAR2 expression during CIA. Murine samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed, and cut into sections before staining. PAR2 expression was stained using APR-32 antibody in naïve (A) and CIA parenchyma (B), quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (C). Airways of naïve (D) and CIA (E) samples and quantification (F), and arterioles of naïve (G) and CIA (H) with quantification (I) were also stained for PAR2. Isotypes are shown as insets. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's unpaired t test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad) with naïve (n=4) and CIA (n=3) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM * $P < 0.05$.

6.5.6 Increased neutrophil elastase expression in CIA murine tissue

It is widely recognised that neutrophil invasion is a key factor in COPD development and so products of activated neutrophils, such as NE, are likely contributors to the destruction of ECM in airway walls and lung parenchymal tissue (Hoenderdos and Condliffe, 2013; Polosukhin *et al.*, 2021). However, other cell types will also contribute to the levels of NE in the lung such as smooth muscle cells (Dollery *et al.*, 2003). A predominance of neutrophils was noted in RA-ILD alongside increased populations of lymphocytes and eosinophils (Shaw *et al.*, 2015). Since PAR2 activation has been shown to be important in mediating joint pathology in RA and the CIA model (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003; Crilly *et al.*, 2016), and a known target of NE (Zhao *et al.*, 2015), it is plausible that this receptor might experience enhanced activation in tissues with enhanced expression of this key serine protease, and thus may contribute to this inflammatory state in disease (Zhao *et al.*, 2015). To further investigate the decrease in parenchymal tissue density observed in the CIA samples, NE expression was stained and quantified using both Zen Blue software and TissueGnostics Strataquest.

The results observed via analysis using Zen Blue software (Figure 6.8, C) show that there is a marked and significant increase in neutrophil elastase expression in the parenchyma of the CIA samples (50.2 ± 2.2 arbitrary units; Figure 6.8, B) compared with the untreated-naïve control (25.3 ± 1.4 arbitrary units; Figure 6.8, A). The results observed via analysis using Strataquest software for neutrophil elastase expression in the parenchyma (Figure 6.9, C), concur, showing a small but significant increase in expression in the CIA samples (35.1 ± 0.6 arbitrary units; Figure 6.9, B) compared with the untreated-naïve control (32.1 ± 0.8 arbitrary units; Figure 6.9, A). The airways showed similar results (Figure 6.9, F), with an increase in NE expression in the CIA (32.9 ± 0.5 arbitrary units; Figure 6.9, E) compared with the control (30.2 ± 1.0 arbitrary units; Figure 6.9, D). The arterioles exhibited similar results (Figure 6.9, I), showing an increase in NE in the CIA (33.3 ± 0.8 arbitrary units; Figure 6.9, H) compared with the naïve (30.6 ± 0.8 arbitrary units; Figure 6.9, G). Although significance was found in the analysis of the samples within the Strataquest study, perhaps due to the apparent small degree of error, the changes occurring are small, and the biological relevance of such modest differences in expression is unclear.

To summarise, the data show a significant increase in neutrophil elastase expression in all three tissues of the CIA samples compared with the untreated-naïve controls, with consistent results being produced using both ZEN (Figure 6.8) and Strataquest methods of analysis (Figure 6.9).

Figure 6.8: Neutrophil elastase expression in murine naïve and CIA lung parenchyma. Murine samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed, and cut into sections before staining and immunohistochemical analysis of NE expression in parenchymal tissue. Representative images of neutrophil elastase staining in naïve (A) & CIA (B), with isotype staining using rabbit IgG₁ shown inset. Quantification of the cells positively stained was carried out using Zen Blue software in the CIA (n=3) vs naïve (n=4) samples (C). Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's unpaired t test and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM (n=4-3) *** P < 0.001.

Figure 6.9: Relative quantification of lung NE expression in CIA. Murine samples were subject to collagen induced arthritis for a 28-day period before culling. Following cull, lung tissue was dissected, processed, and cut into sections before NE staining in naïve (A) and CIA parenchyma (B), quantified using TissueGnostics Strataquest software (C). Airways of naïve (D) and CIA (E), with quantification (F), and arterioles of both naïve (G) and CIA (H) with quantification (I) were also stained for NE. Isotypes shown as insets. All images were captured using Zeiss Axio scan Z.1 and representative images selected. Statistical analysis was carried out using Student's unpaired t test on Prism 7.0 (GraphPad) with naïve (n=4) and CIA (n=3) and the data are presented as the mean \pm SEM ** P < 0.01.

6.6 Discussion

This study has characterised structural features and key markers involved in remodelling and inflammation of the lungs in the CIA model of inflammatory arthritis, revealing differences in lung architecture and marker expression that merit further investigation. To date, the findings reported in this chapter have not been previously described in the existing literature. A summary of the results provided within this chapter can be seen in Table 6.3 below.

Tissue / experiment	Naive	CIA
Alveolar Septal Width	-	↓
Cell Count	-	↓
Airway Wall Thickness	-	NSD/↑
Parenchyma / collagen expression	-	↑
Airway / collagen expression	NSD	NSD
Arterioles / collagen expression	NSD	NSD
Airway / SM expression	-	NSD/↓
Arterioles / SM expression	-	↓
Parenchyma / PAR2 expression	NSD	NSD
Airway / PAR2 expression	NSD	NSD
Arterioles / PAR2 expression	-	↓
Parenchyma / NE expression	-	↑
Airway / NE expression	-	↑
Arterioles / NE expression	-	↑

Table 6.3 Summary of key findings. No significant difference (NSD).

Previous studies investigating lung histomorphology have utilised similar techniques compared to the current work. Analysis of either collapsed or inflated lung tissue are commonly used for histomorphometric analysis of the respiratory system, with stains such as haematoxylin and eosin and Masson's Trichrome both widely utilised to explore architectural differences (Wawryk-Gawda *et al.*, 2020). For example, a study exploring lung morphological changes post cigarette and electronic smoke exposure used Masson's Trichrome stain using collapsed lung tissue (Wawryk-Gawda *et al.*, 2020). Another study researching methods of lung histology, utilised perfusion, inflation and fixation of the tissue for post-fixation histological analysis (Davenport *et al.*, 2020).

CIA is a model of RA, which primarily affects the joints but can also affect the whole body and cause systemic inflammation (Teixeira *et al.*, 2019; Schnabolk, Obert, Banda, & Rohrer, 2021). It is plausible that this systemic inflammation could manifest in the airway and drive remodelling, leading to the thickening of the airway wall. One study quantified a range of chemokines and inflammatory cytokines to further investigate the systemic inflammatory impact of the CIA model. Specific pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-4, 5, 6, 12 and 17 were all significantly increased in CIA, highlighting the impact of the disease model to cause a systemic inflammatory profile similar to RA (Teixeira *et al.*, 2019).

Various structural changes were observed between the parenchymal tissue of the CIA and the naïve control, such as reduction in cellular density within the parenchymal tissue and decrease in alveolar wall thickness were observed in CIA. In COPD patients, a common pathophysiological feature is thickening of the airway walls causing obstruction of airflow (Polosukhin *et al.*, 2021). In the current study the airway walls of the small airways showed no significant difference. It has also been reported that patients with RA commonly experience disease of the airways, as a result of inflammation driving airways remodelling (Sakai, 2018, Mori *et al.*, 2018), whilst it is thought that the thickening observed in the airway walls of COPD patients is due to a combination of inflammatory changes and remodelling (Shantanam, 2018). It has also been proposed that inflammatory changes in the small airways may secondarily induce mucosal edema which subsequently leads to bronchial narrowing and obstruction of

the airways in COPD (Hassan *et al.*, 1994). Similar changes observed between COPD and lung changes in CIA could imply similar mechanisms are at play in disease pathology.

Type I collagen is the major structural element of the lung, comprising 50% of the extracellular matrix (Lang *et al.*, 1994). Given the architectural changes to the lung parenchymal tissue, such as alveolar wall breakdown and the increase in collagen content in the CIA samples compared with the naive, it can be suggested that changes in collagen content may play a role in the destruction of the lung tissue in disease pathology, alongside normal structural roles. The dysregulation of ECM can cause alteration in mechanical properties such as elastic recoil, as well as critical cellular functions such as proliferation, migration and differentiation (Herrera, Henke and Bitterman, 2018). There have been conflicting reports in the literature regarding the roles of collagen in the lung. Some workers have reported that in a transgenic mouse model the development of emphysema was associated with a loss of collagen (Foronjy and D'Armiento, 2001). However this study conflicted with earlier findings that collagen content was actually increased in septal regions of emphysematous patients (Cardoso *et al.*, 1993). This discrepancy may be explained by the fact that the remodelling of the extracellular matrix (ECM) is a dynamic process, and so the initial degradation of collagen is followed by imperfect repair, ultimately causing collagen deposition in the lung (Lucas, Yasa and Lucas, 2020). This finding was consistent with the increase in collagen content observed within the CIA samples of this study.

It could also be suggested that collagen deposition in and around specific alveoli could expose neighbouring alveoli to potentially harmful forces of expansion. If an alveolus in the earlier stage of emphysema is surrounded by alveoli that are in the repair phase, the effects could be exaggerated and even more harmful to bordering alveoli, creating a knock on effect leading to disease pathology (Foronjy and D'Armiento, 2001). In idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), repetitive lung injury repair mechanisms lead to an ongoing destruction of elastic parenchymal lung tissue, which subsequently is increasingly replaced by stiff scar tissue (Burgstaller *et al.*, 2017). In relation to COPD specifically, collagen-focused studies have demonstrated a significant increase in collagen abundance in alveoli of COPD patients displaying the phenotype of emphysema compared with the non-emphysematous samples (Vlahovic *et al.*, 1999, Martín-Mosquero *et al.*, 2006). Thus, it is interesting to speculate that the lung collagen changes observed in the current study may share underpinning mechanisms with COPD.

In terms of collagen deposition surrounding the airways, it has been reported that a decrease in total collagen in bronchioles of severe COPD patients, along with a decrease in type I/III collagen ratio, was associated with a decline in FEV₁ and less tissue surrounding the bronchioles and within the small airways, respectively (Hogg *et al.*, 2009). This suggested that the thickening of small airways could not be attributed to the expression of genes associated with fibrogenesis and causing the airway alteration (Annoni *et al.*, 2012). This study showed that alterations of major ECM components are widespread throughout major compartments of COPD patient's lungs. This modified ECM arrangement in COPD was suggested to be likely to contribute to the persistent tissue injury and may also present a role in the airflow obstruction in this disease (Annoni *et al.*, 2012). A comprehensive review of ECM change in COPD and the role of type I and III collagen as biomarkers for airway remodelling has provided further insight into the role of collagen (Ito *et al.*, 2019). Patients with COPD were found to have an increased expression of total collagens I, III, and IV in the basement membrane and an increased expression of collagens I and III in bronchial lamina propria and adventitia (Kranenburg *et al.*, 2006). It was also revealed by this study that COPD is associated with an increased deposition of ECM components in the bronchial airway, suggesting that this may contribute to airway remodelling and obstruction to airflow (Kranenburg *et al.*, 2006). This finding by Kranenburg showing an increase in collagen levels in COPD patients contradicts with the findings of Hogg who identified a decrease in collagen levels of the airways of COPD patients. It is also identified in the literature that ASMC proliferation is affected by ECM stiffness in the airways, resulting in the loss of smooth muscle in small and terminal airways of patients with emphysema (Niu, Liu and Fu, 2002). The ECM rigidity in respiratory disorders is increased by enzymatic covalent crosslinking of collagen and elastin (Burgstaller *et al.*, 2017). COPD lung presented higher collagen content and altered airway mechanics compared to normal lung, with lower dynamic

tissue elasticity as well as hyper resistance in a mouse model of emphysema (Ito *et al.*, 2005). No similar decrease in airway smooth muscle was observed during CIA in this present study.

In COPD airway smooth muscle specifically has been reported to have an increased mass compared with that of healthy counterparts (Yan *et al.*, 2018a). The airway remodelling and inflammation observed are considered as major factors which result in irreversible airflow limitation in COPD (Hogg *et al.*, 2004). In more specific terms the airway smooth muscle of COPD patients are often reported to be subject to hypertrophy and hyperplasia causing a thickening of the ASM (Hong *et al.*, 2017). Potential mechanistic changes in the CIA samples may represent very early disease compared to the COPD ASM manifestations and thus allude to the differences between COPD reports and sections of this study which highlighted no change in ASM of the CIA samples.

PAR2 is commonly associated with an inflammatory state within tissues and is well reported to be involved in the pathology of both OA and RA including roles in synovial hyperplasia, destruction of cartilage and pain (McCulloch *et al.*, 2018). Due to this, inhibiting PAR2 activation has been suggested as a potential target for treatment of both OA and RA (McCulloch *et al.*, 2018), both of which are established co-morbidities for COPD (Liu *et al.*, 2019). The slight in PAR2 expression observed in the CIA model was not anticipated due to the proinflammatory capabilities of the receptor and the systemic inflammation associated with the condition of RA-ILD (Shaw & Collins, *et al.*, 2015), in addition to the increased PAR2 expression reported in both RA and CIA (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003; Crilly *et al.*, 2016) (McCulloch *et al.*, 2018). A study investigating the expression of PAR2 in COPD patients and bronchial asthma patients also identified no significant changes in the expression of the receptor (Matěj *et al.*, 2014), indicating that perhaps despite an inflammatory environment in certain lung pathologies such as COPD and RA-ILD, the receptor expression is not significantly increased as hypothesised. However, activation of the receptor could be markedly enhanced by the elevated presence of cognate proteases such as NE. PAR2, although the expression is not increased in the parenchyma or the airway, the receptor could still have an involvement in remodelling through its association with systemic inflammation arising from the CIA protocol (Teixeira *et al.*, 2019). Despite PAR2 expression not showing a change, receptor activity may still be altered due to a different protease load. The imbalance of proteases and antiproteases in COPD is a common hallmark and contributes to the progression of the disease, as supported by evidence from both animal and human studies (Gadek & Pacht, 1990; Churg & Wright, 2005; Demedts *et al.*, 2006).

It is well known that neutrophil invasion is a key factor in COPD development and so products of activated neutrophils, such as NE, are likely contributors to the destruction of ECM in airway walls and lung parenchymal tissue (Hoenderdos and Condliffe, 2013; Polosukhin *et al.*, 2021). NE can cause considerable damage to tissue due to its ability to degrade many components of the ECM, including collagen, fibronectin, proteoglycans, heparin and cross-linked fibrin (Travis, 1988). The significant increase in NE expression within the CIA samples indicates a possible cause of the destruction of the parenchymal tissue in the CIA leading to the emphysema-like phenotype observed. Other proteolytic enzymes such as cathepsin G and proteinase 3 are thought to cause destruction of the alveolar-capillary cells and this has generally been accepted as one of the key principal mechanisms of destructive airspace enlargement (El-Zein *et al.*, 2003, Taraseviciene-Stewart & Voelkel, 2008). The proteolytic enzymes previously mentioned along with NE may also be disarming PAR2 proteases (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2011). The changes to the lung in RA-ILD are similar to that of emphysema due to the honeycomb-like destructive changes that are observed following inflammation (Sugitani *et al.*, 2018). The small airways also exhibit changes similar to COPD pathology; these changes include bronchial wall thickening causing airflow obstruction (Wilsher *et al.*, 2012).

The ability of NE to cause destruction to the ECM may help explain the architectural changes observed in the parenchymal tissue in CIA. Similarly, it has been reported that in collagen-related lung diseases such as RA-ILD, there are increased levels of neutrophil elastase (Sibille *et al.*, 1990). As COPD is often associated with neutrophilic inflammation, the secretion of NE from active neutrophils has been proposed to be a biomarker of COPD, particularly during bacterial infection (Thulborn *et al.*, 2019). It

has also been reported that increases of NE in COPD patients have been associated with exacerbations, a decline in lung function and also disease severity (Muhlebach *et al.*, 2016; Chalmers *et al.*, 2017).

The changes within this study highlight the potential to use the CIA murine model, as a model for not only arthritis but also for RA-associated lung disease. Further, the increase in NE observed indicates an increase in the neutrophilic lung population, which is likely to be accompanied by an increase in proinflammatory cytokines and other inflammatory cells in the lung (MacNee, 2007). Supported by the evidence of NE being expressed by other cells such as smooth muscle and macrophages (Dollery *et al.*, 2003).

CIA being the most commonly used model for RA, allows the use of a well-established model to explore similarities between RA-ILD and COPD. The results presented in this study highlight the similarities between RA-ILD and features of COPD in the context of architectural changes and this may inform underpinning mechanisms in COPD, especially in RA-COPD co-morbidity.

A significant difference in lung architecture between the CIA and naïve lung was observed, with the CIA lung having less cell density compared with that of the naïve and the overall cell count being lower in the CIA compared with the untreated-naïve control, suggesting that the CIA disease model is causing pathological changes in murine lung tissue similar to that noted within RA-ILD (Shaw & Collins, *et al.*, 2015). As mice are a suitable model to establish various disease models as already seen with the CIA model for RA, it can be said that they provide potential for COPD models due to the genetic compatibilities with humans, ease of breeding and their high survival rates within disease models (Yang *et al.*, 2021). The changes observed in the CIA samples compared with the naïve and the benefits discussed with murine models, provides scope for the use of the CIA murine model for the investigation of disease mechanisms in the lung. The emphysemous phenotype and decrease in alveolar septal width observed in the CIA samples are both modifications of the lung similarly observed in COPD patients (Sharafkhaneh, Hanania and Kim, 2008).

In terms of the modifications observed in the CIA lung, neutrophil elastase is commonly associated with the destruction of the alveolar tissue leading to emphysema (Chang *et al.*, 2016). From the data presented within this study, the increase in neutrophil elastase expression could be responsible for the architectural changes and alveolar destruction observed. This association with neutrophil elastase in CIA is relevant to COPD due to the disease often being linked to neutrophilic inflammation and the secretion of NE from active neutrophils in the lung is a proposed biomarker of COPD (Thulborn *et al.*, 2019).

There have been various reports, in both human and animal contexts, investigating the impact of neutrophil elastase inhibitors on lung injury and its potential therapeutic role (Polverino *et al.*, 2017). A number of NE inhibitors such as elafin and secretory leukocyte protease inhibitor are endogenously produced at sites of tissue injury or by the liver (by α 1-AT) and upregulated in response to inflammatory stimuli (Williams *et al.*, 2006). The anti-protease α 1-AT is an endogenous neutrophil elastase inhibitor mentioned previously in response to injury. The genetic disorder that is the basis of emphysematous COPD in around 5 % of cases (Brode, Ling and Chapman, 2012), known as α 1-AT deficiency, reduces the amount of neutrophil elastase inhibitors in the lung, and thus an overall increase in neutrophil elastase activity is observed (McCarthy, Reeves and McElvaney, 2016). Thus the potential for neutrophil elastase inhibitors as therapeutic targets in lung disease is a concept worth exploring further to combat lung destruction (Henriksen, 2014).

The apparent decrease of PAR2 observed in the arterioles of CIA samples could be due to a higher activation rate of PAR2 in the CIA tissue due to elevated NE levels, which subsequently results in internalisation and degradation of the receptor or by NE disarming PAR2. This possibly reflects activation and receptor turnover in the inflammatory model due to elevated serine protease activity, and increased neutrophil elastase levels observed throughout CIA lung tissue are consistent with this idea.

A current limitation of this study is the small sample group size, thus the findings reported here remain preliminary. The COVID-19 pandemic unfortunately curtailed further CIA experiments being performed, thus preventing further tissue access.

To further develop this study the ability to gain bronchial or tracheal tissue from CIA experiments for functional analysis would be beneficial in determining a difference in response to PAR2 activation. Characterisation of other physical properties such as compliance of the lung could provide further understanding of lung pathology in this model. Subsequently, utilising a PAR2-deficient mouse model that was subject to the CIA protocol, or administration of a PAR2 antagonist would also allow for a definitive understanding on the impact of systemic inflammation on the functionality of PAR2 in the airways and the role of PAR2 in this disease model (Huesa *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, a longer duration of the CIA protocol would allow a more comprehensive characterisation of the disease course in the lungs. However, this may present regulatory difficulties, as an extended duration would entail animal welfare considerations. A limitation of the study is the use of immunohistochemistry as a single quantitative measurement of surface protein expression. The quantification of the stains acts as a constraint as it is a subjective method and can be subject to bias analysis of the user. In order to more accurately understand the expression of the proteins, this could be done using another method of quantitative measurement known as western blot. To further enhance the histological results, the difference in collagen deposition between the samples within the study could be further investigated using a more collagen specific stain could be used, for example Picosirius red stain. This stain would allow histological visualisation of different size of collagen type I and collagen type III fibres. Further investigation into collagen content within these samples could be explored using collagen specific antibodies for example, anti-collagen I and anti-collagen III (Croxford *et al.*, 2013), to allow us to distinguish between specific collagen types in the lung. Other markers could also be explored to further characterise the disease in the lungs, for example macrophage elastase (MMP-12) and mast cell tryptase alongside other immune cell types such as mast cells and macrophages (Frungeri *et al.*, 2002; Guan *et al.*, 2019). The discovery and development of new potent and selective antagonists and agonists of PAR2 (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020) will help both clearly define the role of the receptor in a lung setting, as well as opening the door to acutely needed new therapeutic directions for conditions such as COPD. Ligand-induced biased signalling through G-protein coupled receptors including PAR2 is an area which offers great promise, through the potential to fine tune compounds to specifically modulate intracellular pathways associated with disease pathology, without affecting beneficial effects associated with the same receptor in normal physiology (Jiang *et al.*, 2017).

This study represents a preliminary characterisation of lung changes in the CIA murine preclinical RA model. A more detailed future characterisation will build on the current study to determine if this model can be used to better understand RA-associated lung pathology, and potentially to explore pathogenic mechanisms that may be relevant to the development of RA-COPD co-morbidity.

6.7 Conclusion

Histomorphometric signs of lung pathology, specifically a decrease in tissue density and a decrease in alveolar septal width were observed in CIA mice, consistent with the observed development of lung pathology in RA patients. Changes in smooth muscle and collagen, the major ECM component, add further detail to this picture of altered lung structure in CIA, though unclear currently if these changes accurately reflect features of RA-ILD. Increases in NE expression in CIA raises possibility that lung pathology in this model may share common underpinning mechanisms with COPD. Whilst the potential involvement of PAR2, an important downstream protease sensor key to inflammatory responses, remains unclear. These data indicate that further work would be valuable to confirm and extend current findings, and explore any common underpinning mechanisms shared with COPD. To understand if the CIA model might help illuminate mechanisms driving pathology, particularly in RA-COPD co-morbidity.

Chapter 7:

General Discussion

7 General Discussion

The main focus of this study was to investigate the role of PAR2 in airway smooth muscle at both a cellular and whole tissue setting. In short, the data produced within this thesis support the hypothesis of a protective role for PAR2, particularly in an airway context (Cocks & Moffatt, 2001).

In general, there are a lack of new and effective therapies for COPD. The work described herein suggests that PAR2 influence on bronchial tone could make it a potential target for therapeutic strategy if targeted correctly. Notably, this study has shown that the bronchorelaxation observed in response to PAR2 activation is modulated by COPD-relevant challenges such as ageing and oxidative stress. The increase in PAR2-dependent relaxation observed in the condition of oxidative stress is a key finding which highlights the therapeutic potential of targeting PAR2 to induce bronchial relaxation to alleviate disease symptoms. However, the potential negative impacts of PAR2 involvement, such as inflammation and hypertrophy, are factors to be considered when addressing the overall proposal of PAR2 as a therapeutic target (Nichols *et al.*, 2012). As inflammation is a key symptom involved in COPD, further prolonging this inflammatory state by targeting PAR2 could be detrimental in disease pathology. This could be further assessed through the use of PAR2-deficient cell cultures to understand if the receptor is having a modulatory role. Similarly, qPCR could be utilised to investigate the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines in PAR2-stimulated and deficient cells.

The study allowed characterisation of PAR2 in both human primary bronchial smooth muscle cells and isolated murine airways. The expression of PAR2 observed in the bronchial smooth muscle cells, supported by findings in the literature, confirm that PAR2 is present in the smooth muscle and merits further investigation on the role of the receptor in this cell type (Schmidlin *et al.*, 2001; Miotto *et al.*, 2002). PAR2 expression was previously reported in hBSMC, assessed through immunohistochemical staining of bronchial rings (Miotto *et al.*, 2002). Subcellular re-distribution of the receptor may also occur upon stimulation, as established by studies investigating trafficking of PAR2 using trypsin to activate the receptor (Déry *et al.*, 1999; Ayoub & Pin, 2013). Utilisation of confocal microscopy in future development of this work may facilitate such studies in hBSMC by helping visualise the receptor within the plasma membrane by resolving a narrower depth of focus (Smyth and Shaw, 2008; Castillo-Badillo, Cabrera-Wrooman and García-Sáinz, 2014).

It is well documented that PAR2 plays a role in modulating inflammation, and has been reported to be a key player in acute and chronic diseases which effect the joints such as rheumatoid arthritis (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003; Steven *et al.*, 2013) and osteoarthritis (Huesa *et al.*, 2016; McCulloch *et al.*, 2018). There have also been reports of PAR2 being involved in inflammatory conditions in the lungs such as asthma (Kim *et al.*, 2019), and thus investigation into potential pathogenic roles of the receptor in the context of COPD is merited. Multiple cytokines orchestrate an inflammatory response in airway diseases such as COPD through amplification of the response and the recruitment of inflammatory cells (Barnes, 2009).

To investigate a putative role for PAR2 in the context of bronchial smooth muscle cells in COPD, proinflammatory cytokine secretion (Barnes, 2018) from hBSMC was therefore studied. In this section of the study, PAR2 was not found to be involved substantially in the modulation of proinflammatory cytokines IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α secretion, though modulation of other COPD-relevant cytokines, or potential responses in cells derived from COPD patients, cannot be excluded. This lack of cytokine response to PAR2 activation in the bronchial smooth muscle may indicate distinct roles and interplay between the epithelial layer and smooth muscle in providing overall airway function. For instance, one previous study (not focused on PAR2) showed increased levels of IL-6 and IL-8 secretion in damaged airway epithelia (Chow *et al.*, 2010). A study in oesophageal epithelial cells revealed that the use of a PAR2 blocking antibody caused reduced IL-8 production in trypsin-stimulated cells, indicating PAR2-dependence (Yoshida *et al.*, 2007). An emerging study utilising both COPD and healthy bronchial epithelial cells highlighted an impact of PAR2 antagonism on reducing the levels of both IL-8 and IL-6 (Bailo *et al.*, 2020). The findings in this and the current study suggest that IL-8 secretion may not be

modulated by PAR2 directly in airway smooth muscle, yet PAR2-dependent inflammatory responses may nevertheless play an indirect role in smooth muscle modulation in a disease setting. This question could be addressed by performing myography experiments after denuding the epithelial layer, but also by future utilisation of tissue-specific cre-loxp KO models utilising either a smooth muscle actin promoter (Wu *et al.*, 2007) or an airway epithelial specific promoter to selectively delete PAR2 (Sinha and Lowell, 2017).

Diverse signaling outcomes of PAR2 activation can arise through cleavage of the receptor by different proteases. There is convincing evidence that activation of PAR2 by different proteases or in complex with other receptors provoke distinct signalling outcomes (Soh *et al.*, 2010). Selective cleavage by extracellular proteases enables PAR2 to act as a sensor on the surface of the cell and permit regulation of intracellular signalling and cell function in response to changes in a particular extracellular protease (Jiang *et al.*, 2017). Pharmacologically, one could modify synthetic peptide ligands to differentially alter signalling and function, which raises the prospect of differential control of individual signalling pathways linked to different state of disease (McIntosh *et al.*, 2020). Ligand-induced biased signalling through G protein coupled receptors is an evolving research area which has promising advantages from fine tuning compounds to specifically modulating one intracellular pathway associated with disease pathology, without affecting other pathways associated with the same receptor and normal physiology (Jiang *et al.*, 2017).

In terms of G-protein-dependent signalling, PAR2 couples to G protein α subunits $G\alpha_{q/11}$, $G\alpha_i$ or $G\alpha_{12/13}$, dependent on cellular context (Chandrabalan and Ramachandran, 2021), thus, activating downstream signalling messengers and inducing multiple physiological effects. Macfarlane and colleagues showed that G protein-coupled receptors utilise at least two branches of signal transduction pathways to elicit cellular responses with each branch stimulating several pathways (Macfarlane *et al.*, 2005). These include the traditional G protein-dependent, and the more recently discovered β -arrestin-dependent signalling pathway (Walker & DeFea, 2014). PARs also signal through G protein-independent β -arrestin scaffolding protein that initiates RhoA, PI3K/Akt, and Src (ERK1/2) pathways. β -arrestin can also desensitise PARs through uncoupling G protein-coupled PARs (Adams *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, the two pathways are also temporally separable, with β -arrestin signalling sometimes occurring before the G-protein signalling pathway and at other times, exhibiting a delayed or prolonged signal (Ahn *et al.*, 2004; Zoudilova *et al.*, 2007). A study has highlighted that co-localisation of β -arrestin-1 and -2 following PAR2 activation induces ERK1/2 signalling (Stalheim *et al.*, 2005). Calcium mobilisation and PKC activation is triggered by G protein signalling which subsequently results in hydrolysis of phosphoinositide and production of inositol (1,4,5)-triphosphate (IP3) and diacylglycerol (DAG) (McLaughlin *et al.*, 2005). Changes in intracellular Ca^{2+} are key to the function of smooth muscle and these changes can be sustained, cell-wide increases or localised changes (Hill-Eubanks *et al.*, 2011). An interesting finding within the cellular investigations involving PAR2, was a dose-dependent Ca^{2+} increase in response to PAR2 activating peptide FLIGRLO-NH₂, indicating that PAR2 uses calcium flux as a signalling mechanism to mediate as yet undetermined downstream effects in hBSMC. This highlights a need for better understanding the function of the receptor and its activating proteases present within disease, in both isolated cells and tissue where interactions are intact.

Murine studies have highlighted that PAR2 activation can play opposing roles in allergic asthma by mediating both potent bronchorelaxation and increased inflammation (Nichols *et al.*, 2012) as well as bronchoconstriction (Rivas *et al.*, 2022). The current study using a FLIGRLO-NH₂ dose response reinforces a bronchorelaxation role of PAR2 in isolated murine airways in both bronchial and tracheal murine rings. Importantly, this first use of a PAR2^{-/-} model revealed an abolished relaxation in response to FLIGRLO-NH₂ stimulation.

The investigation of sex on the bronchodilatory role of PAR2 highlighted no difference in the PAR2-dependent response between male and female airways. The results from this study suggest that known sex-based differences in COPD susceptibility are not likely to be based on differential PAR2 function in airways.

The investigation of PAR2-dependent bronchorelaxation within this study builds on previous findings to explore disease-relevant conditions. A major risk factor for COPD is an environment promoting oxidative stress, which is now recognised as being a major predisposing factor in driving pathogenesis, specifically oxidative inactivation of antiproteases, smooth muscle hyperplasia and remodelling of extracellular matrix, all *via* inflammation (Kirkham & Barnes, 2013). The results from this portion of the study indicate that even short-term *ex vivo* oxidative stress has potential to impact both the function and expression of PAR2, as well as COPD associated features of the lungs and airways involved in remodelling, such as collagen and smooth muscle. This highlights the importance of PAR2 as a potential regulator of BSM pathophysiology due to its ability to enhance broncho-relaxation in a disease setting. The data confirms a bronchodilatory effect of PAR2 that is dependent on ROS and is not only maintained but enhanced during oxidative stress, at least in this experimental model. This represents a first insight into the role of PAR2 in modulating bronchial tone in oxidative stress. A more detailed future characterisation will build on this work to further explore pathogenic mechanisms that may be relevant to the development of COPD. However, the current findings provide the insight that any future strategy to ameliorate inflammation by targeting PAR2 antagonism in the epithelia would need to consider potential impact of loss of smooth muscle-mediated bronchoprotective relaxation.

Myography studies utilising exogenous antioxidant as a 'rescue' approach emphasised that an increase in ROS underpinned a subsequent increase in PAR2-dependent bronchorelaxation, indicating a further factor to be considered if PAR2 was to be targeted to reduce inflammation. Antioxidants, specifically SOD1, have the potential to be a therapeutic strategy in inflammatory disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis (Salvemini *et al.*, 1999). The use of SOD1 as an antioxidant and therapeutic agent in acute and chronic inflammatory conditions has been previously reported in the literature (Bowler *et al.*, 2004; Younus, 2018).

PAR2-mediated Ca²⁺ signalling is involved in both intra and extracellular processes that regulate cellular functions. The calcium signalling pathways interact with other cellular signalling systems such as ROS, with increasing evidence supporting interplay between the two systems (Görlach *et al.*, 2015). In a study within the vascular setting, PAR2-mediated calcium signalling resulted in nitric oxide synthase (NOS) activation and subsequent relaxation of vascular smooth muscle relaxation (McGuire, Dai, *et al.*, 2002). This supported the observations previously reported in the literature indicating that there is a prerequisite role of NOS in PAR2-mediated vasodilation (Moffatt and Cocks, 1998). This dependence on NOS for PAR2-mediated smooth muscle relaxation identified could allude to the mechanism underpinning both basal and oxidative stress-enhanced bronchorelaxation (Hsieh *et al.*, 2014). Future work could explore whether PAR2 activation can regulate contraction in isolated hBSMC, and if oxidative stress and exogenous antioxidants could modulate such a response.

Tissue remodelling, a hallmark of arthritic diseases, is also a common feature of COPD pathology and so investigating the impact of risk factors associated with the disease on tissue remodelling is important to understand disease mechanisms. The most abundant component of the extracellular matrix is collagen type I, which provides structural support and is a primary contributor to lung and airway mechanics (Suki & Bates, 2008; Yue, 2014), and this study found significant increases in collagen abundance under oxidative stress. Although more collagen was observed in PAR2-deficient lungs, an oxidative stress-dependent collagen increase was observed regardless of PAR2 status, indicating that this phenomenon is PAR2-independent in murine lung.

Overall, results from this portion of the study show that short-term *ex vivo* oxidative stress has an impact on both the function and expression of PAR2 and COPD associated features of the lungs and airways involved in remodelling, such as collagen and smooth muscle. This highlights the potential importance of PAR2 in BSM pathophysiology due to its ability to enhance broncho-relaxation in a disease-relevant setting. The data confirms a bronchodilatory effect of PAR2 that is dependent on ROS and is not only maintained but enhanced during oxidative stress in this experimental model. This represents a first insight into the role of PAR2 in modulating bronchial tone in oxidative stress. A more detailed future characterisation will build on this work to further explore pathogenic mechanisms that may be relevant to the development of COPD.

Key findings revealed in the data included the impact of age in reducing both PAR2 expression and PAR2-dependent bronchorelaxation. The loss of PAR2 and thus bronchoprotective response in older animals could be interpreted as potentially contributing to the increased development of pathology and loss of function with age. The process of ageing affects the function and the overall structure of the airways and respiratory muscles which results in changes of respiratory flow, a decrease in lung volume and an overall increase in residual volume. All of these features appear progressively with age and could be partly explained by changes in PAR2-dependent relaxation tissue from older animals (Occhipinti *et al.*, 2017). At present the only existing report of age-dependent changes in PAR2 response was in rat aortic rings (Maruyama *et al.*, 2017). To summarise, the loss of PAR2 bronchoprotection may be highly relevant to COPD, as a disease associated with advancing and accelerated ageing, and a key feature of the disease pathology is hypercontractility (Mercado *et al.*, 2015; MacNee, 2016; Yan *et al.*, 2018). The loss of smooth muscle actin concomitant with reduced (age) or absent (KO) PAR2 expression are also consistent with a role for PAR2 in airway smooth muscle.

The investigations of disease-relevant challenges described were utilised in part due to the limitations and technical difficulties associated with current murine models for COPD-related changes, though much effort has been made in recent years to address this problem (Ghorani *et al.*, 2017). The investigation in the final chapter of this study explored the possibility of using an inflammatory arthritis model (CIA) for a disease that is an important COPD co-morbidity (RA) to investigate the mechanisms underpinning lung pathology that might be common. CIA, regarded as the ‘gold standard’ preclinical model for RA, allows the use of a well-established model to assess similarities in murine lung pathology that may be present in the model with those seen in RA-ILD, and to tentatively explore whether mechanisms observed might extrapolate to early COPD development, particularly in patient cohorts suffering this co-morbidity.

In COPD patients, a common pathophysiological feature is thickening of the airway walls causing obstruction of airflow (Polosukhin *et al.*, 2021). The results presented in the study of CIA lungs reveal similarities with both RA-ILD and certain features of COPD in the context of airway wall thickening and architectural changes. It has also been reported that patients with rheumatoid arthritis commonly experience disease of the airways, as a result of inflammation that destroys the bronchi (Sakai, 2018, Mori *et al.*, 2018), whilst it is thought that the thickening observed in the airway walls of COPD patients is due to a combination of inflammatory changes and remodelling (Shantanam, 2018). It has also been proposed that inflammatory changes in the small airways may secondarily induce mucosal oedema, which subsequently leads to bronchial narrowing and obstruction of the airways (Hassan *et al.*, 1994).

The significant increase in collagen levels observed in the parenchyma of the CIA samples is of interest regarding the remodelling of the lung tissue in disease pathology, alongside its normal structural roles. It could also be suggested that collagen deposition in and around specific alveoli could expose neighbouring alveoli to potentially harmful forces of expansion. If an alveolus in the earlier stage of emphysema is surrounded by alveoli that are in the repair phase, the effects could be even more exaggerated and harmful to bordering alveoli, creating a knock on effect of disease pathology (Foronjy and D’Armiento, 2001). In relation to COPD specifically, collagen-focused studies have demonstrated a significant increase in collagen abundance in alveoli of COPD patients displaying the phenotype of emphysema compared with the non-emphysematous samples (Vlahovic *et al.*, 1999, Martín-Mosquero *et al.*, 2006). Patients with COPD were found to have an increased expression of total collagens I, III, and IV in the basement membrane and an increased expression collagens I and III in bronchial lamina propria and adventitia (Kranenburg *et al.*, 2006). It was also revealed by this study that COPD is associated with an increased deposition of ECM components in the bronchial airway, suggesting that this may contribute to airway remodelling and obstruction to airflow (Kranenburg *et al.*, 2006). It has been suggested that the activation of the nuclear-factor $\kappa\beta$ pathway triggers metabolic alterations leading to the degradation of muscle tissue and thus could allude to the changes observed in disease pathology (Li, Malhotra and Kumar, 2008).

PAR2 is commonly associated with an inflammatory state within tissues and is well reported to be involved in the pathology of both OA and RA including roles in synovial hyperplasia, destruction of

cartilage and pain (Sokolove and Lepus, 2013). However, in this study, no significant change in PAR2 expression was identified. This result is not what was anticipated due to the proinflammatory capabilities of the receptor and the systemic inflammation associated with the condition of RA-ILD (Shaw, Collins, *et al.*, 2015). However, a study investigating the expression of PAR2 in COPD patients and bronchial asthma patients also identified that there were no significant changes in the expression of the receptor between the two groups (Matěj *et al.*, 2014). This indicates that perhaps despite an inflammatory environment in certain lung pathologies such as COPD and RA-ILD, receptor expression is not significantly increased as hypothesised. However, activation of PAR2 may be nonetheless increased, through increased protease load.

It is well known that neutrophil invasion is a key factor in COPD development and so products of activated neutrophils, such as NE, are likely contributors to the destruction of ECM in airway walls and lung parenchymal tissue (Hoenderdos and Condliffe, 2013; Polosukhin *et al.*, 2021). The changes to the lung in RA-ILD are similar to that of emphysema due to the honeycomb-like destructive changes that are observed following inflammation (Sugitani *et al.*, 2018). The small airways also exhibit changes similar to COPD pathology, including bronchial wall thickening causing airflow obstruction (Wilsher *et al.*, 2012). This known ability to cause destruction to the ECM in RA-ILD may help reflect the architectural changes observed in the parenchymal tissue of the CIA samples. As COPD is often associated with neutrophilic inflammation, the secretion of NE from active neutrophils has been proposed to be a biomarker of COPD, particularly during bacterial infection (Thulborn *et al.*, 2019). It has also been reported that increases of NE in COPD patients have been associated with exacerbations, a decline in lung function and also disease severity (Muhlebach *et al.*, 2016; Chalmers *et al.*, 2017). The emphysematous phenotype and decrease in alveolar septal width observed in the CIA samples are both modifications of the lung similarly observed in COPD patients (Sharafkhaneh, Hanania and Kim, 2008). Overall, these changes highlight the potential to use the CIA murine model, as a model for not only arthritis but also potentially for lung disease associated with RA, which may even offer insight into the early development of COPD pathology in patients suffering RA-COPD co-morbidity.

Mice represent a suitable organism to establish COPD models due to the genetic compatibilities with humans, ease of breeding and their high survival rates within disease models (Yang *et al.*, 2021). Current models use defined exposures such as cigarette smoke extract and protease challenge to recapitulate common hallmark features observed in COPD. The lung changes observed in CIA hint at the potential for this system to represent a novel class of preclinical COPD model based on investigating mechanisms underlying co-morbidities, rather than on exposures. This direction could help indicate novel avenues for developing stratified/patient-directed medicine as COPD given the highly heterogeneous nature of COPD.

7.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, the role of PAR2 in airway smooth muscle is complex but this study reaffirms using a combination of activators and a transgenic model that the receptor has a protective function in bronchial reactivity. In addition, novel evidence is presented that PAR2 response is impacted in COPD-relevant conditions. Furthermore, this work highlights the potential to utilise a well-established arthritis disease model to investigate lung disease mechanisms relevant to COPD. In corollary, these findings give further support to the notion that modulating PAR2 activity may be viable as a route toward novel therapeutic strategies for COPD and suggests further investigation on the mechanism of its action is warranted at cellular, whole tissue and organismal levels.

Chapter 8: References

8. References

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Appendix I: Publications

Poster Presentations

BREATH Launch event: November 2017, Dundalk, Ireland.

BREATH annual conference: June 2018, Dundalk, Ireland.

University of the West of Scotland Health Symposium: May 2018, Lanarkshire, Scotland.

Irish Thoracic Society meeting: Irish Journal of Medical Science, 187, S249-S249. November 2018, Belfast, Northern Ireland.

University of the West of Scotland annual research conference: June 2019, Paisley, Scotland.

British Association for Lung Research meeting: September 2019, Cambridge, England.

European Respiratory Society meeting: European Respiratory Journal, 56, 1895, Virtual, September 2020.

Oral Presentations

BREATH Launch event: November 2017, Dundalk, Ireland.

Institute for Biomedical Health Research Presentation: December 2017, Paisley, Scotland.

BREATH annual conference: June 2018, Dundalk, Ireland. **Oral presentation prize winner.**

University of the West of Scotland Health Symposium: May 2019, Lanarkshire, Scotland. **Commendation prize winner.**

BREATH annual conference: June 2019, Belfast, Northern Ireland.

Irish Thoracic Society meeting: Irish Journal of Medical Science, 188, 286-286. November 2019, Galway, Ireland. **Oral presentation prize winner.**

BREATH annual conference: June 2020, Virtual, hosted by UWS.

BREATH annual conference: June 2021, Virtual, hosted by DkIT.

Publications

Proteinase activated receptor 2 (PAR2) modulation of airway smooth muscle function

K. Black¹, A. MacKenzie¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, L. McGarvey², K. Thornbury³, C.S. Goodyear⁴, J.C. Lockhart¹, G.J. Litherland¹

¹Border & REgions Airways Training Hub, Centre for Musculoskeletal Science, Institute of Biomedical and Environmental Health Research, School of Health & Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, Scotland. ²Queens University Belfast. ³Dundalk Institute of Technology. ⁴Institute of Infection, Immunity & Inflammation, University of Glasgow.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a progressive lung condition characterised by airflow obstruction and irreversible lung damage. Hyperactivity and growth of airway smooth muscle (ASM) limit airflow and are key features of COPD. Proteinase activated receptor-2 (PAR2) is a key modulator of inflammatory responses in respiratory disease, such as asthma and promotes ASM relaxation. However, the precise role of the receptor in ASM in conditions such as COPD is not well understood (Sokolova and Reiser, 2007). The aim of this study was to establish an *ex vivo* murine airway myograph assay for investigation of functional PAR2 responses to challenges relevant in COPD pathology. To achieve this, murine trachea and bronchi tissue was either mounted on a wire myograph for dynamic tension recording or processed for immunohistochemical localisation of PAR2 expression. PAR2 was present on both murine airway and lung tissue. Stimulation of PAR2 with trypsin (10 U ml⁻¹) or activating peptide was observed to induce relaxation responses in ASM tension. Taken together this data verifies that PAR2 is present and functional in murine airways, and *ex vivo* modulation alters ASM tone. Ongoing experiments will investigate the effect of disease-relevant insults on this modulation in wild type and PAR2-deficient airways.

1. Sokolova E, Reiser G. A novel therapeutic target in various lung diseases: Airway proteases and protease-activated receptors. *Pharmacol Ther.* 2007;115(1):70–83.

This study was funded by the EU under the Interreg VA Programme, managed by the Special EU programmes body (SEUPB)

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Enhanced airway smooth muscle relaxation via proteinase activated receptor 2

K. Black¹, A. MacKenzie¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, J. Brzezczynska¹, L. McGarvey², K. Thornbury³, C.S. Goodyear⁴, J.C. Lockhart¹, G.J. Litherland¹

¹Border & REgions Airways Training Hub, Institute of Biomedical and Environmental Health Research, School of Health & Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, Scotland.

²Queens University Belfast, Belfast, Northern Ireland. ³Dundalk Institute of Technology, Dundalk, Ireland. ⁴Institute of Infection, Immunity & Inflammation, University of Glasgow.

Hyper-reactivity, inflammation and hyperplasia/hypertrophy of airway smooth muscle (ASM) limit airflow and are key features of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Proteinase activated receptor 2 (PAR2) is a critical modulator of inflammatory responses in respiratory disease such as asthma yet is reported to promote ASM relaxation. However, the role of ASM PAR2 in COPD is not well understood¹.

Our aim was to determine the presence and role of PAR2 in murine lung and ASM subjected to oxidative stress using both immunohistochemistry (IHC) and wire myography.

PAR2 was detected using APR-32 antibody (Alomone, Israel) on both murine airway and lung tissue, with clean isotype.

Oxidative stress increased trypsin-induced ASM relaxation in both bronchial and tracheal tissue. This was PAR2 dependent, as relaxation was significantly reduced in PAR2^{-/-} compared with WT tracheal (mean \pm SEM; WT 53.4 \pm 13.4 % vs. PAR2^{-/-} 2.5 \pm 0.8 %; $p=0.02$; $n=3-4$) and bronchial tissue (WT 56 \pm 13.3 % vs. PAR2^{-/-} 2.3 \pm 0.9 %; $p=0.02$; $n=3-4$).

In conclusion, this study confirms a functional PAR2 role in murine airway tissue; importantly, the role of PAR2 in mediating ASM relaxation appears to be enhanced in oxidative environments such as found in COPD. This may have important implications for future potential therapies.

1. Sokolova E, Reiser G. A novel therapeutic target in various lung diseases: Airway proteases and protease-activated receptors. *Pharmacol Ther.* 2007;115(1):70–83.

This study was funded by the EU under the Interreg VA Programme, managed by the Special EU programmes body (SEUPB)

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Murine airway bronchodilation via Proteinase Activated Receptor 2

K. Black¹, A. MacKenzie¹, L. Dunning¹, A. Crilly¹, J. Brzezczynska¹, L. McGarvey², K. Thornbury³, C.S. Goodyear⁴, J.C. Lockhart¹, G.J. Litherland¹

¹Border & REgions Airways Training Hub, Institute of Biomedical and Environmental Health Research, School of Health & Life Sciences, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, Scotland.

²Queens University Belfast, Belfast, Northern Ireland. ³Dundalk Institute of Technology, Dundalk, Ireland. ⁴Institute of Infection, Immunity & Inflammation, University of Glasgow.

Hyper-reactivity, inflammation and hyperplasia/hypertrophy of airway smooth muscle (ASM) limit airflow and are key features of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Proteinase activated receptor 2 (PAR2) is a critical modulator of inflammatory responses in respiratory disease such as asthma, yet is reported to promote ASM relaxation. However, the role of ASM PAR2 in COPD is not well understood (Sokolova, E. *et al.* *Pharmacol Ther.* 2007; 115(1):70-83).

Our aim was to determine the presence and role of PAR2 in murine lung and ASM subjected to an oxidative stressor environment using both immunohistochemistry (IHC) and wire myography. PAR2 was detected using APR-32 antibody (Alomone, Israel) on both murine airway and lung tissue, with clean isotype. Data presented as mean \pm SEM.

An oxidative stressor environment increased trypsin-induced ASM relaxation in both bronchial (Oxidative 54.5 \pm 8.5 % vs. Control 35.1 \pm 3.7 %; $n=6$; $p<0.05$; *paired t-test*) and tracheal tissue (Oxidative 56.7 \pm 10.5 % vs. Control 30.3 \pm 2.9 %; $n=6$; $p=0.052$; *paired t-test*). This was PAR2 dependent, as relaxation to trypsin was virtually abolished in PAR2^{-/-} compared with WT tracheal (WT 56.7 \pm 10.5 % vs. PAR2^{-/-} 2.5 \pm 0.7 %; $n=3-6$; $p<0.01$; *unpaired t-test*) and bronchial tissue (WT 54.5 \pm 8.5 % vs. PAR2^{-/-} 2.3 \pm 0.9 %; $n=3-6$; $p<0.01$; *unpaired t-test*). Further confirmation of PAR2 dependent relaxation was achieved using a PAR2 specific peptide (2-FLIGRLO-NH₂).

In conclusion, this study confirms a functional PAR2 role in murine airway tissue; importantly, the role of PAR2 in mediating ASM relaxation appears to be enhanced in oxidative environments such as found in COPD. This may have important implications for future potential therapies.

This study was funded by the EU under the Interreg VA Programme, managed by the Special EU programmes body (SEUPB)

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Published: 28/10/2020**

Figure I.1: Breath annual conference. June 2018, Dundalk, Ireland. Oral presentation prize winner. Photo reuse with permission from John C Lockhart.

Figure I.2: University of the West of Scotland Health Symposium. May 2019, Lanarkshire, Scotland. Commendation prize winner. Photo reuse with permission from John C Lockhart.

@Breath_COPD PHD success:
@UniWestScotland PhD student @kimberlyblack_
receives @irishthoracicS runner up prize for best oral
presentation at #Galway 2019 meeting, awarded by
Professor McGarvey. Congratulations Kimberly and
team. @SEUPB @INTERREGTweets

Figure I.3: Irish Thoracic Society meeting. November 2019, Galway, Ireland. Irish Journal of Medical Science, 188, 286-286. Oral presentation prize winner. Photo reuse with permission from John C Lockhart.